

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO

Scuola di Dottorato in Fisica, Astrofisica e Fisica Applicata

Dipartimento di Fisica

Corso di Dottorato in Fisica, Astrofisica e Fisica Applicata

Ciclo XXXVII

Measurement of the magnetic and electric dipole moments of the Λ baryon at LHCb

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Anno Accademico 2024-2025

VNIVERSITATIS VALÈNCIA

Escuela de doctorado

Departament de Física Atòmica, Molecular i Nuclear

Programa de Doctorat en Física

Measurement of the magnetic and electric dipole moments of the Λ baryon at LHCb

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Juny 2025

Final examination:

Date: 30 September 2025

Place: Università degli Studi di Milano, Dipartimento di Fisica, Milano, Italy

Abstract

One of the most profound and unresolved questions in modern physics is why the Universe is composed predominantly of matter, with negligible antimatter. This imbalance suggests the existence of processes that violate the fundamental symmetry between matter and antimatter, the so-called CP symmetry. However, the amount of CP violation predicted by the Standard Model of particle physics (SM), via the Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) quark-mixing mechanism, cannot explain the large observed asymmetry, thus new sources of CP violation, beyond the SM, are expected. A possible way to probe such sources is to search for electric dipole moments (EDMs) of fundamental particles. This thesis explores that possibility through the study of the Λ baryon: an EDM observation with the current sensitivities would constitute evidence of CP violation beyond the SM. Moreover, the magnetic dipole moment (MDM) of the Λ baryon and the $\bar{\Lambda}$ antibaryon will be measured simultaneously, allowing an unprecedented test of the CPT symmetry in this particle-antiparticle system. Notably, the MDM of the $\bar{\Lambda}$ antibaryon has never been measured to date. All these measurements of the Λ baryon electric and magnetic dipole moments are performed for the first time at a collider experiment.

The analysis is conducted using data collected by the LHCb experiment during the Run 1 and Run 2 of the LHC, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of about 9 fb^{-1} . The LHCb detector was designed to investigate CP-violating phenomena of beauty and charm hadrons. This thesis describes how its capabilities have been extended to enable investigations of dipole moments of strange baryons. The measurement relies on the spin precession of longitudinally polarized Λ baryons in the magnetic field of the LHCb tracking system. The polarization is inferred via an angular analysis of the Λ decay products. A novel aspect of this work is the use of particles that decay downstream of the LHCb magnet, reconstructed solely with hits in the final tracking stations. These so-called T tracks present significant challenges in the reconstruction due to their limited momentum and vertex resolutions. Their exploitation in physics analyses is being pioneered in the context of this study.

To overcome the performance limitations, a dedicated study to improve the reconstruction of long-lived Λ and K_S^0 decays using T tracks has been conducted in the first part of the thesis, developing custom techniques with significant impact on the reconstruction efficiency and resolutions. In the second part, the measurement of the electric and magnetic dipole moments is performed using $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays. The analysis is validated using $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays as control sample, in which the long-lived K_S^0 meson, being a pseudoscalar particle, does not exhibit any polarization nor dipole moments. The measurement of dipole moments is performed on the control sample as a null test to validate the method before applying it to the signal decays.

The LHCb detector has undergone a major upgrade for the data-taking during Run 3 of the LHC. In this context, the new detector is briefly presented, with a particular focus on the Upstream Tracker. The author of this thesis contributed to this subsystem during its assembly, installation, and commissioning phases.

Resumen

Una de las preguntas más profundas aún sin resolver de la física moderna es por qué el Universo está compuesto predominantemente por materia, con una cantidad insignificante de antimateria. Este desequilibrio sugiere la existencia de procesos que rompen la simetría fundamental entre materia y antimateria, la llamada simetría de conjugación de carga-paridad (CP). Sin embargo, la cantidad de violación de CP predicha por el Modelo Estándar de la física de partículas (ME) a través del mecanismo de mezcla de quarks de Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) no puede explicar la gran asimetría observada, por lo que se esperan nuevas fuentes de ruptura de CP más allá del ME. Una posible vía para explorar dichas fuentes es la búsqueda de momentos dipolares eléctricos (EDMs) en partículas fundamentales. Esta tesis investiga dicha posibilidad mediante el estudio del barión Λ : la observación de un EDM con las sensibilidades experimentales actuales constituiría una evidencia de ruptura de CP más allá del ME. Además, se mide de manera simultánea el momento dipolar magnético (MDM) del barión Λ y del antibarión $\bar{\Lambda}$, lo que permite una prueba sin precedentes de la simetría combinada de CP e inversión temporal T (CPT) en este sistema partícula-antipartícula. Es relevante destacar que, hasta la fecha, nunca se ha medido el MDM del antibarión $\bar{\Lambda}$. Todas estas medidas se realizan por primera vez en un experimento de colisionador.

El análisis se lleva a cabo utilizando datos registrados por el experimento LHCb durante el Run 1 y el Run 2 del LHC, correspondientes a una luminosidad integrada de unos 9 fb^{-1} . El detector LHCb fue diseñado para estudiar fenómenos de ruptura de CP en hadrones con belleza y encanto. Esta tesis describe cómo sus capacidades se han ampliado para permitir el estudio de momentos dipolares en bariones extraños. Las medidas se basan en la precesión de espín de bariones Λ longitudinalmente polarizados en el seno del campo magnético de LHCb. La polarización se infiere mediante un análisis angular de los productos de desintegración de barión Λ . Un aspecto novedoso es el uso de partículas que se desintegran en la región del imán de LHCb, y que son reconstruidas utilizando únicamente las señales del subsistema de trazas más alejado del punto de interacción pp . Estas así llamadas trazas T representan un desafío para la reconstrucción debido a sus limitadas resoluciones en momento y vértice. Su uso para análisis de física en LHCb se está explorando por primera vez en el contexto de esta tesis.

Para superar estas limitaciones, en la primera parte de la tesis se ha llevado a cabo un estudio para mejorar la reconstrucción de desintegraciones de partículas de larga vida como son los hadrones Λ y K_S^0 empleando la trazas T, desarrollando para ello técnicas dedicadas que tienen un impacto significativo en la eficiencia y la resolución de la reconstrucción. En la segunda parte se realiza la medida de los momentos dipolares eléctrico y magnético usando procesos de desintegración $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\Psi\Lambda$. El análisis se valida utilizando una muestra de control que contiene desintegraciones $B^0 \rightarrow J/\Psi K_S^0$, ya que el mesón K_S^0 , al ser una partícula pseudoscalar, no presenta polarización ni momentos dipolares. Las medidas en la muestra de control representan un prueba nula para validar el procedimiento de medida antes de aplicarlo a los sucesos de señal.

El detector LHCb ha sido objeto de una gran actualización para la toma de datos durante el Run 3 del LHC. En este contexto, se presenta brevemente el nuevo detector, con especial énfasis en el *Upstream Tracker*. La autora de esta tesis ha contribuido a este subsistema durante las fases de montaje, instalación y puesta en marcha.

Resum

Una de les preguntes més profundes encara sense resoldre de la física moderna és per què l'Univers està compost predominantment per matèria, amb una quantitat insignificant d'antimatèria. Aquest desequilibri suggereix l'existència de processos que trenquen la simetria fonamental entre matèria i antimatèria, l'anomenada simetria de conjugació de càrrega-paritat (CP). No obstant això, la quantitat de violació de CP predita pel Model Estàndard de la física de partícules (ME) a través del mecanisme de mescla de quarks de Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) no pot explicar la gran asimetria observada, per la qual cosa s'esperen noves fonts de ruptura de CP més enllà del ME. Una possible via per a explorar aquestes fonts és la cerca de moments dipolars elèctrics (EDMs) en partícules fonamentals. Aquesta tesi investiga aquesta possibilitat mitjançant l'estudi del barió Λ : l'observació d'un EDM amb les sensibilitats experimentals actuals constituiria una evidència de ruptura de CP més enllà del ME. A més, es mesura de manera simultània el moment dipolar magnètic (MDM) del barió Λ i de l'antibarió $\bar{\Lambda}$, la qual cosa permet una prova sense precedents de la simetria combinada de CP i inversió temporal T (CPT) en aquest sistema partícula-antipartícula. És rellevant destacar que, fins a la data, mai s'ha mesurat el MDM de l'antibarió $\bar{\Lambda}$. Totes aquestes mesures es realitzen per primera vegada en un experiment de col·lisionador.

L'anàlisi es duu a terme utilitzant dades registrades per l'experiment LHCb durant el Run 1 i el Run 2 del LHC, corresponents a una lluminositat integrada d'uns 9 fb^{-1} . El detector LHCb va ser dissenyat per a estudiar fenòmens de ruptura de CP en hadrons amb bellesa i encant. Aquesta tesi descriu com les seues capacitats s'han ampliat per a permetre l'estudi de moments dipolars en barions estranys. Les mesures es basen en la precessió d'espín de barions Λ longitudinalment polaritzats en el si del camp magnètic de LHCb. La polarització s'infereix mitjançant una anàlisi angular dels productes de desintegració de barió Λ . Un aspecte nou és l'ús de partícules que es desintegren a la regió de l'imant de LHCb, i que són reconstruïdes utilitzant únicament els senyals del subsistema de traces més allunyat del punt d'interacció pp . Aquestes així anomenades traces T representen un desafiament per a la reconstrucció a causa de les seues limitades resolucions en moment i vèrtex. El seu ús per a anàlisi de física en LHCb s'està explorant per primera vegada en el context d'aquesta tesi.

Per a superar aquestes limitacions, en la primera part de la tesi s'ha dut a terme un estudi dedicat per a millorar la reconstrucció de desintegracions de partícules de llarga vida com són els hadrons Λ i K_S^0 emprant la traces T, desenvolupant per a això tècniques dedicades que tenen un impacte significatiu en l'eficiència i la resolució de la reconstrucció. En la segona part es realitza la mesura dels moments dipolars elèctric i magnètic usant processos de desintegració $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\Psi \Lambda$. L'anàlisi es valida utilitzant una mostra de control que conté desintegracions $B^0 \rightarrow J/\Psi K_S^0$, ja que el mesó K_S^0 , a ser una partícula pseudoscalar, no presenta polarització ni moments dipolars. La mesura dels moments dipolars en la mostra de control representa una prova nul·la per a validar el procediment de mesura abans d'aplicar-lo als successos de senyal.

El detector LHCb ha sigut objecte d'una gran actualització per a la presa de dades durant el Run 3 del LHC. En aquest context, es presenta breument el nou detector, amb especial èmfasi en el *Upstream Tracker*. L'autora d'aquesta tesi ha contribuït a aquest subsistema durant les fases de muntatge, instal·lació i posada en marxa.

Riassunto

Una delle domande più profonde e ancora irrisolte della fisica moderna è perché l'Universo sia composto prevalentemente da materia, con una quantità trascurabile di antimateria. Questo squilibrio suggerisce l'esistenza di processi che violano la simmetria fondamentale tra materia e antimateria, la cosiddetta simmetria CP. Tuttavia, l'entità della violazione CP prevista dal Modello Standard della fisica delle particelle (SM), attraverso il meccanismo di mescolamento dei quark di Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM), non è sufficiente a spiegare l'ampia asimmetria osservata; ci si aspetta quindi l'esistenza di nuove fonti di violazione CP oltre il Modello Standard. Un possibile approccio per indagare tali fonti è la ricerca dei momenti di dipolo elettrico (EDM) delle particelle fondamentali. Questa tesi esplora tale possibilità attraverso lo studio del barione Λ : l'osservazione di un EDM con le attuali sensibilità costituirebbe una prova della violazione CP oltre il Modello Standard. Inoltre, verrà misurato contemporaneamente il momento di dipolo magnetico (MDM) del barione Λ e dell'antibarione $\bar{\Lambda}$, permettendo un test senza precedenti della simmetria CPT in questo sistema particella-antiparticella. È importante sottolineare che, fino ad oggi, il MDM dell'antibarione $\bar{\Lambda}$ non è mai stato misurato. Tutte queste misure dei momenti di dipolo elettrico e magnetico del barione Λ vengono effettuate per la prima volta in un esperimento su collisore.

L'analisi è stata condotta utilizzando i dati raccolti dall'esperimento LHCb durante il Run 1 e il Run 2 del LHC, corrispondenti a una luminosità integrata di circa 9 fb^{-1} . Il rivelatore LHCb è stato progettato per studiare i fenomeni di violazione CP nei adroni contenenti quark beauty e charm. In questa tesi si descrive come le sue capacità siano state estese per permettere lo studio dei momenti di dipolo dei barioni strani. La misura si basa sulla precessione dello spin dei barioni Λ polarizzati all'interno del campo magnetico del sistema di tracciamento di LHCb. La polarizzazione viene determinata mediante un'analisi angolare dei prodotti di decadimento del Λ . Un aspetto innovativo di questo lavoro è l'utilizzo di particelle che decadono a valle del magnete di LHCb, ricostruite esclusivamente con segnali nelle stazioni di tracciamento successive al magnete. Queste tracce vengono chiamate T tracks e rappresentano una sfida significativa per la ricostruzione, a causa delle limitate risoluzioni in impulso e vertice. Il loro utilizzo in analisi fisiche viene esplorato per la prima volta in questo lavoro.

Nella prima parte della tesi è stato condotto uno studio dedicato per migliorare la ricostruzione dei decadimenti a lunga vita media di Λ e K_S^0 utilizzando le T tracks, sviluppando tecniche specifiche con un impatto significativo sull'efficienza e la risoluzione della ricostruzione. Nella seconda parte, viene effettuata la misura dei momenti di dipolo elettrico e magnetico attraverso i decadimenti $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$. L'analisi viene validata utilizzando i decadimenti $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ come campione di controllo, poiché il mesone K_S^0 , essendo una particella pseudoscalare, non presenta né polarizzazione né momenti di dipolo. La misura sui decadimenti di controllo rappresenta un test nullo per validare il metodo prima di applicarlo ai decadimenti segnale.

Il rivelatore LHCb ha subito un importante aggiornamento per la presa dati durante il Run 3 del LHC. In questo contesto, il nuovo rivelatore viene brevemente descritto, con particolare attenzione all'Upstream Tracker, dal momento che l'autrice di questa tesi ha contribuito a questo sottosistema durante le fasi di assemblaggio, installazione e presa data.

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Flavour physics and electromagnetic dipole moments

1.1 Flavour physics in the Standard Model and beyond

1.1.1 The Standard Model

Our understanding of the fundamental constituents of matter and their interactions has been shaped by decades of experimental and theoretical work. Since the 1930s, physicists have established that all known physical phenomena can be described by four fundamental interactions: the electromagnetic, weak and strong nuclear forces, and gravity [1]. The theoretical framework that unifies our current understanding of these interactions, excluding gravity, is known as the *Standard Model of particle physics* (SM). Developed throughout the second half of the 20th century, the SM has been remarkably successful in describing the behavior of subatomic particles and has been confirmed by numerous experimental results [2].

Elementary particles, illustrated in Fig. 1.1, are divided into two main categories according to their spin. Particles with half-integer spin, known as fermions, are the constituents of matter. These include leptons and quarks. Leptons, such as the electron and neutrinos, interact via the electroweak force but do not participate in the strong interaction. Quarks, by contrast, interact through all three forces in the SM: strong, electromagnetic and weak. Both leptons and quarks are organized into three families (or generations), where particles in higher families are heavier but share the same charges and interactions. Particles with integer spin are called bosons, and they mediate the fundamental forces: the gluon for the strong force, the photon for electromagnetism, and the W^\pm and Z for the weak force. The Higgs boson, also a spin-0 boson, plays a unique role by enabling particles to acquire mass through their interaction with the Higgs field.

The SM is formulated as a quantum field theory based on the gauge symmetry group $SU(3)_C \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$. These symmetries give rise to the forces observed in nature. The strong interaction, described by $SU(3)_C$, binds quarks together inside hadrons through the exchange of the massless gluons, which carry a type of charge known as color. Depending on the presence of 2 or 3 quarks in the hadron, we call the particle meson or baryon. The electroweak interaction is generated by the $SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ symmetry and unifies the electromagnetic and weak forces. The electromagnetic force governs the interactions between charged particles through the exchange of the massless photons and it is responsible for phenomena ranging from atomic structure to light. The weak isospin representation $SU(2)_L$ describes how left-handed fermions transform as doublets under the weak interaction. This means that they form two-component vectors that are acted upon by the $SU(2)_L$ symmetry transformations. For instance, each

generation of leptons and quarks contains a weak isospin doublet of the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_e \\ e^- \end{pmatrix}_L, \quad \begin{pmatrix} u \\ d \end{pmatrix}_L,$$

which are said to belong to the fundamental representation of $SU(2)_L$, i.e., the 2-dimensional representation. Right-handed fermions, on the other hand, are singlets under $SU(2)_L$, meaning they do not transform under this symmetry and hence do not participate in weak charged-current interactions. The weak force is responsible for processes like beta decay and neutrino interactions and is mediated by the massive W^\pm and Z bosons. The electroweak symmetry is spontaneously broken via the Higgs mechanism, which gives mass to the weak bosons, leaving the photon massless and preserving a residual $U(1)_{em}$ symmetry associated with electromagnetism.

Figure 1.1: Fundamental particles of the SM. On the left the fermions: quarks (top) and leptons (bottom), while on the right are the gauge bosons.

Although the SM has collected extensive experimental validation, numerous indications suggest the necessity for a Beyond the Standard Model (BSM) theory. Some of the primary discrepancies between experimental observations and the SM include the following. We know that only about 5% of the Universe consists of ordinary matter, while approximately 27% is dark matter [3]. The nature of dark matter remains a mystery and cannot be explained by the SM. The remaining 70% of the Universe is composed of dark energy, which is even less understood than dark matter. While dark energy does not have any local gravitational effect, it influences the Universe on a global scale. Consequently, a significant incompatibility to address in the coming years is that between the SM and general relativity. To comprehensively describe all interactions, a BSM theory must also incorporate gravitational interactions.

Another intriguing observation is that neutrinos have mass, contrary to the assumptions of the SM. The discovery of the neutrino mass was initially suggested by observing

their oscillations between different flavour states. Following these measurements, mass terms for neutrinos were incorporated into the model, but this ad hoc addition presents some theoretical challenges. Neutrino masses are exceedingly small compared to those of other particles, and the reason for this disparity remains unclear. Additionally, it is essential to determine whether the mechanism by which neutrinos acquire mass is the same as that for the other SM particles.

Finally, the SM fails to explain the observed dominance of matter over antimatter in the Universe. One of the major open questions in cosmology is why the Universe is composed almost entirely of matter, while antimatter appears to be nearly absent. Antimatter can only be detected in high-energy environments, such as particle accelerators or cosmic rays, where it is produced in small amounts through interactions of primary particles with the interstellar medium.

The observed imbalance is quantified by the Baryon Asymmetry of the Universe (BAU) [4], defined as

$$\eta = \frac{n_B - n_{\bar{B}}}{n_\gamma} \sim \frac{n_B}{n_\gamma} \sim 6 \cdot 10^{-10}, \quad (1.1)$$

where n_B and $n_{\bar{B}}$ are the number densities of baryons and antibaryons, respectively, and n_γ is the photon number density, as inferred from measurements of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB). The approximation $\eta \sim n_B/n_\gamma$ holds because essentially no antibaryons are observed today. This small but nonzero value of η implies that, in the early Universe, there was an excess of baryons over antibaryons of the order of one part in a billion. In the context of the baryogenesis theory, as the Universe cooled down, the matter–antimatter pairs annihilation should have had stopped at the critical temperature at which the expansion rate exceeded the annihilation one. At this time the antibaryons could not find baryons to annihilate with and the residual baryon antibaryon asymmetry was ‘frozen out’. This tiny excess of baryons left is what now constitutes the visible matter in the cosmos. However, calculations show that such a freeze-out would only yield an asymmetry of order $\eta \sim 10^{-18}$ [5], which is eight orders of magnitude smaller than the observed value in Eq. 1.1 and it still represents an open puzzle. To dynamically generate the observed asymmetry from an initial symmetric state ($B = 0$) via baryon-number-violating interactions, Andrei Sakharov proposed in 1967 three necessary conditions, now known as the *Sakharov conditions* [6]:

- **Baryon number violation:** Processes must exist that violate baryon number conservation, so that an excess of baryons over antibaryons can be created.
- **C and CP violation:** Interactions must violate both charge conjugation (C) symmetry, which swaps particles with their antiparticles, and charge–parity (CP) symmetry, which in addition inverts spatial coordinates. Without these violations, any baryon-number-violating process would affect matter and antimatter equally. For example, if only C were violated but CP were preserved, then although decay rates for $X \rightarrow Y + B$ and $\bar{X} \rightarrow \bar{Y} + \bar{B}$ could differ for different helicities, their total rates would remain equal after summing over spins:

$$\Gamma(X \rightarrow Y_L B_L) = \Gamma(\bar{X} \rightarrow \bar{Y}_R \bar{B}_R) \quad (1.2)$$

$$\Gamma(X \rightarrow Y_R B_R) = \Gamma(\bar{X} \rightarrow \bar{Y}_L \bar{B}_L) \quad (1.3)$$

$$\Gamma(X \rightarrow Y_L B_L) + \Gamma(X \rightarrow Y_R B_R) = \Gamma(\bar{X} \rightarrow \bar{Y}_R \bar{B}_R) + \Gamma(\bar{X} \rightarrow \bar{Y}_L \bar{B}_L), \quad (1.4)$$

leading to no net baryon number generation. Therefore, both C and CP must be violated to allow asymmetric behavior between matter and antimatter.

Table 1.1: Effect of discrete transformations on some physical observables.

Observable		P -transformed	T -transformed	C -transformed
Space position	\mathbf{x}	$-\mathbf{x}$	\mathbf{x}	\mathbf{x}
Time	t	t	$-t$	t
Momentum	\mathbf{p}	$-\mathbf{p}$	$-\mathbf{p}$	\mathbf{p}
Angular momentum	\mathbf{J}	\mathbf{J}	$-\mathbf{J}$	\mathbf{J}
Spin	\mathbf{P}	\mathbf{P}	$-\mathbf{P}$	\mathbf{P}
Energy	E	E	E	E
Electric field	\mathbf{E}	$-\mathbf{E}$	\mathbf{E}	$-\mathbf{E}$
Magnetic field	\mathbf{B}	\mathbf{B}	$-\mathbf{B}$	$-\mathbf{B}$
Electric charge	q	q	q	$-q$

- **Departure from thermal equilibrium:** In thermal equilibrium, any process creating a baryon excess is exactly balanced by its inverse process, which destroys it. For instance:

$$\Gamma(X \rightarrow Y + B) = \Gamma(Y + B \rightarrow X) \quad (1.5)$$

holds in equilibrium, and prevents net baryon production. Only when the Universe is out of equilibrium a net asymmetry can be preserved.

In principle, the SM satisfies all three Sakharov conditions. Although baryon number is conserved at the classical level, it is violated non-perturbatively by quantum anomalies. These processes simultaneously violate baryon and lepton numbers by three units ($\Delta B = \Delta L = \pm 3$) and become significant at high temperatures, above the electroweak scale ($T > T_{EW} \sim 100 \text{ GeV}$), where the Higgs field undergoes a phase transition and acquires a non-zero vacuum expectation value.

The SM effectively incorporates C and CP symmetry violations, initially observed in muon and antimuon decays, and later in the $K_L^0 \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^-$ decays. However, the amount of CP violation (CPV) within the SM can only account for $\eta \sim 10^{-20}$ [7], far too small as compared to the observations. As a consequence, new sources of CP violation are being investigated by numerous experiments. In the following sections, CP violation within the SM will be thoroughly described and a possible new source of CPV is presented as main object of this thesis.

1.1.2 Discrete symmetries and CP violation

In particle physics, discrete symmetries are of great interest. Specifically, we will focus on parity (P), time-reversal (T), and charge-conjugation (C) symmetries, as well as their combinations, due to the physics motivations previously explained.

The parity transformation inverts the spatial components, and its effect on the main physical quantities is presented in Table 1.1. The parity operator acts on quantum states as follows,

$$P|\Psi(\vec{x}, t)\rangle = \eta_p|\Psi(-\vec{x}, t)\rangle, \quad (1.6)$$

and it is a unitary and hermitian operator with eigenvalues $\eta_p = \pm 1$, representing the parity quantum number. Initially, it was believed that P was a symmetry of all physical laws. However, in 1956, this belief began to vacillate due to the work of Lee and Yang [8]. The first experimental proof came from Wu and her collaborators [9], who demonstrated parity violation in weak interactions. Their experiment involved the β decay of ^{60}Co ,

which has a spin $J^P = 5^+$ and decays to an excited state of ^{60}Ni with a spin $J^P = 4^+$. If parity was conserved, the electron would be emitted isotropically by the polarized nucleus. To achieve polarized nuclei, the experiment was conducted in a magnetic field at low temperatures. An anthracene detector was used to count the rate of β decays, and anisotropy in the counting rate was measured by inverting the external magnetic field, proving parity violation in weak interactions.

The charge conjugation operator transforms a particle into its antiparticle and vice versa, reversing the sign of charges associated with quantum states. This operator is also unitary and hermitian, and its effect is described by

$$C|\Psi\rangle = \eta_C|\bar{\Psi}\rangle, \quad (1.7)$$

with $\eta_C = \pm 1$. Particles without distinct antiparticles are eigenstates of the C operator, such as π^0 , ϕ and γ bosons.

Lastly, the time-reversal transformation reverses the direction of time, swapping initial and final states. Unlike the previous transformations, T is an antiunitary operator, meaning it is both unitary and antilinear. Electromagnetic and strong interactions are invariant under T transformation, while weak interactions exhibit slight violations.

Violation of T symmetry is directly linked to CP violation, according to the CPT theorem [10]. This theorem asserts that every local relativistic quantum field is symmetric under the combined CPT transformation. This is significant because, to preserve the validity of the theorem, if the combination of two symmetries is violated, the third one must be as well. For example, time-reversal violation directly implies CP violation, and vice versa.

1.1.3 Flavour physics

The term ‘‘flavour’’ was introduced for the first time by Murray Gell-Mann in 1971 while he was tasting an ice cream with one of his students. He wanted to point out that quarks have both a flavour and a color, such as ice cream. Nowadays, this term more generally stands for the species of any fermion, so flavour physics deals with studying properties of leptons and quarks. By conducting precise measurements of various processes, flavour physics has enabled the indirect discovery of new particles before they could be directly observed. For instance, the prediction of the charm quark via the GIM mechanism [11] was driven by the failure to detect the $K_L^0 \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ decays. The observation of CPV introduced the flavour mixing among the three quark families. Another example is the high mass of the top quark that was predicted based on the study of B^0 meson mixing.

Considering the kinetic Lagrangian term \mathcal{L}_{kin} of the total SM Lagrangian [12],

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{kin}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Yukawa}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Higgs}}, \quad (1.8)$$

it can be asserted that \mathcal{L}_{kin} is globally flavour symmetric,

$$G_{\text{flavour}} = U(3)_q^3 \times U(3)_{\text{lep}}^2, \quad (1.9)$$

with $U(3) = SU(3) \times U(1)$, where q stands for quark and lep for leptons,

$$U(3)_q^3 = U(3)_Q \times U(3)_u \times U(3)_d, \quad (1.10)$$

$$U(3)_{\text{lep}}^2 = U(3)_L \times U(3)_I. \quad (1.11)$$

We have indicated the left-handed quarks with Q , the up right-handed quarks with u and the down right-handed quarks with d . L stands for the left-handed leptons and l for the right-handed leptons.

The flavour symmetry of \mathcal{L}_{kin} means that each type of fermion can be separately rotated in the flavor space, $\Psi^i \rightarrow U_j^i \Psi^j$, with U_j^i a unitary 3×3 matrix, without changing \mathcal{L}_{kin} [13]. However, this is not a global symmetry for the total Lagrangian because of the presence of the Yukawa term. This is reasonable considering the fact that the Yukawa term is responsible for giving mass to fermions. The flavour symmetry breaking is observed in the fact that up and down quarks have different masses.

An important role in flavour physics is played by the Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) matrix given that it explains the quark mixing. It also provides information on the strength of the flavour-changing weak interactions. Nicola Cabibbo was the first to introduce the idea of quark mixing [14], attempting to classify the quarks known at that time (u, d, s) in the weak isospin representation $SU(2)_L$. Considering a doublet (u, d) and a singlet (s), it was not possible to explain the observed $s \rightarrow u$ transitions. Thus he introduced a mixing angle θ in order to write the weak isospin eigenstates as combination of the mass eigenstates u, d, s ,

$$\begin{pmatrix} u \\ \cos \theta d + \sin \theta s \end{pmatrix}, \quad (-\sin \theta d + \cos \theta s),$$

with the first being the quark doublet and the second the singlet. However, this solution would have led to an increased flavor-changing neutral current with respect to observations, which instead disfavored them. The neutral-current interaction of the u, d and s quarks would be proportional to the product of the participating particles wavefunctions,

$$(u\bar{u} + (d\bar{d}\cos^2\theta + s\bar{s}\sin^2\theta)) + (s\bar{d} + d\bar{s}\sin\theta\cos\theta),$$

where the first term is conserving the flavour $\Delta S = 0$, while the second is not, with $\Delta S = 1$. To avoid this second term, it was necessary to introduce a new quark, the charm c . At the same time, the GIM mechanism was formulated to explain the suppression of flavor-changing neutral currents [11]. With the new quark, there were two weak isospin doublets,

$$\begin{pmatrix} u \\ d' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} u \\ \cos \theta d + \sin \theta s \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} c \\ s' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c \\ -\sin \theta d + \cos \theta s \end{pmatrix}.$$

In this way the unwanted $\Delta S = 1$ neutral current term cancels out.

Finally, the third generation of quarks was predicted by Makoto Kobayashi and Toshihide Maskawa to explain CP violation in K meson decays [15]. The possibility of CP violation requires at least one irreducible complex phase in the quark mixing matrix. With only two quark generations, such a phase can be removed by rephasing the quark fields, leaving a single real mixing angle (the Cabibbo angle) and thus no source of CPV . With three generations, however, one physical complex phase remains after all possible rephasings, providing the necessary degree of freedom for CP violation. This motivated the extension of the Cabibbo matrix into the Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) matrix [16], incorporating the third-generation beauty (bottom) and top quarks,

$$\begin{pmatrix} d' \\ s' \\ b' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} V_{ud} & V_{us} & V_{ub} \\ V_{cd} & V_{cs} & V_{cb} \\ V_{td} & V_{ts} & V_{tb} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} d \\ s \\ b \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1.12)$$

The probability of transition from one up-type quark i to a down-type quark j is proportional to $|V_{ij}|^2$, where V is a unitary matrix and can be parameterized through three angles $\theta_{12}, \theta_{13}, \theta_{23}$ and a CP -violating phase δ ,

$$\begin{pmatrix} V_{ud} & V_{us} & V_{ub} \\ V_{cd} & V_{cs} & V_{cb} \\ V_{td} & V_{ts} & V_{tb} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12}c_{13} & s_{12}c_{13} & s_{13}e^{-i\delta} \\ -s_{12}c_{23} - c_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & c_{12}c_{23} - s_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & s_{23}c_{13} \\ s_{12}s_{23} - c_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & -c_{12}s_{23} - s_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & c_{23}c_{13} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1.13)$$

where c_{ij} and s_{ij} respectively stand for $\cos\theta_{ij}$ and $\sin\theta_{ij}$. All the phenomena in the SM which involve CPV in flavour-changing processes are accounted by the δ phase. Experimentally it has been observed that $s_{13} \ll s_{23} \ll s_{12} \ll 1$, so the CKM matrix can be rewritten in order to highlight this hierarchy using the Wolfenstein parameterization [17], based on four parameters λ, A, ρ, η as follows:

$$s_{12} = \lambda, \quad s_{23} = A\lambda^2, \quad s_{13}e^{i\delta} = A\lambda^2(\rho + i\eta). \quad (1.14)$$

The CKM matrix at order λ^4 becomes

$$V_{CKM} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \lambda^2/2 & \lambda & A\lambda^3(\rho - i\eta) \\ -\lambda & 1 - \lambda^2/2 & A\lambda^2 \\ A\lambda^3(1 - \rho - i\eta) & -A\lambda^2 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + O(\lambda^4). \quad (1.15)$$

With $\lambda \approx 0.23$, $A \approx 0.84$, $\bar{\rho} \approx 0.12$ and $\bar{\eta} \approx 0.35$, where $\bar{\rho} = \rho(1 - \lambda^2/2 + \dots)$ and $\bar{\eta} = \eta(1 - \lambda^2/2 + \dots)$, all currently available for the experimental results. The elements of this matrix are all parameters of the SM, so their measurement is important and it is a major goal of flavour physics. It also allows to experimentally check the unitarity of the matrix, which imposes that $\sum_i V_{ij}V_{ik}^* = \delta_{jk}$ and $\sum_j V_{ij}V_{kj}^* = \delta_{ik}$. The six vanishing combinations can be represented as triangles in a complex plane. The most frequently considered triangle, called the unitarity triangle, can be build starting from

$$V_{ud}V_{ub}^* + V_{cd}V_{cb}^* + V_{td}V_{tb}^* = 0, \quad (1.16)$$

and dividing each side by the most precise known term $V_{cd}V_{cb}^*$. The triangle found, shown is Fig. 1.2, has $(0,0)$, $(1,0)$ and $(\bar{\rho}, \bar{\eta})$ as vertices, while the angles are known as α, β and γ . In the Wolfenstein parameterization, CPV is taken into account by the η quantity and CPV represents faithfully that observed in electroweak hadron interactions and decays. Nevertheless, it is a tiny contribution, because the only terms with a complex phase are V_{ub} and V_{td} and they are suppressed by a λ^3 factor (≈ 0.01). Therefore, it is important to search for other CP violating sources to explain the imbalance between matter and antimatter of the Universe.

CPV in the Standard Model

As previously mentioned, CP violation is allowed in the SM theory and it is accounted by the CKM matrix. Numerous experimental measurements have been performed and confirm the expected CPV in the SM in the quark sector. It is possible to distinguish three different types of CP -violating effects [18]:

- Type 1: CPV in the decay, the hadron decay amplitude (A_f) differs from that of its CP conjugate process ($\bar{A}_{\bar{f}}$),

$$|\bar{A}_{\bar{f}}/A_f| \neq 1. \quad (1.17)$$

Figure 1.2: The unitarity triangle.

This occurs when there is interference between different contributions to the decay amplitudes. This is the only possible source of CPV when mixing effects are absent, as in the case of baryon and charged meson decays. An example from LHCb is the observation of direct CP violation in the decay of $B^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-$ and its CP -conjugate $\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$. LHCb measured the CP asymmetry in these decays, finding a significant difference between the decay rates of the particle and its antiparticle:

$$A_{CP}(B^0 \rightarrow K^+ \pi^-) = -0.082 \pm 0.006 \pm 0.003. \quad (1.18)$$

This result shows direct CP violation in these decays [19].

- Type 2: CP violation in mixing. If we consider the mixing of two flavour eigenstates, M^0 and \bar{M}^0 , the mass eigenstates (heavy H and light L) can be expressed as $|M_H\rangle = p|M^0\rangle - q|\bar{M}^0\rangle$ and $|M_L\rangle = p|M^0\rangle + q|\bar{M}^0\rangle$. The two parameters p and q satisfy $|p|^2 + |q|^2 = 1$. Therefore, CPV is expressed by

$$|q/p| \neq 1. \quad (1.19)$$

This is the only possible CPV in charged-current semileptonic neutral meson decays. An example from LHCb is the measurement of CP violation in $B^0 - \bar{B}^0$ mixing [20], since they are two flavour eigenstates, made by a mixing of mass eigenstates. The time evolution of the neutral B^0 -meson system, which consists of two quantum states (B^0 and \bar{B}^0), leads to flavour oscillations where transitions between the two states occur. CP violation can arise in this mixing process if the probability of a B^0 meson oscillating into a \bar{B}^0 differs from the probability of the reverse transition. When a meson produced as a B^0 decays semileptonically into a final state f , the charge of the resulting lepton identifies the meson flavor at the time of decay. In this context, “wrong-sign” decays, such as a B^0 decaying into a final state typically associated with a \bar{B}^0 , can only occur through mixing followed by decay: $B^0 \rightarrow \bar{B}^0 \rightarrow f$. The flavour-specific, or semileptonic, asymmetry a_{sl}^d is defined in terms of the partial decay rates as

$$a_{sl}^d = \frac{\Gamma(\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow f) - \Gamma(B^0 \rightarrow \bar{f})}{\Gamma(\bar{B}^0 \rightarrow f) + \Gamma(B^0 \rightarrow \bar{f})}, \quad (1.20)$$

and can also be expressed in terms of the difference in masses (Δm_d) and widths ($\Delta\Gamma_d$) of the two mass eigenstates, and the CP -violating phase ϕ_{12}^d , as:

$$a_{\text{sl}}^d = \frac{\Delta\Gamma_d}{\Delta m_d} \tan \phi_{12}^d. \quad (1.21)$$

In the Standard Model, this asymmetry is predicted to be very small, with a value of

$$a_{\text{sl}}^d = (-4.1 \pm 0.6) \times 10^{-4}, \quad (1.22)$$

which is well below the sensitivity of current experimental measurements [21]. The LHCb measurement is in agreement with the SM, with

$$a_{\text{sl}}^d = (-0.02 \pm 0.19 \pm 0.30)\%, \quad (1.23)$$

with the statistical and systematic uncertainty, respectively.

- Type 3: CPV in interference between the decay and the mixing amplitude. This can occur only when the final state is shared by both decays. The interference is between two different paths of the mother particle decaying to the final state. An example from LHCb is the measurement of CP violation in the decay $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S$. LHCb observed the time-dependent CP asymmetry, characterized by the parameter $S_{J/\psi K_S}$,

$$S_{J/\psi K_S} = 0.731 \pm 0.035 \pm 0.020. \quad (1.24)$$

This measurement provides a precise determination of the β angle of the unitarity triangle, confirming CP violation through the interference between decay and mixing amplitudes [22].

CP violation was first discovered in 1964 through the study of neutral kaon oscillations [23]. Cronin, Fitch, and their collaborators conducted an experiment [24] that provided the initial evidence that mass eigenstates differ from CP eigenstates, marking the first observation of CP violation in weak interactions. This initial CPV observation in kaons is attributed to CPV in mixing (type 2), occurring in $\Delta S = 2$ transitions, where S represents the strangeness quantum number. Additionally, CPV in $\Delta S = 1$ transitions was observed in both non-leptonic and semi-leptonic decays of kaons.

Due to the measured values of the CKM matrix elements, CP violation involving beauty quarks is predicted to be more pronounced than that observed in kaon systems. CP violation can be measured by exploiting the interference between decay and mixing amplitudes, specifically by measuring the β angle in the unitarity triangle, defined as $\beta = \arg(-\frac{V_{cd}V_{cb}^*}{V_{td}V_{tb}^*})$. The process that allows for the measurement of this angle is the time-dependent asymmetry in the decay of the initial $B^0\bar{B}^0$ state, produced by the $\Upsilon(4S)$ resonance and decaying into a specific final CP eigenstate f_{CP} , such as the $J/\psi K_S$ final state. The β measurement was carried out by the Belle [25], BaBar [26], and LHCb [27] collaborations, yielding consistent results. Direct CP violation in B decays ($B^\pm \rightarrow D^* K^\pm$) was subsequently observed by BaBar [28] and LHCb [29]. These decay channels also provide access to the measurement of the γ angle, defined as $\gamma = \arg(-\frac{V_{ud}V_{ub}^*}{V_{cd}V_{cb}^*})$.

CP violation has also been observed in the charm sector, in $D^0 \rightarrow K^+ K^-$ and $D^0 \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^-$ decays. The SM prediction for CPV in D^0 decays is small, on the order of $10^{-4} - 10^{-3}$. The LHCb collaboration achieved unprecedented precision and obtained a value that differs from zero by more than five standard deviations [30].

Recently, CP violation has been measured for the first time in baryons by the LHCb collaboration [31]. The decay considered is $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow pK^-\pi^+\pi^-$ and its CP -conjugate. The quantity measured is the relative difference between the rates of the two decays, inferred from the asymmetry in the observed yields of the two decays, which is measured to be

$$A_{CP} = (2.45 \pm 0.46 \pm 0.10)\%, \quad (1.25)$$

showing a discrepancy of 5.2 standard deviations from zero. This is the first time that CPV is measured in baryons, opening a new path towards the discovery of BSM physics.

Strong CP violation

Another source of CP violation allowed by the SM is in the strong interaction Lagrangian

$$\mathcal{L}_\theta = \theta \frac{\alpha_s}{\pi} \sum_a F_{\mu\nu a} \tilde{F}_a^{\mu\nu}, \quad (1.26)$$

where α_s is the strong coupling constant and $F_{\mu\nu a}$ the gluon field tensor. Although the SM permits CP violation in strong interactions, this has not been confirmed by observations. In fact, experimental measurements of the neutron electric dipole moment suggest that the coupling θ has an upper limit of the order of 10^{-10} . This is known as the strong CP problem. Peccei and Quinn proposed an explanation involving the existence of axions, which to date have not been observed. Therefore, the strong CP problem remains unresolved [32].

CPV beyond the SM

As previously mentioned, the CP violation accounted for by the SM is insufficient to explain the asymmetry between matter and antimatter in the Universe. Consequently, BSM theories propose new sources of CP violation, and parallel experiments search for new evidence, particularly in the neutrino sector. A mechanism similar to that of quarks was proposed for leptons by Pontecorvo, Maki, Nakagawa, and Sakata, introducing the PMNS matrix for neutrino CP violation [33]. If neutrinos are Majorana particles, meaning that a fermion is its own antiparticle, two additional phases appear in the PMNS matrix. These so-called Majorana phases cannot be accessed in oscillation experiments, but are the target of dedicated searches such as neutrinoless double-beta decay.

Ongoing experiments, such as T2K, aim to measure the CP -violating phase to identify a new source of CPV . This experiment investigates the oscillation between muon and electron neutrinos and their corresponding antineutrinos. In 2020, the T2K collaboration made an initial claim of CP violation in this sector [34], but further data collection is necessary to confirm a discovery. This measurement is crucial because CPV in the lepton sector could explain the matter-antimatter asymmetry through leptogenesis.

1.2 Electromagnetic dipole moments

In the quest for new sources of CP violation, in addition to flavour-changing CP -violating transitions, as considered in the main LHCb physics program, flavour-diagonal CP -violating processes can be exploited, which do not involve a change of flavour in the decay. In this context, electric dipole moments (EDMs) can play a significant role, since their existence would imply T symmetry breaking, therefore also CP , assuming the validity of the CPT theorem. Due to the highly suppressed contribution from the SM, these measurements are direct indicators of BSM physics.

Figure 1.3: EDM observables and contribution from higher energy scales [35]. At TeV scale, in fundamental theories the CP violation sources could induce EDMs through enhanced (solid arrows) or suppressed (dashed arrows) contributions.

The search for EDMs in various systems began in the early 1950s and includes investigations involving molecules, atoms, protons, neutrons, and hyperons. Nowadays it is still a very active field and physicists worldwide are leading different experiments. For instance, to measure the EDM of the electron, different methods have been developed such as the analysis of the spin of molecules of ThO in an electric field, ultracold molecules such as YbF, and also trapped HfF⁺ molecular ions with which the most stringent upper limit has been set to $|d_e| < 4.1 \times 10^{-30} e \text{ cm}$ [36]. Several collaborations, including nEDM at PSI [37], panEDM at ILL [38], and The Los Alamos National Laboratory nEDM Experiment at LANL UCN facility [39], focus on measuring the neutron EDM. Significant efforts are directed towards measuring the electron and neutron EDMs as they are the simplest systems for constraining CP violation models. The EDM of charm baryons have never been measured up to date, due to the very short lifetime of these particles. A first direct measurement has been proposed to be performed at the LHC, expecting a sensitivity of the order of $\times 10^{-16} e \text{ cm}$. This proposal will be discussed more extensively in the last part of this chapter.

Concerning the strange baryon, some measurements are present in literature and will be discussed in the following. In this thesis we focus on the direct measurement of the EDM of the Λ baryons performed for the first time in a collider environment, the LHCb experiment at the LHC [40]. It is of great interest because it can give direct access to the strange quark EDM. In fact the ud pair forms a spin-0 singlet, so it does not enter in the baryon spin and therefore in the EDM contribution. The SM prediction, obtained indirectly from the neutron EDM upper limit, esteems it to be $< 4.4 \times 10^{-26} e \text{ cm}$, while the current experimental upper limit on the Λ baryon has been set to $1.5 \times 10^{-16} e \text{ cm}$.

The complementarity of the different systems helps in disentangling different theoretical models for the BSM source of CPV. For this purpose, free particles are the cleanest and simplest case to understand and for heavy baryons, the dominance of the valence heavy quark in low-energy hadronic calculations enables a straightforward in-

terpretation. Figure 1.3 illustrates the contributions to EDM observables from higher energy scales, while in Fig. 1.4 the current status of the EDM measurement in different systems is pictured, with the SM predictions and the experimental upper limits.

Figure 1.4: State of the art of EDM measurements in different systems and prediction from the SM [41].

The electric dipole moment is classically defined as

$$\delta = \int \rho(\mathbf{r})\mathbf{r}dV, \quad (1.27)$$

where $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ is the charge density in a point \mathbf{r} . It describes the separation between positive and negative electric charges in the system. In a quantum approach, the EDM of a spin 1/2 particle is proportional to the spin polarization vector \mathbf{P} ,

$$\delta = d\mu_B \frac{\mathbf{P}}{2}, \quad (1.28)$$

expressed in Gaussian units, where d is the gyroelectric factor and μ_B is the particle magneton, equal to $e\hbar/(2mc)$, with e the electric charge and m the particle mass. For fermions, spin polarization is defined as $\mathbf{P} = 2 \langle \mathbf{S} \rangle / \hbar$, with \mathbf{S} the spin operator.

On the other hand, the magnetic dipole moment is classically defined as

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = \frac{1}{2c} \int (\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{j})dV, \quad (1.29)$$

with \mathbf{j} the electric current density. Similarly to the EDM case, for a quantum system its definition becomes

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = g\mu_B \frac{\mathbf{P}}{2}, \quad (1.30)$$

with g the gyromagnetic factor.

These two dipole moments enter in the Hamiltonian of a spin 1/2 particle with the presence of an electromagnetic field, defined as

$$H = -\boldsymbol{\mu} \cdot \mathbf{B} - \boldsymbol{\delta} \cdot \mathbf{E}. \quad (1.31)$$

The expectation value of the EDM Hamiltonian is odd under T and P transformations:

$$T^\dagger \mathbf{P} T = -\mathbf{P}, \quad T^\dagger \mathbf{E} T = \mathbf{E},$$

$$P^\dagger \mathbf{P} P = \mathbf{P}, \quad P^\dagger \mathbf{E} P = -\mathbf{E}.$$

Assuming the validity of the CPT theorem, the existence of a non zero EDM would violate T symmetry and consequently also CP . It may also be a proof of a BSM effect. It is important to highlight that an EDM different from zero implies CPV only in case of a system with definite parity. For instance, in the case of polar molecules such as H_2O , which has degenerated ground states with different parities, the large dipole moment of the order of $10^{-8}e \text{ cm}$ is not a sign of new physics [42]. Their ground state is often a superposition of states with opposite parity due to rotational or vibrational mixing. In this case the EDM originates from classical electrodynamics and structural asymmetry, not from a fundamental CP -violating interaction.

The Hamiltonian term in which the MDM appears is invariant under both T and P transformations, thus the MDM existence does not imply CP violation. The CPT symmetry implies that the MDM of a particle is opposite to that of the antiparticle, so their simultaneous measurements allow for a test of CPT , similarly to what has already been performed for protons, electrons and muons. In fact under CPT :

- C : reverses the sign of the charge, $q \rightarrow -q$; spin remains unchanged;
- P : leaves the spin unchanged since it is an axial vector, $\mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}$;
- T : reverses the direction of spin, $\mathbf{S} \rightarrow -\mathbf{S}$.

Applying all three transformations to the MDM, we have

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{CPT} = g \left(\frac{-q}{2m} \right) (-\mathbf{S}) = -g \left(\frac{q}{2m} \right) \mathbf{S} = -\boldsymbol{\mu}. \quad (1.32)$$

Therefore, the magnetic dipole moment of a particle and its antiparticle are equal in magnitude but opposite in sign,

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\bar{p}} = -\boldsymbol{\mu}_p. \quad (1.33)$$

In the context of this thesis we aim at performing a CPT test with Λ baryons for the first time. The MDM measurement is interesting also because it allows to test different models of low-energy strong interactions, as happened in the past for the case of baryons.

Contrary to baryons, for leptons the MDM can be predicted with a very high accuracy in the context of the SM, due to the perturbative nature of the electroweak interaction. Extremely precise theoretical predictions are needed in order to give a useful comparison with the incredible sensitivity reached by the experiments on the muon and electron anomalous magnetic moment $a_l = (g_l - 2)/2$,

$$a_\mu(\text{exp}) = (116\,592\,059 \pm 22) \times 10^{-11} \quad [43],$$

$$a_e(\text{exp}) = (1.00115965218059 \pm 13)\mu_B \quad [44].$$

The same behavior of the Hamiltonian can be demonstrated in the relativistic quantum field approach, where the EDM of any 1/2 spin particle appears as the coupling constant δ of a spin 1/2 Dirac fermion with an electromagnetic field, expressed by

$$-\frac{i}{2}\delta\bar{\psi}\sigma^{\mu\nu}\gamma_5\psi F_{\mu\nu}, \quad (1.34)$$

where ψ is the spinor of the field, $\sigma^{\mu\nu}$ and γ_5 are the combinations of Dirac matrices and $F_{\mu\nu}$ the electromagnetic tensor.

For the case of baryon dipole moments, the most general form of the electromagnetic coupling of a spin 1/2 Dirac fermion with an electromagnetic field is expressed by [45]

$$\begin{aligned} \langle p'|J_{em}^\nu|p\rangle A_\mu &= \bar{u}(p')\left(\gamma^\nu F_1(q^2) - \frac{iF_2(q^2)}{2m_B}\sigma^{\mu\nu}q_\mu + i(\gamma^\nu q^2\gamma_5 - 2m_Bq^\nu\gamma_5)F_A(q^2) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{F_3(q^2)}{2m_B}\sigma^{\mu\nu}q_\mu\gamma_5\right)u(p)A_\mu \end{aligned} \quad (1.35)$$

where the $F_i(q^2)$ coefficients are the so called form factors, which are functions of the Lorentz-invariant transferred 4-momentum q^2 of the virtual photon, p and p' are the 4-momenta of the initial and final baryon, and m_B its mass. $F_1(q^2)$ and $F_2(q^2)$ are the P - and CP -conserving Dirac and Pauli form factors, respectively. $F_A(q^2)$ represents the P -violating anapole form factor and $F_3(q^2)$ is the electric dipole form factor which is responsible for violating P and CP symmetries. The form factors express the electromagnetic intrinsic properties of the baryon: $F_1(0) = Q$ is its electric charge, the magnetic moment is expressed by $\mu = \frac{F_1(0)+F_2(0)}{2m_B}$, the anapole moment is represented by $F_A(0)$ and finally the electric dipole moment is $\delta = \frac{1}{2m_B}F_3(0)$. The properties of each term after applying the discrete symmetries derive from those of the electromagnetic field and of the Dirac bilinears:

$$P^\dagger A_\mu P = A^\mu, \quad \langle p'|P^\dagger\gamma^\mu P|p\rangle = \langle p'|\gamma_\mu|p\rangle, \quad \langle p'|P^\dagger i\sigma^{\mu\nu}q_\mu P|p\rangle = \langle p'|i\sigma_{\mu\nu}q^\mu|p\rangle,$$

$$\langle p'|P^\dagger(\gamma^\nu q^2\gamma_5 - 2m_Bq^\nu\gamma_5)P|p\rangle = -\langle p'|(\gamma_\nu q^2\gamma_5 - 2m_Bq_\nu\gamma_5)|p\rangle,$$

$$\langle p'|P^\dagger\sigma^{\mu\nu}q_\mu\gamma_5 P|p\rangle = -\langle p'|\sigma_{\mu\nu}q^\mu\gamma_5|p\rangle;$$

$$T^\dagger A_\mu T = A^\mu, \quad \langle p'|T^\dagger\gamma^\mu T|p\rangle = \langle p'|\gamma_\mu|p\rangle, \quad \langle p'|T^\dagger i\sigma^{\mu\nu}q_\mu T|p\rangle = \langle p'|i\sigma_{\mu\nu}q^\mu|p\rangle,$$

$$\langle p'|T^\dagger(\gamma^\nu q^2\gamma_5 - 2m_Bq^\nu\gamma_5)T|p\rangle = \langle p'|(\gamma_\nu q^2\gamma_5 - 2m_Bq_\nu\gamma_5)|p\rangle,$$

$$\langle p'|T^\dagger\sigma^{\mu\nu}q_\mu\gamma_5 T|p\rangle = -\langle p'|\sigma_{\mu\nu}q^\mu\gamma_5|p\rangle.$$

Since the MDM is a combination of the first and second terms and the EDM is proportional to the last one, it follows that the first is even and the second is odd under P and T discrete symmetries.

1.2.1 Experimental technique for electromagnetic dipole moment measurements

Dipole moment measurements exploit the phenomenon of spin precession in an electromagnetic field [46] and require three main components: firstly, a source of polarized particles, such as Λ baryons from beauty or charm weak decays. Secondly, a magnetic field strong enough to induce an observable spin precession during the short lifetime of the particles. Finally, a detector capable of reconstructing the angular distributions that are sensitive to the spin polarization. The LHCb experiment can fulfill all these requirements for particles that are able to fly until the region with the magnetic field, see a sketch in Fig. 1.5. This is possible for Λ baryons and in this work we will focus on such particles, which are copiously produced at the LHC, and are the lightest baryons with strangeness. In the pp collisions at LHC the Λ baryon can be produced in strong or weak interactions. The strongly produced Λ baryons originate promptly from the primary pp collisions. However, those Λ particles that are reconstructible in the detector typically have small Feynman- x values ($x_F \sim 0$), defined as the ratio between the longitudinal momentum of the particle in the center-of-mass frame and its maximum possible value, $x_F = p_L^*/p_L^{\max}$. Since transverse polarization of Λ baryons is known to increase with x_F , baryons produced near central rapidity (low x_F) are expected to be unpolarized, as measured by the LHCb collaboration [47]. However, Λ baryons can be polarized when produced by heavier hadrons weak decays, $H \rightarrow \Lambda X$, with beauty or charm flavour. Other long-lived particles (LLPs) with strangeness reconstructible in LHCb are the K_S^0 mesons and since they have a null spin can be used as control sample for null electromagnetic dipole moment measurements.

As it will be explained later, the precession angle is directly related to the dipole moments. This angle can be extracted by measuring the polarization before and after the LHCb magnetic field. To obtain the spin polarization, it is necessary to analyze the angular distribution of the decay products of the Λ particle. When the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decay is dominated by a single helicity amplitude, as suggested by angular analyses, the daughter Λ baryon can be polarized due to the spin structure of the weak decay. This polarization arises because the weak interaction selects specific helicity configurations, and under the dominance of a single amplitude (e.g., $H_{1/2,0}$), angular momentum conservation leads to a strong correlation between the initial and final baryon spin directions. The observed angular distributions at LHCb support this picture, justifying the assumption that the Λ is fully polarized when produced in such decays from a polarized Λ_b^0 [48], [49], [50]. Since the sensitivity to the electromagnetic dipole moments increases linearly with the initial polarization, this decay is considered a golden channel for the first analysis at a collider experiment. An additional key reason is that during Run 1 and Run 2 of LHCb, a very efficient trigger from $J/\Psi \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ decays was already in place, so data are already available for this channel.

The measurement of the spin direction after the precession in the magnet is the focus of this thesis. It is extremely more challenging than measuring the polarization before the precession because it involves the need of reconstructing the Λ decays after the magnetic field. The difficulty in reconstructing the proton and the pion coming from a Λ decaying in the final part of the magnet lies in the fact that charged-particle tracks traverse a region with low magnetic field and a limited number of tracking stations, along with a relatively large lever arm, therefore their momentum resolution is poor. As additional consequence, the combinatorial background is not negligible. Nevertheless, a great effort has been made to realize this idea and the feasibility has been demonstrated and will be presented in this thesis, based on the work published in Ref. [51]. The reconstruction of $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays and its control sample $B \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ with Λ and K_S^0 decaying at

Figure 1.5: Spin precession scheme in LHCb. The arrows represent the Λ spin precessing in the LHCb magnet.

the end of the magnetic field constitutes a novelty for the LHCb experiment, since these kinds of tracks have never been used for physics analysis. It opens new possibilities for the physics reach of the experiment, not only in the measurement for electromagnetic dipole moments but also in the search for BSM long-living particles.

1.2.2 Spin precession theory

The experimental measurement of dipole moments is based on the spin precession in an external magnetic field. To describe the spin precession of a particle in motion in an external electromagnetic field we can use the Thomas-Bargmann-Michel-Telegdi (T-BMT) equation [52]. This is a relativistic description in a covariant form, using 4-vectors P^μ and u^μ to represent, respectively, the polarization and velocity of the particle. In all reference frames the condition, $P \cdot u = 0$ is fulfilled, in fact in the rest frame of the particle, the four-velocity is $u^\mu = (1, \mathbf{0})$, and the polarization vector has only spatial components, $P^\mu = (0, \mathbf{P})$, so the condition is trivially satisfied:

$$P^\mu u_\mu = 0 \cdot 1 - \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{0} = 0.$$

Under Lorentz transformations, both P^μ and u^μ transform covariantly as four-vectors, and the scalar product $P^\mu u_\mu$ remains invariant. Therefore, if the orthogonality holds in one frame, it holds in all inertial frames,

$$P^\mu u_\mu = P'^\mu u'_\mu = 0.$$

This condition ensures that the polarization is a spacelike vector orthogonal to the particle motion in any frame. In a general frame, the equation of motion is

$$\frac{dP^\mu}{d\tau} = \frac{ge}{2m} \left[F^{\mu\nu} P_\nu + (P_\alpha F^{\alpha\beta} u_\beta) u^\mu \right] - \left[\frac{du^\alpha}{d\tau} P_\alpha \right] u^\mu, \quad (1.36)$$

where $F^{\mu\nu}$ stands for the electromagnetic 4-vector, while τ is the particle proper time. If the electromagnetic fields are homogeneous, we can assert that

$$\frac{du^\mu}{d\tau} = \frac{e}{m} F^{\mu\nu} u_\nu, \quad (1.37)$$

thus the first equation reduces to

$$\frac{dP^\mu}{d\tau} = \frac{e}{m} \left[\frac{g}{2} F^{\mu\nu} P_\nu + \left(\frac{g}{2} - 1 \right) (P_\alpha F^{\alpha\beta} u_\beta) u^\mu \right], \quad (1.38)$$

For experimental purposes, it is convenient to consider the spin precession equation in the laboratory frame, with the spatial spin vector \mathbf{P} evolving with respect to time coordinate t . An explicit derivation is due to Silenko and Fukuyama [53, 54] using $\tau = \gamma t$ and separating temporal and spatial components. Let us denote \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} the electric and magnetic fields in the laboratory frame and \mathbf{v} the velocity. We focus on the spatial part

$$\frac{d\mathbf{P}}{dt} = \frac{e}{m} \left[\frac{g}{2} \mathbf{P} \times \mathbf{B} - \left(\frac{g}{2} - 1 \right) (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{P}) \mathbf{E} \right] + \text{additional terms}. \quad (1.39)$$

The full expression requires projection of the covariant equation into 3-space, including effects from the Thomas precession. Then we introduce

- $a = \frac{g-2}{2}$ the anomalous magnetic moment,
- d the gyroelectric factor.

The full spin precession vector becomes

$$\frac{d\mathbf{P}}{dt} = \mathbf{P} \times \boldsymbol{\Omega}, \quad (1.40)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega} = \frac{e}{m} \left[\left(a + \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) \mathbf{B} - \frac{\gamma a}{\gamma + 1} (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \mathbf{v} - \left(a + \frac{1}{\gamma + 1} \right) \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{E} + \frac{d}{2} \left(\mathbf{E} - \frac{\gamma}{\gamma + 1} (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{E}) \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} \right) \right]. \quad (1.41)$$

It is now important to consider that in experiments aiming to measure EDMs is usually true that $\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$ and $\mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$. In this particular case the previous equation takes the form

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega} = \frac{e}{m} \left[\left(a + \frac{1}{\gamma} \right) \mathbf{B} - \left(a + \frac{1}{\gamma + 1} \right) \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{E} + \frac{d}{2} (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{E}) \right]. \quad (1.42)$$

It is possible to highlight three different contributions in $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$: one due to the EDM, a second from the MDM and the last due to the Thomas effect:

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega}_{\text{EDM}} = \frac{d\mu_B}{\hbar} \left(\mathbf{E} - \frac{\gamma}{\gamma + 1} (\boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{E}) \boldsymbol{\beta} + \boldsymbol{\beta} \times \mathbf{B} \right), \quad (1.43)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega}_{\text{MDM}} = \frac{g\mu_B}{\hbar} \left(\mathbf{B} - \frac{\gamma}{\gamma + 1} (\boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \boldsymbol{\beta} - \boldsymbol{\beta} \times \mathbf{E} \right), \quad (1.44)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega}_{\text{TH}} = \frac{e}{c} \left[\left(\frac{1}{\gamma} - 1 \right) \mathbf{B} + \frac{\gamma}{\gamma + 1} (\boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{B}) \boldsymbol{\beta} - \left(\frac{1}{\gamma + 1} - 1 \right) \boldsymbol{\beta} \times \mathbf{E} \right]. \quad (1.45)$$

Thomas precession arises for charged particles when the particle rest frame rotates and has the consequence of changing the angular velocity of spin precession, as evident from

the equation. It is a purely kinematic effect and defines the difference between the dynamics of the dipole moments in the rest frame and in the instantaneously accompanying frames.

Since now, the field gradients correction have been neglected. It is possible to rewrite the previous equations of motion considering these corrections, but the experimental conditions of LHCb allow to remain with the approximation without any gradient term. In fact the ratio of the gradient field terms and the homogeneous ones is expected to be negligibly small [46]:

$$\frac{\hbar}{2mc} \frac{\beta\gamma}{\gamma+1} \frac{\nabla \mathbf{B}}{\mathbf{B}} \simeq 7.4 \times 10^{-16}, \quad (1.46)$$

considering $\beta \approx 1$ and $\gamma \gg 1$. From the LHCb field mapping it is possible to determine $|\nabla \mathbf{B}| = 114 \text{ Tm}^{-1}$ and $|\mathbf{B}| = 1 \text{ T}$, which represent respectively the maximum magnetic field gradients and field strengths within the detector acceptance.

T-BMT equation for Λ baryons

Due to the fact that Λ baryons do not have any electric charge, the equation of spin precession simplifies further. Moreover, assuming $\mathbf{E} = 0$, as in LHCb detector, one finds [46]

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega} = \frac{\mu_B}{\hbar} \left[g \left(\mathbf{B} - \frac{\gamma(\boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{B})\boldsymbol{\beta}}{\gamma+1} \right) + d\boldsymbol{\beta} \times \mathbf{B} \right]. \quad (1.47)$$

It is possible to solve analytically this equation, with the initial condition $\mathbf{P}(t=0) = \mathbf{P}_0$ and assuming that the particle precession depends only on the integrated magnetic field along its flight path. Thus, the equation of motion of the spin is

$$\mathbf{P}(t) = (\mathbf{P}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})\boldsymbol{\omega} + [\mathbf{P}_0 - (\mathbf{P}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})\boldsymbol{\omega}] \cos(\Omega t) - (\mathbf{P}_0 \times \boldsymbol{\omega}) \sin(\Omega t), \quad (1.48)$$

where $\Omega = |\boldsymbol{\Omega}|$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega} = \boldsymbol{\Omega}/\Omega$. The polarization can be expressed also in terms of the Λ flight length $l = \beta ct$

$$\mathbf{P}(l) = (\mathbf{P}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}')\boldsymbol{\omega}' + [\mathbf{P}_0 - (\mathbf{P}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}')\boldsymbol{\omega}'] \cos \phi - (\mathbf{P}_0 \times \boldsymbol{\omega}') \sin \phi, \quad (1.49)$$

where Φ represents the precession angle, while $\phi = |\Phi|$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}' = \Phi/\phi$. Finally the expression which links the precession angle and the dipole moments is

$$\Phi = \frac{\mu_B}{\beta \hbar c} \left[g \left(\mathbf{D} - \frac{\gamma\boldsymbol{\beta}(\boldsymbol{\beta} \cdot \mathbf{D})}{\gamma+1} \right) + d\boldsymbol{\beta} \times \mathbf{D} \right], \quad (1.50)$$

with the magnetic field integrated along the particle flight length l : $\mathbf{D} \simeq \int_0^l \mathbf{B} dl'$. This solution simplifies further considering Λ baryons flying along the z -axis in the laboratory frame, with an initial polarization $\mathbf{P}_0 = (0, 0, P_0)$ and the magnetic field $\mathbf{B} = (0, B_y, 0)$. This approximation is very close to the situation in the LHCb detector. The final polarization becomes

$$\mathbf{P} = (-P_0 \sin \Phi, -P_0 \frac{d\beta}{g} \sin \Phi, P_0 \cos \Phi), \quad (1.51)$$

with $\Phi = (D_y \mu_B)/(\beta \hbar c) \sqrt{d^2 \beta^2 + g^2} \simeq (g D_y \mu_b)/(\beta \hbar c)$ and $D_y = \int_0^l B_y dl'$. The spin-polarization vector precesses in the plane perpendicular to the magnetic field, with an angle approximately proportional to the gyromagnetic factor. The important observation is that the presence of an EDM would induce a component s_y different from zero. Given

Eq. 1.51, it is now clear why, to obtain the dipole moments, it is important to extract the precession angle Φ , measuring the spin polarization both before (\mathbf{P}_0) and after (\mathbf{P}) the magnetic field. It is possible to perform both these measurements on the same dataset, as it will be shown in the following.

1.2.3 Polarization measurement

The measurement of the polarization is based on the angular distribution of the decay products. In particular, the decay considered is

$$\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-,$$

or

$$\bar{\Lambda} \rightarrow \bar{p}\pi^+.$$

Since Λ and p have spin 1/2 and π has spin 0, the angular distribution of the decay is

$$\frac{dN}{d\Omega'} \propto 1 + \alpha \mathbf{P} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{k}}, \quad (1.52)$$

with α the Λ decay asymmetry parameter, with a measured value of 0.749 ± 0.008 , obtained through independent experiments [16]. For the decay of $\bar{\Lambda}$ baryons we can define $\bar{\alpha}$, which is related to the first one by $\bar{\alpha} = -\alpha$, assuming no CPV . Here \mathbf{P} is the polarization vector that we want to measure. The momentum direction of the proton in the Λ rest frame is expressed by the unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = (\sin \theta' \cos \phi', \sin \theta' \sin \phi', \cos \theta')$, while the solid angle Ω' equals $(\cos \theta', \phi')$.

This angular dependence can be obtained through the helicity formalism, applying the framework developed by Jacob and Wick [55]. In the next calculation we will follow the notation reported in [56]. For simplicity, we refer to the proton and pion which come from the Λ baryon decay as particle 1 and 2, respectively. We work in the Λ rest frame and we define m_Λ as the Λ mass, while its spin is J and the spin projection along an arbitrary \hat{z} -axis is M . The helicity of the final state particles are λ_1 and λ_2 , while their momenta are $\mathbf{p}_1 = \mathbf{p}_f$ and $\mathbf{p}_2 = -\mathbf{p}_f$. We start defining the plane-wave final state in the helicity formalism

$$|\mathbf{f}\rangle = |\mathbf{p}_f \theta_f \phi_f \lambda_1 \lambda_2\rangle = (2\pi)^3 \left(\frac{4m_\Lambda}{p_f} \right)^{1/2} |\theta_f \phi_f \lambda_1 \lambda_2\rangle |\mathbf{p}_f\rangle \quad (1.53)$$

where θ_f and ϕ_f are the polar and azimuthal angle of the final state particles. We can then write the decay amplitude

$$A(\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-) = (2\pi)^3 \left(\frac{4m_\Lambda}{p_f} \right)^{1/2} \langle \theta_f \phi_f \lambda_1 \lambda_2 | U | JM \rangle, \quad (1.54)$$

with U the time-evolution operator. We are interested in this amplitude because $|A|^2$ expresses the probability of having a final-state with θ_f and ϕ_f , thus from Eq. 1.54 we can obtain the angular distribution. The idea of the helicity formalism is to exploit the fact that helicity is rotational invariant, so it is possible to define a two-particle state basis with definite total angular momentum J_f , angular momentum projection M_f , and helicities λ_1 and λ_2 . Thanks to the angular momentum conservation, we can insert a complete set of these states. Neglecting the constants which do not influence the angular distribution, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
A(\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi) &\propto \sum_{J_f M_f} \langle \theta_f \phi_f \lambda_1 \lambda_2 | J_f M_f \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \rangle \langle J_f M_f \lambda_1 \lambda_2 | U | J M \rangle \\
&= \sum_{J_f M_f} \left(\frac{2J+1}{4\pi} \right)^{1/2} D_{M_f, \lambda}^{*J_f}(\phi_f, \theta_f, -\phi_f) \delta_{J, J_f} \delta_{M, M_f} \langle \lambda_1 \lambda_2 | U | M \rangle,
\end{aligned} \tag{1.55}$$

since the matrix element $\langle \lambda_1 \lambda_2 | U | M \rangle$ has to be invariant under rotation, it is more accurate to express it as $A_{\lambda_1 \lambda_2}$, independent on M . Thus, we obtain finally

$$A(\theta_f, \phi_f; M, \lambda_1, \lambda_2) \propto \left(\frac{2J+1}{4\pi} \right)^{1/2} D_{M, \lambda}^{*J}(\phi_f, \theta_f, -\phi_f) A_{\lambda_1 \lambda_2}, \tag{1.56}$$

where $D_{m, m'}^j(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is the element matrix of the rotational operator $R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ on angular momentum eigenstates. In fact,

$$R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) |j, m\rangle = \sum_{m'=-j}^j D_{m' m}^j(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) |j m'\rangle, \tag{1.57}$$

therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
D_{m'' m}^j(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) &= \langle j m'' | R(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) | j m \rangle \\
&= \langle j m'' | e^{-i\alpha J_z} e^{-i\beta J_y} e^{-i\gamma J_z} | j m \rangle \\
&= e^{-i\alpha m''} d_{m'' m}^j(\beta) e^{-i\gamma m},
\end{aligned} \tag{1.58}$$

with $d_{m'' m}^j(\beta)$ given by the Wigner formula [57].

In order to obtain the angular distribution it is necessary to consider the initial density matrix of the Λ baryon

$$\frac{dN}{d\Omega'}(\theta_f, \phi_f) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{M, M', \lambda_1, \lambda_2} A(\theta_f, \phi_f; M, \lambda_1, \lambda_2) \rho_{M M'} A^*(\theta_f, \phi_f; M', \lambda_1, \lambda_2) \tag{1.59}$$

where $\rho_{M M'} = \langle M' | \hat{\rho} | M \rangle$ is the spin-density matrix.

In our decay, we have $M = \pm 1/2$ (Λ) in the initial state, $\lambda_1 = \pm 1/2$ (proton) and $\lambda_2 = 0$ (pion) in the final state. The spin density matrix is $\rho = (\mathbb{I} + \mathbf{P} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})$, with \mathbf{P} the spin-polarization vector and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ the Pauli matrices. Finally we define the asymmetry factor

$$\alpha = \frac{|A_{\lambda_1=+\frac{1}{2}}|^2 - |A_{\lambda_1=-\frac{1}{2}}|^2}{|A_{\lambda_1=+\frac{1}{2}}|^2 + |A_{\lambda_1=-\frac{1}{2}}|^2}. \tag{1.60}$$

To perform the measurement, given that we already know the initial polarization P_0 , we need to insert Eq. 1.49 into Eq. 1.52. The helicity frame is defined with the z axis along the direction of the Λ momenta, so that the polarization is maximal in this frame. For this reason the angular distribution is defined in the helicity frame, but the spin precession equation is defined in the laboratory frame, which is where the magnetic field is known. Therefore, to plug the polarization after the precession, Eq. 1.49, which is in the laboratory frame, into the angular distribution, Eq. 1.52, we need to rotate one of the two frames. The idea is to rotate the precession angle Φ (Eq. 1.50) from the laboratory to the helicity frame through a matrix R_i for each event i . This is possible exploiting the following property of rotations (R) and cross products

$$R(\mathbf{a} \times \mathbf{b}) = R(\mathbf{a}) \times R(\mathbf{b}). \quad (1.61)$$

Applying this to Eq. 1.40, we get

$$R_i \left(\frac{d\mathbf{P}}{dt} \right) = R_i(\mathbf{P} \times \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = R_i(\mathbf{P}) \times R_i(\boldsymbol{\Omega}). \quad (1.62)$$

Since the polarization is already in the helicity frame, the application of the rotation is equal to an identity matrix, the spin and Ω are rotated event-by-event and we end up with

$$\frac{d\mathbf{P}}{dt} = \mathbf{P} \times R_i(\boldsymbol{\Omega}). \quad (1.63)$$

To define the rotation matrix R_i in our case, we can use the direction cosine between the versors of the two reference frames as follows. We call the versors of the laboratory frame $(\mathbf{l}_1, \mathbf{l}_2, \mathbf{l}_3)$ and the versors of the helicity frame $(\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3)$, the rotation matrix from the laboratory to the helicity frame is

$$R_i = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & c_{23} \\ c_{31} & c_{32} & c_{33} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1.64)$$

where

$$c_{jk} = \mathbf{e}_j \cdot \mathbf{l}_k. \quad (1.65)$$

To derive the solution of the equation of motion, we substitute $\boldsymbol{\Phi}$ with $\boldsymbol{\Phi}'' = R_i(\boldsymbol{\Phi})$ in Eq. 1.49. This substitution leads us to the most general expression,

$$\mathbf{P}(l) = (\mathbf{P}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}'')\boldsymbol{\omega}'' + [\mathbf{P}_0 - (\mathbf{P}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}'')\boldsymbol{\omega}''] \cos \phi'' - (\mathbf{P}_0 \times \boldsymbol{\omega}'') \sin \phi'', \quad (1.66)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Phi}''$ represents the precession angle, while $\phi'' = |\boldsymbol{\Phi}''|$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}'' = \boldsymbol{\Phi}''/\phi''$.

1.2.4 Measurements of Λ baryon electromagnetic dipole moments

The search for the EDM of particles, linked to the MDM measurement, has always interested the physics community due to its potential to discover new physics. In this section, two past experiments are discussed, each of which successively established the world's most stringent limits, and one future proposal is presented too.

Nuclear emulsion experiment at CERN

One of the earliest significant results for the electric dipole moment (EDM) and magnetic dipole moment (MDM) of the Λ baryon were obtained through an emulsion experiment conducted in the 1970s at CERN [58], [59]. In this experiment, a π^- beam from the CERN proton synchrotron was directed to a polyethylene target (Fig. 1.6). The beam momentum was approximately 1.05 GeV, which was chosen to maximize the cross section for the reaction $\pi^- p \rightarrow \Lambda K^0$ and to achieve the highest polarization (normal to the production plane) over a broad angular range. The produced Λ baryons exhibited the polarization normal to the production plane due to the parity conservation in the strong interaction,

$$\frac{\mathbf{s}_0}{P} = - \frac{\mathbf{p}_{\text{inc}} \times \mathbf{p}_\Lambda}{|\mathbf{p}_{\text{inc}} \times \mathbf{p}_\Lambda|},$$

Figure 1.6: Nuclear emulsion CERN experiment setup [58, 59].

where p_{inc} represents the direction of the incident beam, p_{Λ} is the Λ momentum, and P is the polarization magnitude. To avoid misidentification with the beam particles, only Λ baryons with deflection angles between 18° and 22° in the laboratory frame were accepted, corresponding to an energy range between 500 and 850 MeV. The spin of the produced Λ baryons precessed in the magnetic field over a region 11 cm long, with the precession occurring in the plane defined by the hyperon momentum and the initial polarization, as the magnetic field was perpendicular to this plane. To minimize systematic errors, the magnetic field was periodically reversed. It should be noted that the apparatus was primarily designed to maximize the measurement of the MDM rather than the EDM, as the precession due to the EDM is not confined to the plane of the detector.

The results obtained from this experiment were:

$$\mu_{\Lambda} = (-0.65 \pm 0.07)\mu_N,$$

$$\delta_{\Lambda} = (-5.9 \pm 2.9) \times 10^{-15} e \text{ cm},$$

with an upper limit on δ_{Λ} of $10^{-14} e \text{ cm}$ at a 95% confidence level. Here, μ_N represents the nuclear magneton, $e\hbar/(2m_p c)$, with m_p the proton mass.

Fixed-target experiment at Fermilab

The currently most precise measurements for the Λ electromagnetic dipole moments were obtained at Fermilab between 1970 and 1980 [60]. A neutral hyperon spectrometer was used, in which a proton beam hit a berillium target to produce Λ and $\bar{\Lambda}$. These particles precessed in the magnetic field of the collimator and due to the high momenta, in the range 60–250 GeV/c, the decay length was of the order of 10 m with a precession angle between 100° – 150° . The integrated magnetic field resulted to be 15 Tm. The magnetic dipole moment was obtained by measuring the spin precession angle using the relation

$$\Phi = \frac{\mu_{\Lambda} c}{\hbar\beta} \int B dl. \quad (1.67)$$

Figure 1.7: (Left) Fermilab set up [60]. (Right top) Measured precession angle vs the measured field integral. (Right bottom) Measured Λ magnetic moment for each of the seven momentum bin.

The Λ particles decayed into p and π^- , detected with multiwire proportional chambers. Their momenta were measured with a spectrometer magnet, the schematic setup is shown in Fig. 1.7.

The first results [61] indicated that the unpolarized proton beam hitting the target produced polarized Λ baryons, while the $\bar{\Lambda}$ baryons were produced unpolarized. A mechanism was proposed to explain this, involving the gluon bremsstrahlung (Fig. 1.9). In this model, two of the proton quarks, u and d , in a singlet spin state are considered spectators, while the other u quark is scattered by the target and emits a gluon, which generates a $s\bar{s}$ pair. This s quark determines the transverse momentum and the spin of the Λ baryon. The $s\bar{s}$ pair is polarized only if the gluon is polarized, and the polarization is correlated with the transverse momentum of the Λ baryon. On the other hand, to produce a $\bar{\Lambda}$ baryon, a \bar{s} is needed, along with \bar{u} and \bar{d} quarks. They contribute to the transverse momentum of the $\bar{\Lambda}$, but not to its polarization. This could explain why the polarization of $\bar{\Lambda}$ baryons at a given transverse momentum is suppressed.

Another observation was that the initial proton beam was in the yz plane and, due to the parity conservation in strong interaction, the initial polarization of the Λ was normal to the production plane, as reported in Fig. 1.8. It was measured that the polarization has a dependence on the transverse momentum (p_T), which was in the range 0-2.1 GeV/c, while is almost independent on the target material (beryllium, copper and platinum were used). The value of the polarization before the precession was rather poor, of only about 9%. The dataset collected was made up of $3 \times 10^6 \Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $2.5 \times 10^5 \bar{\Lambda} \rightarrow \bar{p}\pi^+$. Half of the data were taken with the initial polarization along $-x$ and half along $+x$. The result obtained for the magnetic dipole moment of the Λ baryons was [62]

$$\mu_\Lambda = (-0.6138 \pm 0.0047)\mu_N, \quad (1.68)$$

and it is currently the most precise measurement.

Finally, a limit for the Λ EDM was established. The method used is the already explained precession in the magnetic field, exploiting the T-BMT equations and the fact that a particle moving in a magnetic field is subject to an electric field in its rest frame. A polarization along the y axis would have been a clear signature of the EDM. The experimental apparatus was the same described for the MDM. The result obtained was [63]

$$\delta_\Lambda = (-3.0 \pm 7.4) \times 10^{-17} \text{ e cm}, \quad (1.69)$$

which set the upper limit at 95% C.L. of

$$|\delta_\Lambda| < 1.5 \times 10^{-16} \text{ e cm}, \tag{1.70}$$

the best upper limit of the Λ EDM up to date. The value used for the decay asymmetry parameter α_Λ was 0.647 ± 0.013 [64], which has been updated by the BESIII collaboration, with a new value distant more than five standard deviations [65, 66, 67]: the current average value is 0.749 ± 0.008 [16]. This five sigma discrepancy additionally motivates the need for an updated measurement of the Λ magnetic and electric dipole moments.

Figure 1.8: Spin precession: (a) initial polarization direction, due to the magnetic field and particle directions; (b) the precession angle ϕ is determined by the spin direction after a time t from the production.

Figure 1.9: Gluon bremsstrahlung mechanism.

Proposal of indirect measurement of Λ EDM at BESIII

In contrast to the previously mentioned direct measurements, at BESIII experiment an indirect measurement has been proposed, in which the search for Λ EDM could be realized through the analysis of the J/Ψ decay into entangled $\Lambda\bar{\Lambda}$ pairs [68]. At BESIII, about 10 billion J/Ψ particles are directly produced by the $e^- e^+$ collisions and they decay not only into Λ pairs but in general into $H\bar{H}$, where H can also be Σ^+ , $\Xi^- \rightarrow \Lambda\pi^-$ and $\Xi^0 \rightarrow \Lambda\pi^0$. Analysing all these decays give a significant improvement in the EDM

sensitivity. To indirectly measure the EDM, it is exploited the fact that the electric dipole form factor is incorporated within the P and CP -violating components of the Lorentz invariant amplitude. In addition, assuming a negligible momentum transfer, the electric dipole form factor converges to the EDM value.

The sensitivity estimated using simulated pseudoexperiments shows that it could be possible to improve the current upper limit on the Λ EDM and reach a sensitivity of the order of $10^{-19} e \text{ cm}$. The same sensitivity is expected for Σ^+ , Ξ^- and Ξ^0 hyperons. With a copious statistics to be collected at the future Super Tau-Charm Facility, the result is expected to improve further, of one or two orders of magnitude.

1.3 ALADDIN experiment to measure charm electromagnetic dipole moments

As previously mentioned, a new proposal is under development to measure for the first time the electromagnetic dipole moments of charmed baryons, such as Λ_c^+ and Ξ_c^+ . As for the Λ hyperon, the idea is to exploit the spin precession in an electromagnetic field, but since the charmed baryons have a lifetime three orders of magnitude smaller than the Λ one, a strong magnetic field, of the order of 10^3 T , is necessary in their short decay length. Nowadays magnets providing such an intense field are not available and the technological solution can be found in bent crystals. Positively-charged particles are produced by protons interacting with a fixed target and channeled between the atomic planes of the crystal. They move along a curved path under the action of the intense electric field present between the crystal planes, of the order of 1 GV/cm . In this way their EDM and MDM interact with the electromagnetic field present in the rest frame of the particles and induce the spin to precess. The charmed baryons are produced with a proton beam impinging into a target, due to the parity conservation in the strong force, the initial polarization is perpendicular to the production plane (xz) and the crystal is bent in yz to induce the spin rotation. Similarly to the Λ case, the spin precession angle ϕ is sensitive to the MDM

$$\phi \approx \frac{g-2}{2} \gamma \theta_C, \quad (1.71)$$

where γ is the Lorentz factor and θ_C is the crystal bending angle [46]. The presence of a non-zero EDM induce the spin rotation to be also in the xz plane and the polarization after the precession is equal to

$$\mathbf{P} \approx \left(\frac{d}{g-2} P_0 (\cos \phi - 1), P_0 \cos \phi, P_0 \sin \phi \right). \quad (1.72)$$

An experiment to be performed at the LHC and to be developed in two different phases has been proposed [69]. The first stage, called TWOCRIST, consists in a proof-of-principle to be performed at the Interaction Region 3 (IR3) of the LHC with the aim of measuring the channeling efficiency in the crystals at the LHC energy and to study the backgrounds. In addition, it is a very useful test to validate the machine and detector operational capabilities and verify the achievable proton rate on target. The proof of principle is foreseen to take data in 2025 with a simplified apparatus. A second phase envisage an experiment named ALADDIN, to collect the first physics data for the electromagnetic dipole moments measurement and to be performed during the Run 4 of the LHC.

Figure 1.10: Scheme of the IR3 proof of principle setup for ALADDIN.

The experimental setup, represented schematically in Fig 1.10, is composed by a first bent crystal, with a bending angle of about $50 \mu\text{rad}$, to extract protons from the LHC beam halo. After about 100 m, a system composed by a 2 cm wide tungsten target and a second bent crystal are responsible for the production and spin precession of the charmed baryons. This second crystal has a bending angle of 7 mrad and directs the channeled particles in a spectrometer. At the end of the apparatus, a RICH detector is employed for particle identification. Once the Λ_c^+ are produced, the idea is to exploit their decay into $p\pi^-K^+$ to reconstruct them and extract the polarization after the precession with an amplitude analysis. For the case of the Ξ^+ , the dominant final state considered is $\Xi^-\pi^+\pi^+$. The daughter particles are bent by an in-situ warm dipole magnet, MCBWV.4L3.B2, featuring a magnetic field strength of 1.1 T and an effective length of 1.7 m. The tracking system is needed to detect and reconstruct the particles and is composed by four tracking stations, two upstream and two downstream of the dipole magnet, covering an acceptance in the very forward region, at pseudorapidity $\eta > 5$. Each station is composed by Silicon pixel sensors inside the secondary vacuum of a Roman Pot, inside the LHC beam pipe. The sensors are LHCb VELO pixel sensors, each one is $200 \mu\text{m}$ thick and built in p-in-n technology. The pixel dimension is $55 \times 55 \mu\text{m}^2$ with a pitch of $12 \mu\text{m}$ and a maximum readout rate of 600 MHz/cm^2 . It is organized in tiles with an area of $15 \times 43 \text{ mm}^2$, each one readout by three VeloPix ASICs, connected to the sensor via bump-bonding. The RICH detector aims to distinguish between protons, pions and kaons up to 1 TeV/c momentum. The radiator gas proposed is helium with a refractive index $n = 1.000035$, while the length of the detector is of 5.0 m.

With 1.4×10^{13} proton on target, considering about to years of data taking, the expected sensitivity on the charm baryon MDM is $2 \times 10^{-2} \mu_N$ and on the EDM of the order of $10^{-16} e \text{ cm}$. These results would be the first measurement ever and would provide first experimental checks for the theoretical models.

A small fraction of this thesis involved preliminary studies carried out for the TWOCRYST test. Using parametric simulations, it has been determined that among the existing magnets in the IR3 region, specifically the MCBWV magnet and the MBW magnet, which is 3.4 m long and has a magnetic field of 1.4 T, the first is more suitable. This conclusion has been reached by computing the acceptance, defined as the ratio of particles exiting the magnet to the total number generated. In evaluating the acceptance, trajectory deviations caused by the two crystals, beam spot size, magnetic bending and the opening angle of daughter particles have been considered. The MCBWV magnet demonstrates the highest acceptance, around 90%. Additionally, an acceptance scan has been conducted as a function of the magnet's length and aperture radius, with considerations for potentially developing a dedicated magnet in the future. After selecting the MCBWV magnet, the mass resolution has been analyzed as a function of the tracking station's size. It has been concluded that a minimum of 0.4 m is required to achieve a mass res-

Figure 1.11: Λ_c^+ daughter particles (proton, pion and kaon) in the transversal plane, at the fixed longitudinal tracking stations positions. On the left the first layer of the upstream tracking station is shown, while on the right it is the last layer of the downstream tracking station.

olution below 40 MeV, essential for distinguishing the Λ_c^+ signal from the D^+ and D_s^+ meson background.

The acceptance of the tracking stations has also been evaluated. As shown in Fig. 1.11, the first tracker achieves 100% acceptance, while the final station requires two VELO tiles to cover 95% acceptance. Furthermore, a scan of the acceptance as a function of the distance from the beam axis suggested that a maximum displacement of 6.5 mm is possible, indicating the necessity for Roman Pots, to operate close to the beam. Lastly, preliminary studies on hadron yields revealed that the D^+ is the most abundant hadron after channeling, with an estimated yield of approximately 1000 events after a few days of data-taking at 10^6 p/s. To achieve similar yields for Λ_c^+ candidates, it was estimated that a couple of months of running at the same flux would be required.

This preliminary studies have been useful to demonstrate the feasibility of a first test exploiting the already in-situ magnet and to give general instructions about the set-up. Currently a more sophisticated simulation, which uses the DD4HEP framework, has been put in place to define more accurately the design.

2.1 LHCb experiment at CERN

LHCb is one of the four main experiments at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), located at the CERN (Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire) laboratory in Geneva. Up to date, LHC is the most powerful and world's largest particle accelerator. It boosts protons in a 27-km ring at a depth of about 100 m underground [70]. It made them collide at a center of mass energy (\sqrt{s}) of 7 TeV from 2010 to 2011 and 8 TeV during 2012. These three years of data-taking are collectively called Run 1 of the LHC. During the Run 2 (2015-2018), the energy was increased up to 13 TeV. It was followed by the Long Shutdown 2 (LS2) phase, when the detector has been upgraded to efficiently operate at an instantaneous luminosity about five times higher than in the original LHCb configuration, while data are being collected at a center-of-mass energy of 13.6 TeV. At the time of the writing of this thesis, the Run 3 is ongoing, which has started in 2022 and is continuing until 2026.

At LHC, two proton beams travel in opposite directions in separate beam pipes. The beams are curved in the ring thanks to strong magnetic field maintained by superconducting magnets, specifically dipole magnets, while quadrupole magnets keep the beams focused. The superconducting state allows to efficiently conduct electricity without resistance or loss of energy and requires a magnet chilling to -271.3° C. LHC is actually the last step of the accelerator complex at CERN. It is made of a succession of machines which gradually accelerate proton beams, thanks to radio frequency cavities, and its scheme is in Fig. 2.1. The proton source is simply hydrogen gas. An electric field is applied to strip hydrogen atoms of their electrons producing protons. The first accelerator is Linac 2, where protons are boosted to the energy of 50 MeV. They are then transferred to the Proton Synchrotron Booster (PSB), where they reach an energy of 1.4 GeV. It is followed by the Proton Synchrotron (PS), which pushes the beam to 25 GeV. Protons are then injected into the Super Proton Synchrotron (SPS) where they achieve an energy of 450 GeV, before being directed into the two LHC beam pipes. It takes approximately 20 minutes for the protons to reach their peak energy of 6.5 TeV. The two beams collide inside the four detectors, ALICE, ATLAS, CMS and LHCb. In addition to proton-proton collisions, also heavy ion and proton-gas collisions take place. Dedicated ion runs are usually schedule at the end of each year of data-taking.

The LHCb experiment is primarily dedicated to the study of heavy flavor physics [71], with a particular focus on searching for new physics through the examination of rare decays of beauty and charm hadrons, and the investigation of CP -violating phenomena. Despite its primary focus, LHCb has made significant contributions in other areas of particle physics as well. These include breakthroughs in heavy hadron spectroscopy, such as the discovery of novel tetraquark and pentaquark states, and in the

7/3/2018

The CERN accelerator complex Complexe des accélérateurs du CERN

Figure 2.1: Accelerator complex at CERN.

search for potential new light particles [72], [73], [74], [75]. Additionally, the experiment has played a vital role in the study of heavy ion collisions, including both proton-lead and lead-lead interactions. Furthermore, LHCb is unique among the LHC experiments in its ability to collect data from proton-gas fixed-target collisions, thanks to its gas target system, SMOG (2) [76].

The excellent performance of the LHC enabled the LHCb collaboration to collect over 3 fb^{-1} of data during the 2011-2012 period (Run 1) and 5.7 fb^{-1} during 2015-2018 (Run 2), achieving an efficiency exceeding 90% relative to the total luminosity delivered by the accelerator. The progression of integrated luminosity over the years is depicted in Fig. 2.2. Run 3 of the LHCb experiment began in 2022 and is expected to conclude in 2026. As of the time of writing, approximately 9 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity have been collected. This chapter focuses on describing the detector configuration used during Run 1 and Run 2, which corresponds to the dataset analyzed in this thesis. A discussion of the upgraded detector employed during Run 3, particularly the Upstream Tracker, to which the author has contributed, is presented in the final chapter.

These large data sets have allowed for the reconstruction of an unprecedentedly large sample of D , B , and heavy baryons, enabling the LHCb collaboration to conduct precision measurements with unparalleled accuracy. The LHC is expected to remain the most prolific source of B mesons in the foreseeable future, with significant production

of b -baryons as well. In just one year of data collection, about 10^{12} $b\bar{b}$ pairs could be produced during Run 2, given an instantaneous luminosity of $4 \times 10^{32} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and a pile-up (the average number of visible interactions per beam-beam crossing) of approximately 2.5. The luminosity collected by LHCb is lower than the maximum reachable, due to the leveling of the beams, which means that the experiment's luminosity can be adjusted independently of the other interaction points by altering the beam focus at its interaction point or by modifying the transverse beam overlap. The primary motivation is the limitation of the hardware L0 trigger: at luminosities above about $4 \times 10^{32} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, the hadronic and single-lepton trigger paths would saturate, requiring higher thresholds and thereby reducing efficiency for many key signals. This choice offers additional advantages: it reduces the occurrence of multiple primary pp interactions per bunch crossing, facilitating the correct association of primary vertices to particles. Additionally, it mitigates radiation damage and improves the separation of primary and secondary vertices, which is crucial for many analyses in LHCb. This choice leads to optimized physics performance and is beneficial for the trigger, since some selections do not scale with the luminosity.

Figure 2.2: Integrated luminosity in the different years of data taking during the LHC Run 1, Run 2 and Run 3 up to 2024.

The LHCb detector is a single-arm forward spectrometer, distinct in geometry from the other LHC detectors. This design choice comes from the relatively low mass of b and \bar{b} quarks compared to the energy scales involved in LHC pp collisions, which results in $b\bar{b}$ pairs being produced at high pseudorapidity. Moreover, there is a significant correlation between the b and \bar{b} quarks, causing them to predominantly emerge in either the forward or backward directions. Consequently, the LHCb geometry is optimized to capture a substantial fraction of these produced beauty particles, despite covering a small solid

angle (approximately 4% of the full solid angle). Specifically, about 27% of b or \bar{b} quarks produced in pp collisions fall within the LHCb acceptance. The total number of events containing a $b\bar{b}$ pair can be determined as

$$N_{b\bar{b}} = \sigma(pp \rightarrow b\bar{b}X) \times \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}, \quad (2.1)$$

where σ represents the cross-section, and \mathcal{L}_{int} denotes the integrated luminosity. For 13 TeV collisions within the LHCb pseudorapidity range, the cross-section $\sigma(pp \rightarrow b\bar{b}X)$ is measured to be $154 \pm 14 \mu\text{b}$ [77]. This geometric configuration also benefits the detection of charm particles, as their masses are similar to those of beauty particles if compared to the collision energy at the LHC. The charm cross-section for 13 TeV collisions in the LHCb pseudorapidity range is $\sigma(pp \rightarrow c\bar{c}X) = 2940 \pm 240 \mu\text{b}$ [78]. It is almost 20 times larger than $b\bar{b}$ one, making the LHCb experiment a suitable environment to study charm decays.

The LHCb detector covers a region extending from approximately 10 mrad to 300 mrad horizontally and 250 mrad vertically, providing larger acceptance in the horizontal plane due to the dipole magnetic field influence on charged particles. This corresponds to a pseudorapidity (η) range of $2 < \eta < 5$, where pseudorapidity is defined as $\eta = -\ln(\tan(\theta/2))$, with θ being the angle relative to the beam axis.

Figure 2.3: LHCb detector, side view.

The LHCb detector layout is shown in Fig. 2.3. The z -axis is chosen along the beam,

and the y -axis along the vertical direction, while the center is positioned at the pp collision point. It can be described by three main parts:

- the tracking system,
- the particle identification system,
- the trigger system.

2.2 Tracking system

The tracking system is composed by the VERTex LOcator (VELO), followed by the Tracker Turicensis (TT) and three Tracking stations (T1,T2,T3). These sub-detectors provide measurements to reconstruct the primary interaction vertex, the decay vertex and the trajectories of charged particles in the magnetic field and their momenta.

Figure 2.4: VELO sub-detector layout.

2.2.1 VELO

Beginning at the pp collision point, the first subdetector encountered is the VELO, as depicted in Fig. 2.4. The VELO plays a crucial role in achieving precise measurements of both primary and secondary vertices, which is essential for reconstructing beauty and charm hadrons, given their typical mean flight lengths of approximately 1 cm and a few millimeters, respectively. The VELO is composed of 21 circular silicon modules arranged along the beam axis, each capable of measuring both the radial (r) and azimuthal (ϕ) coordinates. Additionally, there are two planes located upstream of the interaction point, oriented perpendicular to the beam line, known as the *pile-up veto system*. This system's purpose is to identify events with multiple pp interactions.

Each VELO module features a disk-like shape, divided into two retractable halves. The central opening of these modules allows for the passage of the proton beam. During the transition from collision to injection mode, the two halves of the modules retract, a

mechanism designed to protect them from radiation damage during the injection phase. During pp collisions, the VELO modules are positioned just 8 mm away from the beam, with the two halves overlapping. To minimize the amount of material traversed by charged particles before reaching the sensors, the VELO modules are housed in a vessel that maintains a secondary vacuum.

Each half of a VELO module consists of two silicon microstrip sensors, each with a thickness of $220\ \mu\text{m}$. These microstrips are strategically arranged to measure the radial distance from the beam (r) and the azimuthal angle (ϕ) of the hits generated by ionizing particles. The z -coordinate of a hit is determined based on the position of the module in which the hit occurs. The r -sensors are composed of stubs arranged concentrically, divided into four regions of 45° each, while the ϕ -strips are oriented radially. The adoption of this cylindrical geometry has been demonstrated to enable rapid reconstruction of tracks and vertices within the LHCb trigger.

The resolution of primary vertex reconstruction depends on the number of tracks utilized in reconstructing the vertex, as depicted in Fig. 2.5. For a typical event involving approximately 25 tracks, the resolution along the beam direction z is estimated to be around $71\ \mu\text{m}$, while in the direction perpendicular to the beam it is about $13\ \mu\text{m}$ [79]. The impact parameter (IP) of a track, defined as the distance between the track and the primary vertex at the point of closest approach, is a critical quantity for distinguishing displaced vertices from primary ones. The resolution of the IP is of the order of tens of micrometers and is inversely proportional to the particle transverse momentum, as shown in Fig. 2.5. At low momentum, multiple Coulomb scattering in the detector material dominates, causing larger deviations in the extrapolated track position and hence poorer IP resolution. At high momentum, the scattering contribution becomes negligible, and the resolution is limited instead by the intrinsic precision of the vertex detector and its alignment.

Figure 2.5: (Left) primary vertex resolution as a function of the number of tracks (N) used to reconstruct the vertex. (Right) resolution of the x component of IPs. Only events with 1 reconstructed PV are used.

2.2.2 Tracker Turicensis

The Tracker Turicensis is placed between RICH1 and the dipole magnet, with its primary goal being the enhancement of momentum resolution for particles traversing the entire detector. Additionally, it plays a crucial role in suppressing ghost tracks, which are

Figure 2.6: Tracker Turicensis layer. Different colors stands for different readout sectors.

spurious tracks that do not correspond to real particle trajectories. The tracker utilizes silicon strip sensors arranged in four layers, each with a pitch of approximately $200\ \mu\text{m}$ and a thickness of about $500\ \mu\text{m}$.

In the first and last layers, the strips are oriented vertically, while in the second and third layers, the strips are rotated by a stereo angle of $+5^\circ$ and -5° , respectively, to provide vertical position information. Each layer functions as a planar tracking station, with dimensions of $138.6\ \text{cm}$ in width and $132.4\ \text{cm}$ in height, covering the entire detector acceptance, as illustrated in Fig. 2.6. The electronics readout, support system, and cooling structure are positioned above and below the active area of the detector, outside the region of acceptance.

2.2.3 T stations

Figure 2.7: T stations scheme. On the left the layers scheme, while on the right the distinction between IT (red) and OT (blue). Dimensions are expressed in cm.

The three tracking stations, T1, T2, and T3, are positioned downstream of the magnet and are composed of an Inner Tracker (IT) and an Outer Tracker (OT). The IT is located

closest to the beam pipe, while the OT covers the outer region. Due to its proximity to the beam pipe, the particle flux in the IT is approximately 20 times higher than in the OT. Consequently, the IT utilizes silicon strip technology, which offers higher granularity and greater radiation resistance compared to the OT. Each IT station consists of four individual detector boxes arranged around the beam pipe, as shown in Fig. 2.7. Each box contains four detection layers, with each layer composed of seven detector modules. The four layers are configured similarly to those in the TT station, with the first and last layers oriented vertically and the two middle layers rotated by $\pm 5^\circ$. The OT, on the other hand, employs a drift-time detector technology to accommodate the need for covering a larger area. It is designed as an array of gas-tight straw-tube modules, each containing two staggered layers of drift tubes with an inner diameter of 4.9 mm. The drift time is less than 50 ns, and the position resolution is approximately $200 \mu\text{m}$. These performance levels are achieved using tubes filled with a mixture of 70% argon and 30% CO_2 . The OT modules are arranged with the same geometry as the silicon trackers. From these measurements, the particle momentum is determined with high precision; the relative uncertainty is approximately 0.5% at low momentum, increasing to around 1% at $p = 200 \text{ GeV}/c$, as depicted in Fig. 2.8.

Figure 2.8: Relative uncertainty on the momentum reconstruction measured using muons from $J/\Psi \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ decays [80].

2.2.4 Magnet

As previously mentioned, the momentum of a particle is determined from its curvature in the magnetic field, which is generated by a warm dipole magnet. This magnet allows for a forward acceptance of $\pm 250 \text{ mrad}$ vertically and $\pm 300 \text{ mrad}$ horizontally. The bending power is defined as $\int \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{l}$, where \mathbf{l} is the particle trajectory. The bending power experienced by particles traversing the entire detector is approximately 4 Tm. The magnet was specifically designed to meet two conflicting requirements: maintaining an integrated field value $\leq 2 \text{ Tm}$ within the RICH detectors envelope, while maximizing the field strength in the region between the TT and T stations. To mitigate systematic effects on charged particle tracking, the field direction is periodically reversed. The primary component of the magnetic field, B_y , is shown along the z -axis for one polarity in Fig. 2.9. The magnetic field strength has been measured across the entire detector acceptance using Hall probes, allowing for comparison with simulations generated by TOSCA. An

Figure 2.9: Vertical component of the magnetic field in the tracking system. Below, classification of tracks types.

array of Hall probes was built to scan the horizontal and vertical directions, with a precision of 1 mm. The mapping campaign allows to measure the three components of the magnetic field for both magnet polarities, on a grid of $8 \times 8 \times 10 \text{ cm}^3$ covering the full tracking volume. The relative precision achieved for the grid is approximately 4×10^{-4} . The agreement between the measured values and simulations is within 1% throughout most of the detector, except in the upstream region (VELO, RICH1), where the discrepancy is around 3.5% [71]. This discrepancy can be attributed to the computational uncertainties in TOSCA and the proximity of massive iron reinforcements embedded in the concrete of the experimental hall.

2.2.5 Track reconstruction algorithm

Several algorithms work together to reconstruct the trajectories of charged particles (tracks) as they traverse the LHCb tracking system. Depending on the tracking sub-detectors involved in the reconstruction process, different track types are defined, as depicted in Fig. 2.9:

- **VELO tracks:** Particles that only traverse the VELO, typically those produced at wide angles relative to the beam direction.
- **Upstream tracks:** Low-momentum particles that exit the geometric acceptance before reaching T1 due to the magnetic field. Although the residual magnetic field between the VELO and TT can be used to measure their momentum, the relative error is approximately 20%.
- **Downstream tracks:** Long-lived neutral particles, such as Λ and K_S^0 , which decay

between the VELO and the TT. Their charged daughter particles then traverse the TT and the three T stations.

- **T tracks:** Tracks that only have hits in the T1-T3 stations. Similar to downstream tracks, they include decay products of long-lived particles that decay far from the primary vertex. Many of these tracks originate from secondary interactions with the material of the mechanical structures and from back-scattering particles from the calorimeters. Next chapter is focused on the characterization of their reconstruction, efficiency and resolution.
- **Long tracks:** Particles that traverse the entire tracking system, including hits in both the VELO and T1-T3 stations, with optional hits in the TT.

Track reconstruction begins by identifying initial track candidates, known as track seeds, within the VELO region and the T stations, where the magnetic field is minimal. Once identified, these tracks are refined using a Kalman filter, which accounts for multiple scattering effects and corrects for energy loss (dE/dX) due to ionization. The quality of the reconstructed tracks is evaluated using the χ^2 of the fit and the pull distribution of the track parameters. In the VELO, charged particle tracks are approximated as straight-line segments, since in this region the effect of the magnetic field is negligible. For T tracks, the track search is performed in two steps: first, the xy projection is analyzed to identify track candidates, followed by a search for hits in the stereo layers. The track models used in the xz and yz planes are cubic and linear parameterizations, respectively, and the fit is performed using a weighted least-squares method to provide reference states for input to the Kalman-based fitter.

The reconstruction algorithm proceeds hierarchically, first attempting to reconstruct Long tracks before using any remaining segments to build downstream and upstream tracks. The reconstruction of Long tracks begins with the search for VELO tracks, and two algorithms are used to promote VELO tracks to Long tracks. The first algorithm, known as forward tracking [81], reconstructs the particle momentum from a VELO track and one hit in the T station, enabling the extrapolation of the trajectory. If hits are found along this extrapolation in the T stations, they are added to define the Long track. The second method, track matching, combines independently reconstructed VELO tracks and T tracks. In both algorithms, if hits compatible with the Long track are found in the TT, they are added to the trajectory to improve momentum resolution and help discriminate against fake tracks. Long tracks are widely used in analysis due to their better spatial and momentum resolution compared to other track types.

Downstream tracks are reconstructed by starting with segments in the T stations, which are then propagated back to the magnetic field region, and compatible hits in the TT are added to the tracks. Conversely, upstream tracks are reconstructed by starting with VELO segments, which are then matched with compatible hits in the TT, ensuring incompatibility with any T station segments. For both upstream and downstream tracks, at least three hits in the TT stations are required for matching.

Finally, all reconstructed tracks are compared using the clone killer algorithm: if two tracks share most of their hits, only the best one is retained, based on the highest goodness of fit obtained from the Kalman filter and the total number of hits that make up the track. Generally, Long tracks are preferred over other types due to their best resolution; upstream tracks are preferred over VELO tracks, and downstream tracks are preferred over T tracks.

2.3 Particle identification system

Particle identification is a key ingredient of the measurements done with the LHCb detector. Specific subdetectors are devoted in providing these information.

2.3.1 RICH

Figure 2.10: RICH detectors: (left) view of RICH1, (right) a overhead view of RICH2.

Figure 2.11: Cherenkov angle as a function of the particle momentum.

LHCb exploits two Ring Imaging Cherenkov Detectors (RICH) to identify particles, illustrated in Fig. 2.10. They are based on the fact that charged particles traversing a

medium with a velocity higher than the light velocity in that medium, emit the so called Cherenkov light. The radiation is emitted at an angle θ_C with respect to the particle momentum related to the particle velocity,

$$\cos \theta_C = \frac{1}{n\beta}, \quad (2.2)$$

with n the medium refractive index. From the measurement of the Cherenkov light and knowing the value of n index, the particle velocity is extracted. Comparing this quantity with the particle momentum obtained from the tracking system, it is possible to determine the particle type, through the value of its mass. The need of two of these detectors is to cover the full momentum range. In fact, thanks to different media it is possible to access particle discrimination in different momentum range, as can be noticed in Fig. 2.11. The first detector (RICH1) is placed between VELO and TT and uses fluorobutane (C_4F_{10}) gas radiators to cover the low range momentum between about 1 and 60 GeV/c. The first radiator has $n = 1.03$ and constitutes a 5 cm layer to distinguish between particles with few GeV/c momentum, the second gaseous layer fills the remaining volume and has $n = 1.0015$, responsible to distinguish at higher momenta. The Cherenkov light is deflected by a combination of flat and spherical mirrors and once brought out of the detector acceptance, it is detected by an Hybrid Photon Detectors (HPDs) array. Since HPDs are sensitive to the magnetic field, they are surrounded by external iron shields. RICH2 is placed between the T stations and the first muon station; it is meant to distinguish between particles with momenta from 15 GeV/c up to 100 GeV/c, using CF_4 as radiator, with $n = 1.0005$. It does not cover the full acceptance, but it covers from 15 mrad to 120 mrad (100 mrad) in the bending (non-bending) plane. The light detection system is the same described for RICH1.

Figure 2.12: LHCb calorimeter scheme.

2.3.2 Calorimeter

The LHCb calorimeter (Fig. 2.12) performs multiple tasks: in addition to being an integral part of the particle identification system, distinguishing between high transverse energy hadrons, electrons and photons, it also plays a crucial role in the hardware trigger, specifically the first level trigger (L0), which takes decisions within 4 μs after the proton collisions. The calorimeter measures both the energy and the position of particles, which is essential for the LHCb physics program, especially for the precise reconstruction of photons and π^0 mesons.

The calorimeter is composed of three main sections: preceding the main calorimeter, there is a Scintillator Pad Detector (SPD) and a single-layer Pre-Shower detector (PS). These are followed by the Electromagnetic Calorimeter (ECAL) and the Hadronic Calorimeter (HCAL). The SPD/PS includes a 15 mm thick lead absorber sandwiched between two scintillator pad layers, corresponding to about 2.5-3.0 radiation lengths (X_0). The SPD is crucial for distinguishing between charged and neutral particles, particularly for separating photons from electrons, while the lead layer initiates the shower. The PS assists in differentiating between electrons and pions, which have distinct shower lengths.

To achieve optimal energy resolution, it is essential to fully contain the showers from high-energy photons, leading to the selection of an ECAL thickness of $25 X_0$. The LHCb ECAL is a shashlik detector, a type of sampling calorimeter that alternates between 2 mm thick lead absorber layers and 4 mm thick scintillating material (plastic wavelength-shifting fibers). Wavelength-shifting (WLS) fibers transmit the scintillation light to photomultipliers for readout. The transverse dimension of the stack is determined by the Molière radius, which is 3.5 cm. The energy resolution of the ECAL can be expressed as $\sigma_E/E = a/\sqrt{E} \oplus b \oplus c/E$, where a , b , and c are the stochastic, constant, and noise terms, respectively, with energy in GeV. During test beams, these values were found to be $8.5\% < a < 9.5\%$ and $b \sim 0.8\%$, depending on the type of module and test conditions.

The lateral segmentation of the calorimeter varies, as the hit density changes by two orders of magnitude from the beam axis outward. Both the SPD/PS and the ECAL have segmentation that varies across three regions. However, due to the larger dimensions of hadronic showers, the HCAL is segmented into two zones with larger cell sizes. The LHCb HCAL is responsible for measuring the energy of hadronic showers and uses a similar sampling technique, with iron as the absorber and scintillating tiles as the active material. The absorber layers are 16 mm thick, while the scintillating layers are 4 mm thick. The energy resolution terms for the HCAL were determined to be $a \sim 69\%$ and $b \sim 9\%$.

The good ECAL resolution allows for effective discrimination between electrons and charged hadrons, while the HCAL provides information for the Level-0 trigger to select purely hadronic events. This trigger searches for high transverse energy (E_T) particles, forms clusters by adding the E_T of 2×2 cells, and selects the clusters with the highest E_T . The total number of SPD cells with a hit is also counted to measure the charged track multiplicity in each beam crossing.

2.3.3 Muon system

The muon system consists of five stations positioned along the beamline. The first station (M1) is located before the ECAL, while the remaining stations are placed downstream of the calorimeters, interleaved with iron layers to absorb particles that are not muons or neutrinos (see Fig. 2.13). The minimum momentum required for a muon to traverse all five stations is approximately 6 GeV/c, given that the total absorber thickness, including the calorimeters, is around 20 interaction lengths. The placement of the M1 station before the calorimeters serves to enhance the resolution of the transverse momentum. Each detector in the muon system is divided into rectangular logical pads, which provide information on the particle position. The system predominantly employs Multi-Wire Proportional Chamber (MWPC) technology. However, due to the higher particle flux in M1, Gas Electron Multiplier (GEM) technology is used here, owing to its superior radiation resistance. The muon system achieves a 95% trigger efficiency for events involving muons by using a trigger algorithm that requires a five-fold coincidence within

Figure 2.13: (Left) side view of the muon system, (right) layout of a single muon station, with the four regions of different granularity.

a time window shorter than the 25 ns interval between pp collisions.

2.4 LHCb data flow

2.4.1 Trigger system

A crucial component of the detection process is the trigger system. At the LHC, proton-proton collisions take place with a bunch crossing rate of 40 MHz. Due to the limited capability of storage, it is impossible to store them all. The trigger system plays a vital role in reducing the amount of data to be stored by selecting events of interest, particularly those involving the production of $c\bar{c}$ or $b\bar{b}$ quarks, while rejecting generic inelastic pp events. The latter occur at a rate that is one to two orders of magnitude higher than the former. The aim of the trigger is to reduce the event rate from 40 MHz to 12.5 kHz. The LHCb trigger system consists of two sequential stages (see Fig. 2.14): first, the Level-0 trigger (L0), which operates synchronously with the bunch crossing frequency, and then the High Level Trigger (HLT), a two-stage software trigger designed to validate the L0 decision and perform event reconstruction for further analysis.

L0 hardware trigger

The L0 trigger is entirely hardware-based and reduces the event rate to 1 MHz, enabling the readout of the entire detector. Since B mesons have relatively large masses, their decay products often exhibit high transverse momentum (p_T) and energy (E_T). Therefore, the L0 trigger utilizes information from the calorimeter system to select hadron, electron, and photon clusters with E_T exceeding a fixed threshold, as reported in Tab. 2.1 [82]. For instance, for the L0Muon trigger, the transverse momentum of each track is estimated under the assumption that the associated particle originates from the interaction point and traverses all five muon stations. For each event, the trigger decision is based on either the highest p_T muon track (L0Muon) or both of the two highest p_T muon tracks (L0DiMuon). To enhance the efficiency of detecting J/ψ decays, particularly loose occupancy cuts are applied in the L0DiMuon decision, especially concerning the number of SPD hits. The p_T thresholds for muon tracks across different years of data taking

Figure 2.14: Run 2 trigger system scheme.

are provided in Table 2.1. The number of primary pp interactions per bunch crossing is estimated using the VELO detector, while the number of hits in the SPD allows for the deduction of the track multiplicity to avoid saturation at HLT stage. The L0 trigger decision unit combines all this information to filter out non-interesting events.

Table 2.1: L0 trigger lines thresholds for the Run 2 data taking years.

year	L0Muon [GeV/c]	L0Electron [GeV]	L0Hadron [GeV]
2015	$p_T > 2.80$	$E_T > 2.70$	$E_T > 3.60$
2016	$p_T > 1.80$	$E_T > 2.40$	$E_T > 3.70$
2017	$p_T > 1.35$	$E_T > 2.11$	$E_T > 3.46$
2018	$p_T > 1.75$	$E_T > 2.38$	$E_T > 3.75$

High Level Trigger

The HLT is software-based, running on the CPUs of the Event Filter Farm (EFF), and is divided into two stages: HLT1 and HLT2. The algorithms are designed to optimize the performance within the available processing time and to perform the reconstruction and the selection of the events. The goal is to reduce the L0 trigger input rate down to a storable rate, such as 12.5 kHz for Run 2, and 3.5 kHz and 5 kHz for the 2011 and 2012 data-taking periods, respectively.

HLT1 rejects events with an Outer Tracker (OT) occupancy greater than 20% because reconstructing these events would be too time consuming. Following this, the so called L0 confirmation is performed by reconstructing particles in the VELO and T stations that correspond to L0 objects. If the L0 object is a photon or a neutral pion, HLT1 ensures that the object is not charged. The main lines used in this analysis are:

- **HLT1TrackMVA**: selecting a single track with high p_T displaced from any PVs;

Figure 2.15: LHCb data flow for real data and simulation.

- **HLT1TwoTrackMVA**: requiring vertices composed by two high p_T track and displaced from all PV.

After HLT1 reduces the event rate to approximately a factor 20 (10) in Run2 (Run1), HLT2 performs a full reconstruction similar to the offline analysis. The difference consists in the absence of the Kalman filter for track fitting, which would be too computationally intensive online. HLT2 applies loose cuts on momentum and impact parameter to select tracks for constructing composite particles. Additionally, it applies cuts on the invariant mass or the pointing angle of the B momentum toward the primary vertex. The process concludes with either an inclusive or exclusive selection, with the latter allowing for looser cuts due to its lower final rate. Inclusive triggers select decays where the final state particles are only partially reconstructed, making them less dependent on the online reconstruction. On the other end, exclusive lines select specific decays, applying requirements on the PID of the final particles. The final trigger decision is the logical OR of all the selections.

As illustrated in Fig. 2.14, events are temporarily buffered to disk between HLT1 and HLT2 stages while the online detector calibration and alignment are performed. This process is crucial for achieving optimal reconstruction at the HLT2 level using the best information from the detector. Two types of HLT output streams are utilized:

- **Full stream**: the entire raw event data is saved, allowing for future reprocessing to improve the reconstruction or to select new decay channels. These datasets tend to be large, so a set of preselection criteria, known as *Stripping*, is applied to reduce their size. Typically specific decay channels are extracted for the analysis from the *Stripping* output.
- **Turbo stream**: only partial event and raw detector information are saved directly from the HLT2 output. Various configurations are available, such as saving only the signal candidates or predefined parts of the event. This format is particularly useful for collecting dedicated calibration samples, which can be employed for tracking and PID data-simulation corrections.

2.4.2 Offline software framework

The entire LHCb software, both online and offline, is executed within the GAUDI framework [83]. This framework ensures that all LHCb tools and algorithms are consistently available, maintaining a unified environment for all LHCb analyses. The main components of the data processing workflow are depicted in Fig. 2.15:

- **Generation and Simulation:** The `Gauss` package [84] allows the generation of simulated Monte Carlo (MC) events. Primary pp interactions are modeled using `PYTHIA` [85], while the decays of b - and c -hadrons are handled by the `EvtGen` package [86]. Additionally, the `Geant4` toolkit [87] is used to simulate the particles interaction with the detector.
- **Digitization:** The `Boole` application [88] simulates the detector response to the generated events. The output of this process is a digitized version of the detector response, which serves as the MC equivalent of the real data.
- **Trigger:** Both simulated and real data are processed through the three trigger stages (L0, HLT1, and HLT2) as previously described, using the `Moore` framework [89].
- **Reconstruction:** Signal hits within the detector are clustered, and the full event reconstruction is performed by the `Brunel` offline application [90]. Particle properties, such as momentum and PID probability variables, are calculated and stored in Data Storage Tape (DST) files.
- **Analysis:** The `DaVinci` software package [91] utilizes the information stored in DST files to compute various kinematic and topological variables during event selection. This step includes determining quantities such as the invariant masses of decayed particles, their flight distances, and decay times. The output from `DaVinci` is in the form of ROOT `Ntuples` data files [92], which are then used for conducting physics analyses.

T track performance studies for electromagnetic dipole moment measurements

In the LHCb experiment, physics analyses have never employed particles reconstructed exclusively with T tracks to date. Instead, final particles are typically reconstructed combining information from the tracking stations upstream and downstream the magnet, mainly Long and to less extent Downstream tracks, to maximize the detector capabilities, thereby achieving the highest possible resolution on the charged track parameters. Despite the suboptimal performance of T tracks, it will be shown their feasibility for physics analyses. This is particularly relevant for the measurement of electromagnetic dipole moments, as outlined in Chapter 1. In this Chapter, we detail the performance studies of T tracks, the challenges that appear in their reconstruction and the methodologies we developed to enhance their performance where possible. It is the first time that these tracks have been considered for physics analyses, thus we developed data driven techniques to compare the performance on data and simulation. Due to the poor momentum resolution, the bottleneck of their reconstruction is the vertexing part. For this reason, different vertexing algorithms have been studied and a new one is presented, designed adhoc for T tracks. Its performance studies have been developed in the context of this thesis work and will be presented at the end of the chapter. This extensive study provides a demonstration that the LHCb physics reach can be expanded exploiting also T tracks, opening new physics opportunities for the experiment. The content of this Chapter has been already published in [93].

For the performance study we have considered Run 2 data collected by the LHCb experiment between 2015 and 2018 with a total integrated luminosity of 6 fb^{-1} . Since we know that the sensitivity to the electromagnetic dipole moments is enhanced when the long-lived particles transverse a larger integrated magnetic field, we have selected Λ and K_S^0 decaying into the $p\pi^-$ and $\pi^+\pi^-$ between 6 and 7.6 m from the interaction point along the beam direction, decaying after the magnetic field region, thus that their polarization precession is maximal. The $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$, with $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$, $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $K_S^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays are chosen as benchmark channels for these studies. The first decay can be exploited for the Λ electromagnetic dipole moments measurement, since the Λ baryon has been measured to be fully polarized before the precession and therefore gives the highest sensitivity to the dipole moments. The second decay is very useful as control sample, since it has a null polarization due to the pseudoscalar meson involved. In addition, the two decays are cross-feed-backgrounds, so it is necessary to consider one as main physical background for the other, and viceversa. The flight length of Λ_b^0 and B^0 hadrons is typically around 10 mm, thus they decay inside the VELO detector. Muons are reconstructed as Long tracks, providing a precise determination of their momenta and of the J/ψ decay vertex, which coincides with the decay vertex of the Λ_b^0 or B^0 hadron. The Λ and K_S^0 candidates are reconstructed as combinations of two

Figure 3.1: Reconstruction and selection efficiency as a function of the true Λ decay vertex position along the beam axis for simulated $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ signal events (grey) and its breakdown for different reconstruction and selection steps: the reconstruction and quality selections of the four tracks of the final state (blue); the reconstruction of the Λ and Λ_b^0 decay vertices (orange); the initial selections applied to the final-state and decaying particles as described in Table 3.1; the fraction of successful decay chain vertex fits (DTF, red); the B^0 mass veto (violet); the selection efficiency of the HBDT (maroon); and the AP veto (pink). The four-track efficiency contribution and the total efficiency (see text) are evaluated for reconstructible signal decays, while all other contributions are relative to the previous reconstruction step.

T tracks. The selection is based on the inclusive detached J/ψ trigger, which was part of the LHCb trigger strategy in the Run 1 and Run 2 data-taking campaigns [94].

For modeling various aspects of the experiment, including detector acceptance, detector response, reconstruction efficiency, and the impact of signal selection criteria, simulated samples are generated. In the simulation process, pp collisions are generated using PYTHIA [95] with a specific LHCb configuration [96]. The decays of unstable particles are handled by EVTGEN [86], with final-state radiation generated by PHOTOS [97]. The GEANT4 toolkit [98] is employed to simulate the transport of the generated particles and the detector response, as detailed in Ref. [99].

3.1 Signal candidate reconstruction and selection

3.1.1 T tracks reconstruction

The reconstruction starts with the combination of the information collected by the tracking stations to form particle trajectories, which we refer to as tracks. As mentioned, the only information used for T tracks are those coming from the T stations (T segments), exploiting a tracking algorithm called PatSeeding [81], already described in the previous chapter. Tracks are represented with a five-dimensional vector at a given z :

$$\mathbf{x} = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ t_x \\ t_y \\ q/p \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.1)$$

with $t_x = dx/dz$ (the same holds for t_y) and q/p is the charge-to-momentum ratio. The state is transformed to a state $(x, y, z, p_x, p_y, p_z, E)$, where E is the particle energy corresponding to momentum vector (p_x, p_y, p_z) at position (x, y, z) for a given mass hypothesis [100]. The performance of the track reconstruction is assessed by the efficiency and the ghost rates, computed on simulation. The efficiency is normalized with respect to the *reconstructible* tracks, which are defined on the basis of a minimum number of hits in the subdetectors. Tracks are defined as correctly *reconstructed* if at least the 70% of the associated hits are originated by the same Monte Carlo particle. In Fig. 3.1 the so called "4-track reconstruction" is visible, computed as the ratio of reconstructed particles over reconstructible as a function of the Λ z vertex position. The behavior shows that more particles are reconstructed at larger distances from the T stations, or lower values of z , which is linked to the fact that the pattern recognition assumes that all the tracks are originated at the origin, also T tracks. This assumption is closer to reality for Λ decaying at lower z .

For our decays, once the muons are reconstructed as Long tracks and the protons and pions (two pions) are reconstructed as T tracks, it is needed to combine them and find the decay vertices of the J/ψ and Λ (K_S^0), followed by the Λ_b^0 (B^0) vertex to reconstruct the full decay chain. The standard vertexing algorithm employed in the LHCb official framework is called Vertex Fitter (VF), part of the LoKi analysis toolkit [101], and it proceeds via a bottom up approach, starting from the final state particles and fitting the decays until the mother particle is reached. The information taken as input by the VF for each track is the output of the track fit, mainly the first measurement point r , the momentum at that position and the associated covariance matrix V , which can be written in block structure as

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} V_r & V_{rq} \\ V_{rq}^T & V_q \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.2)$$

Since it is symmetric and positive defined, we can define the formal inverse matrix $G = V^{-1}$ in the analogous block form,

$$G = \begin{pmatrix} G_r & G_{rq} \\ G_{rq}^T & G_q \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} V_r & V_{rq} \\ V_{rq}^T & V_q \end{pmatrix}^{-1}. \quad (3.3)$$

The VF provides the optimal fit value \mathbf{x} for the common origin vertex, alongside its covariance matrix C and the χ^2 statistic, which can be utilized to assess the quality of the fit. The algorithm begins with a first step of the Kalman filter finding a starting point of the vertex, called seed, with an associated covariance matrix. At the beginning of each iteration the covariance matrix is rescaled by a factor s , with $0 < s < 1$, to decrease its relative importance in the following vertex computation,

$$C_0^i = C_n^{i-1} \times s^2, \quad (3.4)$$

by default $s = 10^{-4}$. Then the track is transported from the reference point, in the case of the first iteration it is the measurement point, to the z component of the $i - 1$

vertex position, updating also the covariance matrix V_{kr}^i . Within an individual iteration, denoted by a superscript i , the VF algorithm advances through k steps indicated by subscripts, with each step corresponding to the inclusion of the k -th daughter particle. At each step a new iteration of the Kalman filter adjourns the position of the vertex and the covariance matrix as follows, adding the track k

$$(C_k^i)^{-1} = (C_{k-1}^i)^{-1} + (G_k^i)_r, \quad (3.5)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_k = C_k^i \left((C_{k-1}^i)^{-1} \mathbf{x}_{k-1}^i + (G_k^i)_r \mathbf{r}_k^i \right). \quad (3.6)$$

Finally also the momentum and the χ^2 are updated accordingly

$$\mathbf{q}_k^i := \mathbf{q}_k^i - (V_k^i)_{rq} (G_k^i)_{rq} (\mathbf{r}_k^i - \mathbf{x}_k^i), \quad (3.7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi^2)_k^i &= (\chi^2)_{k-1}^i + (\mathbf{r}_k^i - \mathbf{x}_k^i)^T (G_k^i)_r (\mathbf{r}_k^i - \mathbf{x}_k^i) \\ &+ (\mathbf{x}_k^i - \mathbf{x}_{k-1}^i)^T (C_{k-1}^i)^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_k^i - \mathbf{x}_{k-1}^i). \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

The iterations continue until one of the convergence criteria is satisfied,

$$|\mathbf{x}^{(i-1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(i)}| < d_1, \quad (3.9)$$

$$0 \leq (\mathbf{x}^{(i-1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(i)})^T C^{-1(i)} (\mathbf{x}^{(i-1)} - \mathbf{x}^{(i)}) \leq d_2, \text{ for } i \geq 2 \quad (3.10)$$

By default, $d_1 = 1 \mu\text{m}$ while $d_2 = 1\%$. The maximum number of iterations by default is 10, thus if the criteria are not met by the tenth iteration, then the result is a no convergence of the fit.

As said, at each step of the algorithm an extrapolation of the state is computed. Usually for Long and Downstream tracks a cubic approach is used, but for the specific case of the T tracks, it has been understood the essential need for a fifth order Runge-Kutta (RK) method. In the RK formalism, the state is expressed by Eq. 3.1. When the track is extrapolated for a distance Δz , the new track state is obtained with a fifth-order RK expansion:

$$\mathbf{x}(\Delta z) = \mathbf{x}_0 + \sum_{m=1}^6 c_m \frac{d^m \mathbf{x}}{dz^m} \Delta z, \quad (3.11)$$

with

$$\mathbf{x}^m = \sum_{n=1}^{m-1} b_{mn} \frac{d^n \mathbf{x}}{dz^n} \Delta z, \quad (3.12)$$

where the parameters b_{mn} and c_m are chosen to reach a precision of $(\Delta z)^6$. This method is more suitable for the extrapolation of T tracks in the high- \mathcal{B} region with respect to the commonly used parabolic technique.

From Fig. 3.1 it is evident that the vertex reconstruction constitutes the bottleneck of the reconstruction and selection procedure, with an efficiency lower than 50%. In particular it has been studied separating the reconstruction of the Λ and Λ_b^0 , finding as a result that the responsible for the inefficiency is the first one. This result is due to

Figure 3.2: Standard vertexing algorithms workflow: VF for vertex position followed by DTF for refitted momenta.

the combination of two factors: firstly the limited number of tracking stations available to reconstruct the T tracks. Secondly, the fact that the magnetic field in that region is low, ending in a very poor momentum resolution. This effect has been tested using the simulation and using the true momenta with a very precise covariance matrix, mainly a 1% resolution on momenta and $100 \mu\text{m}$ on the z position. In this case, the efficiency integrated over the z vertex component equals about 94%. This result demonstrates the importance of a good momentum resolution in the vertexing algorithm convergence and motivates the effort in its improvement.

After the VF, a second vertexing algorithm is applied, which fit the complete decay chain simultaneously, referred to as Decay Tree Fitter (DTF) [102]. The vertexing procedure is schematically pictured in Fig. 3.2. This second algorithm has the advantage of giving as output refitted values of the momenta computed at the fitted vertex position and has the possibility to constrain the values of the intermediate particles masses and the primary vertex (PV) position, which is the reconstructed position of the initial interaction point between the two protons. In addition, fitting the full decay chain allows the constraints upstream of a vertex to contribute to the parameters of the vertex itself, which is not possible with the bottom-up approach of the VF. The decay is parametrized by the momenta, decay time and vertex position, represented collectively by \mathbf{x} . It consists in a least square fit, where the parameters of interest are extracted through a Kalman filter. The constraints are formulated as χ^2 contributions as a function of \mathbf{x} . We can distinguish between internal constrains, which are exact, and measured constraints, which have an associated uncertainty. An example of the former is the momentum of a mother particle that can be replaced by the sum of the momenta of its daughters particles. This kind of constraints could be applied simply by substitution, but it is not optimal for the use of recurrency in the algorithm, so they are applied as Lagrange multipliers. The exact constraints are expressed as a function of \mathbf{x} as $g_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}) = 0$, therefore the χ^2 contribution is expressed by

$$\chi_{\mathbf{k}}^2 = 2\lambda_{\mathbf{k}}^T g_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (3.13)$$

with $\lambda_{\mathbf{k}}$ the Lagrange multiplier. For a measurement constraint the χ^2 contribution is

$$\chi_{\mathbf{k}}^2 = \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}}^T(\mathbf{x}) V_{\mathbf{k}}^{-1} \mathbf{r}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (3.14)$$

where $\mathbf{r}_k(\mathbf{x})$ is the constraint residual, defined as $\mathbf{r}_k(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{m}_k - \mathbf{h}_k(\mathbf{x})$, where \mathbf{m}_k is the value of the measured quantity (for example the parameters from a reconstructed track) and $\mathbf{h}_k(\mathbf{x})$ is the measurement model that expresses this quantity in terms of the parameters \mathbf{x} . With this definition, V_i is the covariance matrix of the measurement \mathbf{m}_k .

In our case, the constraints require the b -hadron candidate to originate at the PV, the J/ψ and $\Lambda(K_S^0)$ masses to be equal to their known values [16], and the $\Lambda(K_S^0)$ momentum aligned with its flight direction, defined by the J/ψ and $\Lambda(K_S^0)$ decay vertices.

By construction, the algorithm fixes the flight directions of the particles and it has been checked that this brings the highest improvement in the momentum resolution. On the other hand, refitting the vertices introduces another efficiency loss, equal to about 50% at $\Lambda z_{\text{vtx}} \approx 6$ m and up to about 85% at $\Lambda z_{\text{vtx}} \approx 7.5$ m. This inefficiency is compensated by the gain in the momentum resolution of the refitted momenta, passing from a resolution of 20–30% to $\approx 5\%$, as will be shown later. A similar behavior is observed in the case of the B^0 decay.

3.1.2 Selection

The selection strategy is based on an initial loose selection (preselection) to reduce the amount of data and remove a part of the background. It is followed by an invariant mass veto requirement application to suppress the B^0 physics background, by a Boosted Decision Tree (BDT), and finally the Armenteros-Podolanski (AP) requirements. We first present the selection on the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays and then a similar procedure is applied to $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays.

The $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ signal decay

In the first step, to remove background, the cuts applied are reported in Table 3.1 and are based on the following variables: the momentum p of the proton and the pion, the transverse momentum p_T of the proton and Λ candidates; the invariant masses of the $\mu^+ \mu^-$, $p\pi^-$ and $J/\psi \Lambda$ systems; the z coordinate of the Λ candidate decay vertex, z_{vtx} ; the cosine of the angle between the proton and the Λ momenta $\xi_p(\Lambda)$, and between the proton and the Λ_b^0 momenta $\xi_p(\Lambda_b^0)$; the χ_{IP}^2 and χ_{vtx}^2 of the Λ and Λ_b^0 candidates, where χ_{IP}^2 is the difference in the vertex-fit χ^2 of the PV candidate reconstructed with and without the particle considered and χ_{vtx}^2 is the decay vertex-fit χ^2 . The efficiency of these cuts is about 90% reported in Fig. 3.1, independently from the Λ decay position.

The main physical background for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ with $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ decays are $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ with $K_S^0 \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^-$ decays, where a pion is present instead of the proton in the final state and no Particle Identification (PID) information is available for T tracks in Run 1 and Run 2 data (at the time of this analysis). In Fig. 3.3 (left), we compare the invariant mass distribution of K_S^0 candidates from simulated $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays with that of Λ candidates from Λ_b^0 decays, focusing on the final state proton. The poor mass resolution makes these two distributions almost completely overlapping, hence a veto based on this variable is ineffective. However, Fig. 3.3 (right) demonstrates that the invariant mass of $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ effectively discriminates between the two b -hadron decays. Consequently, a veto is applied to candidates with $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ within ± 70 MeV/ c^2 of the known B^0 mass [16]. This retains 87% of the Λ_b^0 signal while rejecting 65% of the B^0 decays. The possibility of adding the PID information from the RICH2, calorimeter, and muon systems to further refine signal selection and enhance background rejection has been explored after this performance study and will be discussed in Chapter 4.

Table 3.1: Loose selection requirements applied to $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ candidates passing the online event selection. The invariant masses $m(p\pi^-)$ and $m(J/\psi \Lambda)$ are obtained from the VF.

Variable	Units	Minimum	Maximum
$p(\pi^-)$	MeV/c	2 000	500 000
$p(p)$	MeV/c	10 000	500 000
$p_T(p)$	MeV/c	400	–
$m(p\pi^-)$	MeV/c ²	600	1 500
z_{vtx}^A	m	5.5	8.5
$\cos \xi_p(\Lambda)$		0.9999	–
$\chi_{\text{IP}}^2(\Lambda)$		–	200
$\chi_{\text{vtx}}^2(\Lambda)$		–	750
$ m(\mu^+\mu^-) - m(J/\psi) $	MeV/c ²	–	90
$p_T(\Lambda)$	MeV/c	450	–
$m(J/\psi \Lambda)$	MeV/c ²	4 700	8 500
$\cos \xi_p(\Lambda_b^0)$		0.99	–
$\chi_{\text{IP}}^2(\Lambda_b^0)$		–	1 750
$\chi_{\text{vtx}}^2(\Lambda_b^0)$		–	150

The contribution of the combinatorial background is still dominant after the preselection, exceeding the signal by a factor 10^3 . To suppress it, a multivariate classifier is employed, in particular a histogram-based boosted decision tree (HBDT) algorithm has been selected, taken from the Scikit-learn 0.24.02 package for Python 3.6.8 [103]. To train the HBDT classifier, a sample of 43000 simulated signal decays is used, selected within ± 600 MeV/c² window from the PDG Λ_b^0 mass value [16]. For the background sample, about 6×10^6 events are taken from the lower and upper sidebands of the $m(J/\psi \Lambda)$ distribution in data, chosen as 150 and 300 MeV/c² wide windows below and above the signal region, respectively. The datasets are divided in 90% for training and 10% for testing the performance. The variables which show the largest impact in the discrimination are the following: the longitudinal and transverse momenta of the proton, pion and J/ψ candidates at the first measurement point; the coordinates of the Λ decay vertex given by the VF, $(x_{\text{vtx}}^A, y_{\text{vtx}}^A, z_{\text{vtx}}^A)$; the cosine of the Λ (Λ_b^0) direction angle between its momentum and the flight direction defined by the Λ (Λ_b^0) and J/ψ decay vertices; the χ_{vtx}^2 , χ_{IP}^2 and χ_{dist}^2 of the Λ and Λ_b^0 candidates, where χ_{dist}^2 is the squared distance between the PV and the particle decay vertex normalised to its uncertainty; and the status flags (converged/failed) of the DTF with only the J/ψ mass constraint, and also adding the Λ mass constraint. The Λ decay position plays an important role in the HBDT for the rejection of background due to material interactions. An optimization of the hyperparameters of the algorithm is performed, involving the maximum number of leaf nodes for the decision trees; the learning rate, *i.e.* the weight applied to each successive decision tree of the boosting procedure; and the total number of iterations, namely the number of decision trees in the ensemble. The figure of merit optimized is the Area-Under-Curve (AUC), which corresponds to the area of the signal purity versus the signal efficiency, varying continuously the thresholds applied on the HBDT from 0 to 1. The operating point is determined by applying a threshold to the HBDT response, chosen by optimizing the figure-of-merit ratio

$$\text{Significance} = \frac{S}{\sqrt{S+B}}, \quad (3.15)$$

Figure 3.3: (Left) invariant mass distribution $m(\pi^+\pi^-)$ of K_S^0 candidates from simulated $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays (orange points) compared with the mass distribution of Λ candidates from $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays, where the proton in the final state is assigned the pion-mass hypothesis (blue points). (Right) invariant mass distribution $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ from simulated $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays (orange points) compared with the corresponding distribution from $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ simulation, where the proton in the final state has assigned the pion-mass hypothesis and the intermediate Λ has assigned the K_S^0 -mass hypothesis (blue points).

where S and B represent the signal and background yields in the signal region, respectively. To achieve this, the figure-of-merit is calculated for each HBDT threshold by performing a binned fit to the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ invariant mass distribution in data. For the optimal threshold, a signal efficiency of 72% is obtained and a significance of 54. Training the classifier with signal and background samples of similar size causes a shift in the optimal threshold without affecting the figure-of-merit.

To address the lack of PID information and further remove the physics background, in addition to applying the veto, an AP cut has been also applied. Considering a two body decay of a mother particle M into two final state particles of masses m_1 and m_2 , the AP plot represents the transverse momentum versus the asymmetry of the longitudinal momenta of the final-state particles with respect to the parent flight direction,

$$\alpha = \frac{p_L^{(1)} - p_L^{(2)}}{p_L^{(1)} + p_L^{(2)}}. \quad (3.16)$$

Substituting the momenta with their expression in terms of the center-of-mass frame of the decay, and introducing the angle θ between the momenta of particle 1 in the center-of-mass frame, with modulus p^* and the Lorentz β , we obtain

$$\alpha = \frac{m_1^2 - m_2^2}{M^2} + \frac{2p^*}{\beta M} \cos \theta \equiv \alpha_0 + \frac{r_\alpha}{\beta} \cos \theta, \quad (3.17)$$

with

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{m_1^2 - m_2^2}{M^2} \quad (3.18)$$

and

$$r_\alpha = \frac{2p^*}{M}. \quad (3.19)$$

Figure 3.4: The AP plot for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ candidates passing the loose, HBDT and B^0 veto selection criteria, for (left) simulated $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ signal events and (right) Run 2 data. The symbol p_L^+ (p_L^-) refers to the longitudinal momentum of the positively (negatively) charged final-state particle, i.e. the p and π^+ (π^- and \bar{p}) in the Λ and $\bar{\Lambda}$ decay, respectively, and p_T their transverse momentum, calculated with respect to the hyperon flight direction.

We can further elaborate through the Pythagorean trigonometric identity $\cos^2 \theta + \sin^2 \theta = 1$, yielding

$$\frac{(\alpha - \alpha_0)^2}{r_\alpha^2} + \frac{p_T^2}{p^{*2}} = 1. \quad (3.20)$$

This demonstrates that the momenta of daughter particles from a two-body decay define an ellipse in the $\alpha - p_T$ Armenteros-Podolanski space, with radii and center depending on the particle masses. The expected shapes are observed in Fig. 3.4 (left), where the true momenta from the simulation have been employed. Here, α is typically calculated by assigning the positive particle to m_1 , which corresponds to p in Λ decays and π^+ in $\bar{\Lambda}$ and K_S^0 decays, leading to two symmetric ellipses for $\Lambda_b \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ events. Although a selection based on the K_S^0 and Λ ellipses might seem straightforward, the momentum resolution affects the plot and must be considered. Figure 3.4 (right) shows the Armenteros-Podolanski space for the same events, constructed with the DTF algorithm using the J/ψ mass constraint. The substantial overlap of the two event classes prevents selection criteria based solely on the p_T axis but allows for an α criterion that minimizes false positives.

Given the symmetric nature of the Armenteros-Podolanski space, the veto was implemented as

$$|\alpha| \geq \alpha_{\text{thres}}, \quad (3.21)$$

where α_{thres} was optimized to maximize the significance of the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda^0$ signal, $\alpha_{\text{thres}} = 0.5$. The efficiency of the AP requirement for signal decays is reported in Fig. 3.1 and amounts to 99%, largely independent on the Λ decay vertex position.

After the outlined selection, the invariant mass distributions $m(p\pi^-)$ and $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ found are reported in Figs. 3.5 and 3.6, comparing the results in simulation and data. For their computation, the momenta from the DTF are employed, in the case of the $J/\psi\Lambda$ both the constraints on Λ and J/ψ are applied, while the $p\pi^-$ invariant mass is computed only with the J/ψ one. The signal and background yields, as well as the invariant mass resolution, are determined by independently fitting these distributions. The $m(p\pi^-)$ and

Figure 3.5: invariant mass distribution (left) $m(p\pi^-)$ and (right) $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ for simulated $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ signal decays. The black points with error bars represent the simulation, and the overlaid (blue) curves are the results of the mass fits.

$m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ signals are effectively modelled using asymmetric and symmetric double-tail Crystal Ball functions [104], respectively, with the tail parameters fixed in the data based on values obtained from simulation. In the $m(p\pi^-)$ distribution, the background, which is predominantly from K_S^0 decays, is parameterized using a template derived from simulated $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays. Conversely, the background in the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ distribution, primarily consisting of random combinations of J/ψ and Λ candidates and a minor contribution from $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays, is described using an exponential function.

The simulated sample yields approximately 31 000 signal decays, leading to an invariant mass resolution of 16.4 ± 0.2 and 68.0 ± 0.5 MeV/c^2 for $m(p\pi^-)$ and $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$, respectively. In this and subsequent results, resolutions are defined as the central 68.3% confidence level region of the underlying distribution, with statistical uncertainties based on the fourth moment of the distribution [105].¹ The data fits yield approximately 43 500 $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and 6 140 $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ signal events, with mass resolutions of 17.8 ± 0.3 and 74.4 ± 0.6 MeV/c^2 , respectively, which are about 10% worse than those obtained in simulation. These resolutions are determined after subtracting the statistical background using the *sPlot* technique [106], with $m(p\pi^-)$ and $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ as the discriminant variables. The K_S^0 background is estimated to include around 15 000 candidates within the full $m(p\pi^-)$ range shown in Fig. 3.6 (left), while the background yield in the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ distribution, evaluated in a region defined by three times the invariant mass resolution around the mean mass, amounts to 10 800.

The $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ control sample

The loose selection applied is very similar to that already presented for the signal channel, outlined in Table 3.2. In this case, the physical background is represented by the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decay, therefore a veto is applied to reject candidates with $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ in the range ± 150 MeV/c^2 around the known Λ_b^0 mass [16], where the positive pion from the K_S^0 candidate is reconstructed using the proton mass hypothesis for the π^- candidate. The resulting selection efficiency is 96% for the B^0 decays, while it amounts to 37% for the Λ_b^0 background. It is followed by the training of an HBDT classifier using about

¹Refer to Eq. 6h.3.1 in the cited reference.

Figure 3.6: invariant mass distribution (left) $m(p\pi^-)$ and (right) $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ candidates reconstructed using Run 2 data after all selection criteria. The results of the mass fits are superimposed (blue curves) along with the background contribution (dotted orange curves).

Figure 3.7: The AP plot for $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ candidates after the loose, HBDT and Λ_b^0 veto selection criteria, for (left) simulated $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ signal and (right) Run 2 data.

22 000 simulated B^0 signal decays for the signal sample and about 6×10^6 background candidates selected in data from the lower and upper sidebands of the $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ distribution. The same figure-of-merit is optimized, finding the optimal point at 89, with a signal efficiency of 91%. The last step is again a requirement on the longitudinal momentum asymmetry in the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ AP plot, shown in Fig. 3.7 for simulation and data to be within the range $[-0.5, 0.5]$. The $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ background rejection yields to 99%, while 66% of the B^0 decays are retained.

In Fig. 3.8 the $m(\pi^+\pi^-)$ and $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ distributions are displayed for the reconstructed and selected $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ candidates from simulation, with a yield of about 13 000 candidates, along with the corresponding mass fits. In comparison, Figure 3.9 shows the equivalent distributions for B^0 candidates reconstructed from data after applying selection criteria.

An asymmetric double-tail Crystal Ball function [104] is used to model the signal, while the combinatorial background contributions to the $m(\pi^+\pi^-)$ and $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ dis-

Table 3.2: Loose selection requirements applied to $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ candidates passing the online event selection. The invariant masses $m(\pi^+\pi^-)$ and $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ are obtained from the VF.

Variable	Units	Minimum	Maximum
$p(\pi^+, \pi^-)$	MeV/c	2 500	500 000
$m(\pi^+\pi^-)$	MeV/c ²	100	1 300
$z_{\text{vtx}}^{K_S^0}$	m	5.0	9.5
$\cos \xi_p(K_S^0)$		0.9995	–
$\chi_{\text{IP}}^2(K_S^0)$		–	200
$\chi_{\text{vtx}}^2(K_S^0)$		–	100
$ m(\mu^+\mu^-) - m(J/\psi) $	MeV/c ²	–	90
$p_T(K_S^0)$	MeV/c	600	–
$p(J/\psi)$	MeV/c	18 000	–
$p_T(J/\psi)$	MeV/c	250	–
$m(J/\psi K_S^0)$	MeV/c ²	4 700	6 500
$\cos \xi_p(B^0)$		0.995	–
$\chi_{\text{IP}}^2(B^0)$		–	60
$\chi_{\text{vtx}}^2(B^0)$		–	35

tributions are described with an exponential function. In the data, a total of 120 000 K_S^0 and 13 300 $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ signal candidates are reconstructed, yielding mass resolutions of $51.0 \pm 0.3 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ and $47.1 \pm 0.5 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, respectively. These values can be compared to the resolutions obtained from the simulation, which are $51.0 \pm 0.5 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ and $48.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ MeV}/c^2$. The background yield within the $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ region, defined as three times the invariant mass resolution, is approximately 13 200.

The overall reconstruction and selection efficiency varies from around 10% for K_S^0 decays occurring 6.0 meters from the nominal IP to approximately 16% for decays closer to the T stations, as shown in Fig.3.10. The total efficiency is lower with respect to Λ_b^0 decay, mainly due to the reduced efficiency of the AP veto. It is also visible that the tracking and vertexing efficiencies closely match those observed for the Λ_b^0 case (see Fig. 3.1), while the decay chain vertex fit demonstrates slightly better performance. Although the loose selection efficiency is lower, this is compensated by the higher efficiency of the HBDT selection.

3.2 T track reconstruction performance

After having selected the signal candidates, the aim was to study the reconstruction of T tracks and their momentum and vertex position resolutions, which are the ingredients to define the helicity angles, from which the electromagnetic dipole moments will be extracted. It is fundamental to compare the resolution we get from the simulation directly to what we obtain on data, for this reason we have developed novel data-driven techniques for their evaluation.

3.2.1 Momentum resolution

The momentum resolution of T tracks is worse with respect to Long tracks due to their relatively low curvature, as they are reconstructed only using hits from a region characterized by a weak magnetic field and a relatively short lever arm. To evaluate directly

Figure 3.8: invariant mass distribution (left) $m(\pi^+\pi^-)$ and (right) $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ for simulated $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ signal decays. The mass fit results are overlaid.

Figure 3.9: invariant mass distribution (left) $m(\pi^+\pi^-)$ and (right) $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ for $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ candidates using Run 2 data after all selection criteria. The mass fit results are overlaid.

on data the resolution, we followed a similar approach as utilized in the evaluation for Long tracks with muons coming from inclusive J/ψ decays in LHCb, shown in Fig. 2.8 [80]. In that case, some assumptions are made on the muon final state particles: their masses have been neglected and only muons with the same momenta have been considered. What we developed is a more general approach, to study decays with different final state particles and momenta. We started considering a particle decaying into two daughter particles with masses m_1 and m_2 and four-momenta (E_1, \mathbf{p}_1) and (E_2, \mathbf{p}_2) . The invariant mass of the mother particle follows as

$$m^2 = m_1^2 + m_2^2 + 2(E_1 E_2 - p_1 p_2 \cos \theta_{12}), \quad (3.22)$$

where θ_{12} is the angle between \mathbf{p}_1 and \mathbf{p}_2 , p_1 and p_2 are their magnitudes, and $E_1 = \sqrt{p_1^2 + m_1^2}$ and $E_2 = \sqrt{p_2^2 + m_2^2}$ the energies. Propagating the error on Eq. 3.22 and ap-

Figure 3.10: Reconstruction and selection efficiency as a function of the true K_S^0 decay vertex position along the beam axis for simulated $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ signal decays (grey) and its breakdown for different reconstruction and selection steps: the reconstruction and quality selections of the four tracks of the final state (blue); the reconstruction of the K_S^0 and B^0 decay vertices (orange); the initial selection applied to the final-state and decaying particles as described in Table 3.2 (green); the fraction of successful decay chain vertex fits (DTF, red); the Λ_b^0 mass veto (violet); the selection efficiency of the HBDT (maroon); and the AP veto (pink).

proximating $\sin \theta_{12} \approx \theta_{12}$ lead to

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_p}{p}\right)^2 = g_m \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{m}\right)^2 - g_\theta \left(\frac{\sigma_{\theta_{12}}}{\theta_{12}}\right)^2, \quad (3.23)$$

where $p_2 = p$ and

$$\begin{aligned} g_m &= g \left(\frac{m}{p}\right)^4, \\ g_\theta &= g \xi^2 \theta_{12}^4, \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

and

$$\frac{1}{g} = \xi^2 \left(\frac{\xi_E}{\xi} - \cos \theta_{12}\right)^2 + \xi^2 f^2(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2) \left(\frac{\xi}{\xi_E} - \cos \theta_{12}\right)^2. \quad (3.25)$$

Here, we have introduced the kinematic ratios $\xi = p_1/p_2$ and $\xi_E = E_1/E_2$, and the ratio of relative momentum uncertainties

$$f(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2) = \frac{1}{\xi} \frac{\sigma_p(\xi p, \eta_1)}{\sigma_p(p, \eta_2)}, \quad (3.26)$$

where $\sigma_p(p, \eta)/p$ stands for the relative momentum uncertainty of the daughter particle 1 (2) evaluated as a function of its momentum $p_1 = \xi p$ ($p_2 = p$) and pseudorapidity η_1 (η_2).

The mass and angular factors, g_m and g_θ respectively, take into account the kinematic dependence when propagating the relative mass and angle uncertainties to the relative momentum uncertainty. This is the most general case, which can be reconnected to the result in [80] considering the relativistic limit where $E_1 \approx p_1$ and $E_2 \approx p$, and the small angle approximation, $1 - \cos \theta_{12} \approx \theta_{12}^2/2$. In this limit, Eq. 3.23 holds whereas 3.24 and 3.25 reduce to

$$\begin{aligned} g_m &\approx \frac{4}{1 + f^2(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2)} \frac{1}{\xi^2 \theta_{12}^4} \left(\frac{m}{p}\right)^4, \\ g_\theta &\approx \frac{4}{1 + f^2(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2)}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.27)$$

Further assuming $m \gg m_1, m_2$, which is the case for $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$, it follows that

$$g_m \approx g_\theta \approx \frac{4}{1 + f^2(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2)}, \quad (3.28)$$

since in this case $m^2 \approx \xi p^2 \theta_{12}^2$. For $m_1 \approx m_2$ and assuming candidates satisfying $\xi \approx 1$ and $\eta_1 \approx \eta_2$, leads to $f(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2) \approx 1$ and $g_m \approx g_\theta \approx 2$. Equation (3.23) can then be written as

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_p}{p}\right)^2 \approx 2 \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{m}\right)^2 - 2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{\theta_{12}}}{\theta_{12}}\right)^2, \quad (3.29)$$

in agreement with Eq. 1 of Ref. [80],² where this approximate expression has been been applied to $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ decays to measure the momentum resolution of Long tracks. The approximate Eqs. 3.27 to 3.29 do not hold in either of the cases of this analysis. Thus we exploit Eqs. 3.23 to 3.25 to measure the relative track momentum resolution in bins of momentum for T tracks from $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $K_S^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays. After applying all selection criteria, signal candidates in data are binned according to the reconstructed momentum of the proton and the two pions, for $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $K_S^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays, respectively. The *sPlot* technique [106] with $m(p\pi^-)$ and $m(\pi^+\pi^-)$ as the discriminating variable is adopted to statistically subtract the background contribution. In order to assess its validity, the procedure is also applied to simulation, in addition to the evaluation of the resolution from the distributions of differences between reconstructed and true quantities (residuals). In the following, we identify particle 2 with the positively charged decay product, *i.e.* the proton (π^+) for Λ (K_S^0) decays. In each momentum bin, the mass resolution σ_m is determined from the 68.3% confidence level (CL) region of the $m(p\pi^-)$ and $m(\pi^+\pi^-)$ invariant mass distributions. The world-average masses for Λ and K_S^0 [16] are used for m . By substituting these values with the mean or most probable values of the distributions has a negligible effect on the resolution.

The angular resolution is determined from the distribution of per-event differences between the angle θ_{12} reconstructed using the VF and DTF, since the resolution for the former is about a factor of four worse. We checked on simulation that computing the residual distribution subtracting from the angle reconstructed with the VF the one reconstructed with true information or with the DTF does not introduce any difference. Figure 3.11 shows this distribution for Λ and K_S^0 decays, respectively, as obtained from simulation and data signal candidates passing all selection criteria, compared to the distribution of residuals in simulation, *i.e.* replacing the reconstructed angle with the DTF

²There is a misprint in the factor p/mc of the angular term, which should not be present.

Figure 3.11: Distributions of the event-by-event differences between the cosine of the proton-pion opening angle at the vertex position reconstructed using the VF and DTF, for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ (left) and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ (right) signal candidates in simulation (orange histogram) and data (black points). For simulation, the residual distribution using the VF is overlaid (blue histogram).

by its true value, integrated over momenta. The average resolution on the cosine of the angle between the $p\pi$ particles is 0.003 and 0.004, for simulation and data, respectively. The resolution on the cosine of the opening angle between the two pions coming from the K_S^0 reaches in simulation 0.002 with the VF, and about a factor of five smaller with the DTF. The former in data is about 40% larger. Compared to Λ decays, K_S^0 decays show a better angular resolution due to the larger opening angle of its decay products, which is itself a consequence of the larger Q value of the decay, determined by the mass difference between the initial and final-state particles.

Regarding the kinematic factor ξ , along with ξ_E , they can be computed directly on an event-by-event basis. Its average value, $\langle \xi \rangle$, is approximately 6 for Λ decays, varying from around 4.7 to 6.8 as the momentum bin increases. In contrast, for K_S^0 decays, it remains close to unity with minimal variation across the bins, consistent in both simulation and data. These approximate averages can also be calculated analytically, given the momentum of particle 1 along the (longitudinal) direction of the decaying particle's motion,

$$p_{1,L}(\cos \theta^*) = \gamma p^* \left(\cos \theta^* + \beta \sqrt{1 + \frac{m_1^2}{p^{*2}}} \right), \quad (3.30)$$

where p^* and θ^* are the momentum and angle of particle 1 (and 2) in the centre-of-mass frame of the decaying particle, and $\beta\gamma \gg 1$ its Lorentz boost. It can be computed analogously for particle 2, reversing the sign of $\cos \theta^*$ and replacing m_1 by m_2 . The average value is obtained integrating over $\cos \theta^*$,

$$\langle \xi \rangle \approx \frac{\int p_{1,L}^*(\cos \theta^*) \Gamma(\cos \theta^*) d \cos \theta^*}{\int p_{2,L}^*(\cos \theta^*) \Gamma(\cos \theta^*) d \cos \theta^*}, \quad (3.31)$$

where $\Gamma(\cos \theta^*)$ represents the angular distribution of the $m \rightarrow m_1 m_2$ decay. For $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ decays, since $\Gamma(\cos \theta^*) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \alpha \cos \theta^*)$ with $\alpha \approx 0.75$ [16], we get $\langle \xi \rangle \approx 6.5$. For $K_S^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays, with $\Gamma(\cos \theta^*) = 1/2$ and $m_1 = m_2$, one finds $\langle \xi \rangle \approx 1$.

Figure 3.12: (Left) Relative momentum resolution for protons and pions from Λ and K_S^0 decays (left) in bins of momentum and pseudorapidity, evaluated with residual distributions (68.3% CL region) from simulated signal events passing all selection criteria, and (right) after spline interpolation. The statistical uncertainties are stable across the bins and amount to about 0.003.

The $f(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2)$ factor is estimated from the ratio of relative momentum uncertainties of the two daughter particles evaluated at $(\xi p, \eta_1)$ and (p, η_2) , following Eq. 3.26. The dependence of the relative momentum uncertainty is itself obtained from simulation, binning in momentum and pseudorapidity. Since the relative momentum resolution does not depend on the particle mass, protons and pions from both Λ and K_S^0 decays are combined. The two-dimensional binning along with the 68.3% CL region of the residual distribution in each bin are illustrated in Fig. 3.12 (left).

The factor $f(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2)$ is calculated as the ratio of the relative momentum uncertainties of the two daughter particles, evaluated at $(\xi p, \eta_1)$ and (p, η_2) , as described in Eq. 3.26. The dependence of the relative momentum uncertainty is derived from simulation, using binning in both momentum and pseudorapidity. Since the relative momentum resolution is independent of the particle mass, protons and pions from Λ and K_S^0 decays are added together. The two-dimensional binning, along with the 68.3% CL region of the residual distribution within each bin, is illustrated in Fig.3.12 (left). Based on this plot, an spline interpolator is used and an extrapolation is then produced in Fig.3.12 (right). For $K_S^0 \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^-$ decays, where the two pions are selected in the same momentum bin, *i.e.* $\xi \approx 1$, it follows $f(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2) \approx 1$ when $\eta_1 \approx \eta_2$.

The relative resolution σ_p/p can then be evaluated on an event-by-event basis using the per-bin mass and angular resolutions, the angle θ_{12} , the momentum p , the kinematic factors ξ and ξ_E , the pseudorapidities η_1 and η_2 , and the $f(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2)$ ratio evaluated using Eq. 3.26 and Fig. 3.12 (right). Figure 3.13 (left) illustrates the σ_p/p distributions for the central bins [see Figs. 3.14 and 3.15 (left)]. The wider shape and positive tail of the distribution for Λ decays reflects the larger event-by-event variation of its kinematics with respect to K_S^0 decays. An average relative momentum resolution per bin is evaluated using the most probable value of the distribution, with uncertainty determined from the central 68.3% CL region divided by the square root of the bin yields, added in quadrature to the half difference between the most probable value and the mean of the distribution. The addition of this second term aims to take into account a systematic effect due to the not Gaussian distribution and the long tails of the Λ , visible in Fig. 3.13. The broader and more asymmetric distribution for Λ decays result in larger uncertainties as compared to K_S^0 decays. Other sources of uncertainty originated by the propagation of uncertainties

Figure 3.13: Distributions of the relative momentum resolution for T tracks from $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $K_S^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays for the central momentum bin, (left) from track reconstruction and (right) after decay chain fitting.

on σ_m and $\sigma_{\theta_{12}}$, estimated through the method of moments [105], and the $f(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2)$ statistical uncertainties, are also taken into account and found to be subdominant. The final results of the procedure are shown in Figs. 3.14 and 3.15 (left).

Figure 3.14: Relative momentum resolution as a function of momentum for protons (left) and pions (right) reconstructed as final state of the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ (left) and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ (right) decays, obtained with the VF. The resolution obtained from residuals in simulation (blue triangles) is compared to that obtained from the data procedure applied to both simulation (orange squares) and data (black points).

The method can be expanded to consider a decay chain with subsequent decays like $m \rightarrow m_3 m_4, m_4 \rightarrow m_1 m_2$. In this case the mother particle invariant mass is

$$m^2 = m_3^2 + m_4^2 + 2E_3(E_1 + E_2) - 2p_3\sqrt{(E_1 + E_2)^2 - m_4^2} \cos\theta_{34}, \quad (3.32)$$

where p_3 and $E_3 = \sqrt{p_3^2 + m_3^2}$ are the momentum and energy of particle 3, and θ_{34} is the angle between the three-momenta of particles 3 and 4. Assuming that m_4 is kinematically (mass) constrained, which means that its value is well defined without any

Figure 3.15: Relative momentum resolution as a function of momentum for protons (left) and pions (right) reconstructed as final state of the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ (left) and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ (right) decays, obtained with the full decay chain fitter (DTF). The resolution from residuals in simulation (blue triangles) is compared to that obtained from the data procedure applied to both simulation (orange squares) and data (black points).

associated uncertainty, the error propagation gives

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_p}{p}\right)^2 = g_m \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{m}\right)^2 - g_\theta \left(\frac{\sigma_{\theta_{34}}}{\theta_{34}}\right)^2 - g_{p_3} \left(\frac{\sigma_{p_3}}{p_3}\right)^2. \quad (3.33)$$

The kinematic dependence can be found in the following factors

$$\begin{aligned} g_m &= g \left(\frac{m}{p}\right)^4, \\ g_\theta &= g \left(\frac{p_4}{p}\right)^4 \kappa^2 \theta_{34}^4, \\ g_{p_3} &= g \left(\frac{p_4}{p}\right)^4 \kappa^2 \left(\frac{\kappa}{\kappa_E} - \cos \theta_{34}\right)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (3.34)$$

with

$$\frac{1}{g} = \kappa^2 \left(\frac{\kappa_E}{\kappa} - \cos \theta_{34}\right)^2 (1 + \xi_E)^2 \left[1 + \frac{\xi^4}{\xi_E^2} f^2(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2)\right], \quad (3.35)$$

where κ and κ_E are the corresponding kinematic factors for particles 3 and 4, *i.e.* $\kappa = p_3/p_4$, $\kappa_E = E_3/E_4$, with p_4 and $E_4 = \sqrt{p_4^2 + m_4^2}$ being the momentum and energy of particle 4.

In the relativistic limit, $E_i \approx p_i$ with $i = 1$ to 4, and small angle approximation, $1 - \cos \theta_{34} \approx \theta_{34}^2/2$, the factors g_{p_3} and g simplify to

$$g_{p_3} \approx \frac{g}{4} \left(\frac{p_4}{p}\right)^4 \kappa^2 \theta_{34}^4, \quad (3.36)$$

and

$$\frac{1}{g} = \frac{1}{4} \kappa^2 \theta_{34}^4 (1 + \xi)^2 \left[1 + \xi^2 f^2(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2)\right]. \quad (3.37)$$

Equations 3.33 to 3.35 can be used to measure the relative track momentum resolution for T tracks from $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $K_S^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays when the whole decay chains $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda(\rightarrow p\pi^-)$ and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0(\rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-)$ are reconstructed and fitted simultaneously with geometric and kinematic constraints. The method is similar to the previous one, with four main differences. First, the resolution of θ_{34} (the angle between the J/ψ and the Λ or K_S^0 hadrons) is determined by subtracting the true and reconstructed angles in the simulation. This resolution is then applied in the analysis with both simulation and data. Unlike the previous case, this angular resolution is significantly less dominant compared to the mass contribution. The second point observed on simulation is that the relative momentum uncertainty is largely independent of momentum and pseudorapidity, due to the constraints applied to the decay chains, resulting in a ratio $f(p, \xi, \eta_1, \eta_2) \approx 1$. Third, the last term in Eq. 3.33 is negligible since the J/ψ momentum resolution, σ_{p_3}/p_3 , is about 0.5% [80], an order of magnitude smaller than the first two terms. Lastly, the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ and $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ invariant masses are fitted as discriminating variables to statistically subtract the background contribution in the data. The average relative momentum resolution per bin along with its uncertainty are shown in Fig. 3.15 for both the decays. Figure 3.13 (right) illustrates the σ_p/p distributions for the central momentum bin. Comparing with Fig. 3.13 (left), there is almost a factor 10 improvement. The distributions of the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ chain are more spread due to the kinematic of the decay. Another important different feature visible in the (left) plot is that the Λ distribution is more asymmetric with respect to the K_S^0 , which ends up in larger error bars in Fig. 3.14.

3.2.2 Decay vertex resolution

The momentum resolution not only impacts the efficiency of the vertexing algorithm, but also the resolution of the fitted vertex. Specifically for the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decay, inward-bending track pairs can result in **Ghost** vertex events, where the wrong z -position of the decay vertex is reconstructed. These events degrade the resolution of the z component of the vertex position. These events, sketched in Fig. 3.16 (left), exhibit particle trajectories with two (consistent within track uncertainties) crossing points, inducing the VF to converge frequently to the wrong vertex (denoted in the following as **Ghost**). In contrast, opening-track decays, shown in Fig. 3.16 (right), do not have a ghost vertex and converge to the correct position (denoted **Good**). Figure 3.17 shows the impact of these events on the vertex resolution illustrating the residual distributions of the reconstructed Λ vertex z position, z_{vtx} , for **Good** and **Ghost** signal events from simulation. To obtain these plots, the true track from the simulated events are propagated through the detector volume and then the z positions of closest approach between the two tracks in the xz plane are searched for. When there exists a unique minimum, or with two minima and the reconstructed z position closer to the true decay vertex, the event is tagged as **Good**, and **Ghost** otherwise. **Ghost** events amount to about 30% of the reconstructed $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays, showing a broad residual distribution, strongly biased towards larger z positions. Note that **Ghost** events biased towards low z positions can also occur, but their contribution is largely suppressed, as can be observed in Fig. 3.17. Comparing the effect on both the decays, it is evident that for $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ it is not a significant effect, with a **Ghost** contribution of less than 6% comprising backward and upwards events, therefore for the vertexing studies we will focus mainly on the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

Ghost events introduce a significant vertex bias and resolution degradation. The resolution function for **Good** events has its most probable value near zero although it

Figure 3.16: Event displays with (blue) proton and (red) pion trajectories together with the true (black dot) and the reconstructed (green triangle) vertices from simulation. The reconstructed vertex is wrongly assigned to the downstream (larger z) crossing point between particle trajectories in most of the decays with inward-bending track topology (left), while it is found correctly in opening-track topologies (right).

has an asymmetric shape towards larger z values. This can be explained as consequence of the large and non-Gaussian momentum uncertainties and the track transport from higher to lower z positions, as illustrated in Fig. 3.17. The resolution function can be well described by the sum of two Gaussian functions with different means and widths, one centred at zero describing the core resolution, and the other with an offset to account for the positive tail. A single Gaussian function with an offset represents the Ghost events, neglecting the very small contribution of Ghost events with negative residual.

Here, all selection criteria and additional vertex quality requirements, in particular z_{vtx} less than 7.6 m and its uncertainty, $\sigma_{z_{\text{vtx}}}$, estimated event-by-event by the vertexing algorithm, below 0.3 m are applied. Dividing the events in bins of the reconstructed z_{vtx} , we produce the same residual distribution and we evaluate the resolution for each bin as the central 68.3% CL region, summing in quadrature the offset, to take into account the bias of the distribution as well. The result is pictured in Fig. 3.18 (left), where it is evident that the Ghost worsen a lot the resolution. In fact, we can see the effect of the two distinct categories and their combination in the "Before BDT" points, the fraction of ghost events in each bin determines the effect in their combination and is reported in the plot as well.

For the case of the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays, the effect of the ghost is not so important, as visible in Fig. 3.18 (right). In fact, as previously mentioned, the topology of the decay leads to only a 6% of Ghost integrated over the decay length. In the case of the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decay, we have studied the Ghost reconstruction in order to have the best possible resolution. The first approach has been to compare the distribution of kinematic and topological variables for the two categories to find differences and apply a cut for their removal. The difficulty lies in the fact that the distributions look almost identical, except for a variable called horizontality h [35], defined as the y component of the unit vector normal to the Λ decay plane multiplied by the dipole magnet polarity, $\text{sign}(B_y)$, and the proton/antiproton charge, $\text{sign}(\Lambda) = +1$ (-1) for Λ ($\bar{\Lambda}$) baryons, *i.e.*

$$h = \text{sign}(\Lambda)\text{sign}(B_y) \frac{(\mathbf{p}_p \times \mathbf{p}_{\pi^-})_y}{|\mathbf{p}_p \times \mathbf{p}_{\pi^-}|}, \quad (3.38)$$

Figure 3.17: Residual distribution of the reconstructed Λ (left) and K_S^0 (right) vertex z position for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ (left) and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ (right) signal candidates in simulation tagged as Good and Ghost, with true Λ (K_S^0) vertex along the z axis above 6.0 m.

where \mathbf{p}_p and \mathbf{p}_{π^-} are the three-momenta of the proton and pion. Decays with the extreme values $h = \pm 1$ lie exactly in the xz bending plane, with $h = -1$ ($h = +1$) events having a completely closing (opening)-track topology, whereas $h = 0$ events lie in the yz plane. Defining also the Ψ angle as the angle between the reconstructed and true decay plain, we can see the distribution of the two categories in the two-dimensional plot in Fig. 3.19. Unfortunately, to compute this last variable, the true information is needed, therefore a selection based on this plane is not applicable to data.

Although having $h < 0$ is necessary to identify Ghost events, this condition is not sufficient, requiring additional information. For this reason, we have trained a Boosted Decision Tree which takes into account also the correlations between the different variables and can help more in the discrimination with respect to a cut based selection. The algorithm chosen is the CatBoostClassifier, of the CatBoost python library. The simulation have been used for the training and to access the performance, after tagging the two categories.

The variables included in the Ghost BDT are the horizontality, which is the most discriminant, as well as the z_{vtx} coordinate, the vertex uncertainty along the y component and the χ_{vtx}^2 of the Λ candidate, the opening angle between the proton and the pion, the coordinates of the point of closest approach between the proton and pion, the $m(p\pi^-)$ invariant mass, the Λ direction angle, and the fake-track probabilities of the proton and pion. The momentum of the final-state particles, the Λ decay length and the Λ_b^0 decay vertex position as obtained from the DTF are also used. The BDT is trained with Good and Ghost simulated signal events. The chosen threshold on the BDT response has a signal efficiency of 75% and removes 75% of the Ghost events, reducing from 30% to 6% the amount of Ghost events in the simulation sample, as illustrated in Fig. 3.17 (right). After applying the BDT cut, the z vertex resolution becomes closer to that of Good events, as it is shown in Fig. 3.18. Therefore, the BDT represents an effective solution to remove the Ghost events and to improve the resolution.

The resolution on the vertex position has been evaluated using only simulated events. In order to compare with data, we cannot compute the resolution in the same way, since the residual distribution cannot be obtained on data. For this reason we can exploit the

Figure 3.18: Relative precision on the reconstructed Λ decay vertex position along the beam axis for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ signal candidates in simulation tagged as **GOOD** (blue triangles) and **GHOST** (orange squares), as well as for events before (green stars) and after (red points) the BDT selection. The resolution is evaluated as the central 68.3% CL region of the underlying residual distribution, adding in quadrature the offset. The fraction of **GHOST** events before (light blue shadow) and after (light orange shadow) the BDT selection criteria are also indicated. The resolution achieved after the BDT selection approaches closely that obtained for **GOOD** events.

output of the VF, which provides an associated uncertainty to estimate on an event-by-event basis the vertex resolution. Figure 3.20 (left) displays the most probable values of the z axis estimates, $\sigma_{z_{vtx}}$, across various regions (bins) of z_{vtx} , for both simulation and data. The error bars are calculated by combining, in quadrature, the 68.3% CL region of the per-event distribution divided by the square root of the yields, along with the half difference between the most probable and median values, which takes into account a systematic error associated to the choice of the most probable value. In Figure 3.20 (right), the $\sigma_{z_{vtx}}$ distribution for candidates in the second bin on the left are shown for both simulation and data. These distributions can be modeled using a Johnson S_U function [107]. A reasonable agreement is observed between simulation and data. The overall offset relative to the resolution estimated from simulation residuals, also illustrated, is attributed to non-Gaussian effects in the vertex reconstruction and the inherent offset of the resolution function. To be noted that the $\sigma_{z_{vtx}}$ distributions remain unaffected by the presence of **GHOST** events and are compared to the resolution computed on residual for only **GOOD** events, which on the contrary depend on the **GHOST** presence. A similar behavior is observed for both decays, see Figs. 3.20 and 3.21.

The BDT to remove the **GHOST** events does have an effect only on the z_{vtx} resolution, but also on the helicity angles. These variables are used to extract the electromagnetic dipole moments measurement of the Λ baryons and therefore the BDT is extremely important for our final goal. The polar and azimuthal angles, θ_p and ϕ_p , of the proton direction in the Λ rest frame, reached from the Λ_b^0 rest frame and rotated by the spherical angles of the Λ momentum in the Λ_b^0 frame (as previously discussed in Chap. 1) are computed using the momenta given by the DTF. Their residuals in simulation are shown in Fig. 3.22. It is strongly affected by the presence of **GHOST** events. Candidates passing the BDT selection have a resolution close to that of **GOOD** events.

To have a comparison between simulation and data we have considered the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays as control sample. This decay allows us to select events within specific helicity

Figure 3.19: Good (blue) and Ghost (orange) events scatter plot in the horizontality computed with true information versus the Ψ angle.

Figure 3.20: (Left) most probable event-by-event uncertainty divided by the mean value of the reconstructed Λ vertex position along the z axis, for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ signal candidates in simulation (orange squares) and data (black points), and in different z_{vtx} regions. The resolutions in simulation estimated from residuals for GOOD events are also shown (blue triangles). The binning scheme is the same as in Fig. 3.18. (Right) distributions of the $\sigma_{z_{\text{vtx}}}$ uncertainties for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ simulation (histogram) and data (points) candidates falling into the second bin of the reconstructed z position.

angle bins by applying cuts in the laboratory frame, made feasible by the ability to select both daughter particles (pions) within the same momentum range. For the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ this is not possible due to the fact that the proton, with the highest mass, takes most of the momentum of the mother particle. Candidates are selected where the longitudinal momentum of the two pions along the K_S^0 line-of-flight in the laboratory frame differs by less than $5 \text{ GeV}/c$. This criterion selects K_S^0 decays where the pions are aligned in the K_S^0 rest frame at approximately $\pm\pi/2$ relative to the K_S^0 direction, resulting in $\cos\theta_{\pi^+} \approx 0$. The $\cos\theta_{\pi^+}$ distribution for candidates that meet this requirement is well-modelled by a Gaussian function. The width of this distribution reflects both the momentum and angular resolutions in the helicity angle calculation and the variation in the true $\cos\theta_{\pi^+}$ value

Figure 3.21: (Left) most probable event-by-event uncertainty divided by the mean value of the reconstructed K_S^0 vertex position along the z axis, for $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ signal candidates in simulation (orange squares) and data (black points), and in different z_{vtx} regions. The resolutions estimated from residuals for Good events in simulation are also shown (blue triangles). The binning scheme is the same as in Fig. 3.18. (Right) distributions of the $\sigma_{z_{vtx}}$ uncertainties for $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ signal candidates in simulation (histogram) and data (points) falling into the second bin of the reconstructed z position.

due to the finite range and resolution of the longitudinal momentum selection. This variation can be estimated from the truth $\cos \theta_{\pi^+}$ distribution in simulation, which is also well-described by a Gaussian function. The $\cos \theta_{\pi^+}$ resolution, measured as the root-mean-square (rms), is represented by the quadratic difference between the two widths. Similarly, we noticed that events with $\cos \theta_{\pi^+} \approx 0.5$ (-0.5) can be isolated by selecting K_S^0 candidates with momentum between 30 and 70 GeV/ c and ensuring that the cosine of the angle between the K_S^0 and the π^- (π^+) in the laboratory frame is less than 0.005. The rms values obtained using this procedure in both simulation and data are presented in Fig. 3.23 (left) and are compared with the corresponding values derived directly from residuals in simulation. The differences between the rms and the 68.3% CL resolutions are attributed to the non-Gaussian behavior of the residual distributions in simulation. Concerning the resolution on the azimuthal angle, ϕ_{π^+} , it is difficult to isolate events with the same value applying cuts in the laboratory frame. For this reason, we have computed its resolution only from simulation, the comparison between the two decays is reasonable, with a better precision for the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$, as expected from the larger Q value.

3.3 Improvements in the vertex fitting algorithm for T tracks

The vertex fitting process begins with the VF, thus our initial focus was on trying enhancing the performance of this algorithm. We conducted studies using the GaudiPython framework [108], which offers the flexibility to easily modify the algorithm, although it limits the dataset size that can be processed. To investigate the sources of the two observed issues, efficiency and resolution bias, we utilized the true information from simulation as input for the algorithm. One aspect of the study involved adjusting the seed by providing the true positions of the daughter particles as input and initializing the covariance matrix C_0 with infinite precision. As shown in Fig. 3.24, this approach reduced the

Figure 3.22: Resolution on the (left) $\cos \theta_p$ and (right) ϕ_p helicity angles for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ signal candidates in simulation tagged as Good (blue triangles) and Ghost (orange squares), as well as for candidates before (green stars) and after (red points) the BDT selection. The resolution achieved after the BDT selection approaches closely that obtained for Good events.

Figure 3.23: Resolution on the (left) $\cos \theta_{\pi^+}$ and (right) ϕ_{π^+} helicity angles for $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ signal candidates in simulation (red points) and those tagged as Good (green triangles), evaluated as the central 68.3% CL region of the residuals. The rms resolution in three different regions of the $\cos \theta_{\pi^+}$ distribution is also evaluated using a data procedure (see text) applied to the simulation (orange squares) and the data (black points), and is compared to that obtained from residuals in simulation (blue triangles).

ghost contribution to approximately 10%, without affecting the overall efficiency. Then, we explored the impact of using true momenta as input, varying the relative momentum resolution σ_p/p at 10%, 5%, 1%, and 0.5%, while setting the vertex position uncertainty in x and y to 100 μm . The true momenta were initially provided at the true Λ decay vertex, necessitating their transport to the first measurement point using a Runge-Kutta (RK) extrapolator, followed by a smearing with the specified uncertainty. The resulting convergence efficiencies of the VF became 83%, 88%, 94%, and 95%, respectively. As illustrated in Fig. 3.25, these findings indicate that improved momentum resolution mit-

Figure 3.24: Effect of the seed on the vertex z coordinate bias obtained from the VF, in $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays simulation. The ghost peak is reduced using the true MC position of the vertex as seed, instead of the default one.

igates bias and enhances the decay vertex reconstruction efficiency. This highlights the importance of refining the momentum resolution for T tracks, although it is not an easy task.

After gaining an understanding of the VF behavior, we attempted to enhance its performance by adjusting the changeable parameters in the algorithm, such as the scaling factor s , the convergence criteria values d_1 and d_2 , and the maximum number of iterations. Unfortunately, none of these adjustments led to improvements in efficiency or reductions in vertex bias. Additionally, altering the seed to positions such as (0,0,5) m, (0,0,6) m, and (0,0,7) m had no impact on either the bias or efficiency. We also investigated whether the extrapolation process could influence the vertexing by analyzing the momentum residuals for both upstream and downstream extrapolations. The results obtained suggested that the extrapolation does not significantly affect the vertex fit, at least to first order. Furthermore, we considered the impact of the non-Gaussian uncertainties. By using an identity matrix as covariance matrix, we observed a more symmetrical residual distribution, yet the efficiency remained unchanged. To address non-converging events, we artificially increased the errors in the covariance matrix to promote convergence in specific planes, specifically we recalculated the fit three times prioritizing $yz \rightarrow xz \rightarrow xy$ planes in this order. This procedure led to a partial recovery of the non-converging events events, about 10%.

Subsequently, we turned our attention to the DTF algorithm, commonly used in LHCb for refitting momenta. By default, the DTF does not return the vertex position, but it can be employed directly as a vertexing algorithm, bypassing the VF entirely. Our initial comparison between the vertex resolution provided by the VF and that obtained from the DTF, without the VF, revealed a reduction in the ghost contribution and a 20% increase in efficiency when skipping the VF as first stage and applying the DTF directly, as shown in Fig. 3.26. We also evaluated the effect of momentum resolution on the DTF by varying σ_p/p from 30% to 10%, 1%, and 0.1%. The results were consistent with those observed with the VF, as illustrated in Fig. 3.28. This demonstrates that also using the DTF as the sole vertexing algorithm could benefit from improved momentum resolution, leading to better convergence and reduced ghost rates.

Figure 3.25: Effect of the momentum resolution on the vertex coordinate z component bias, obtained using the VF. The momenta considered are the true simulated one, to which an increasing smearing is applied.

Figure 3.26: Comparison of the Λ vertex coordinate z residual distribution obtained from the VF, DTF after applying the VF, and DTF without previously using the VF, for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.27: Efficiency of the DTF algorithm with different mass constraints, with $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.28: Effect of the momentum resolution on the vertex coordinate z component bias, obtained using the DTF algorithm, in $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.29: Effect of changing the parameters s and the maximum number of iterations of the DTF on the z coordinate residual, on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

As for the VF, we attempted to optimize the DTF by adjusting its parameters. Modifying the convergence criteria had no effect, but increasing the number of iterations from the default of 10 to 20 resulted in a significant 16% increase in efficiency, without affecting the contribution from ghost events, as shown in Fig. 3.29. Consequently, the optimal approach for the analysis is to rely solely on the DTF with 20 iterations. We also assessed the impact of varying the mass constraints and setting them to the PV. The latter had no effect on efficiency, while the Λ mass constraint was identified as the cause of reduced performance at lower z coordinates, as depicted in Fig. 3.27. One potential solution could be to apply the Λ_b^0 mass constraint instead of the Λ mass constraint, in addition to the J/ψ mass constraint. This approach improves the momentum resolution but worsening the vertex bias. However, the resolutions for the angular variables remain unaffected by these changes.

3.3.1 Forward Tree Fitter

During the development of this thesis, and based on the extensive studies performed with the standard LHCb tools, previously outlined, a new decay tree fitting framework has been implemented, named Forward Tree Fitter (FTF), specifically thought to address the vertexing and kinematic fitting of particle decays containing long-lived particles [109]. A common assumption in these reconstruction algorithms, for simplicity and computation time limitations, is the linearization of charged-particle trajectories in the proximity of the vertex position during the Kalman filtering process. This assumption works well for particle decays occurring in regions with null or small magnetic field, as it holds for decays to Long and Downstream tracks, but it is too approximate for decays in the magnet region (to T tracks), where there is an intense and inhomogeneous magnetic field. This requires trajectory modeling using numerical Runge-Kutta (RK) methods for the track transportation. Moreover, as previously discussed, the initialization of the decay chain fitting is of critical importance. For this reason, the new framework provides a high configuration flexibility, along with algorithms to determine the point-of-closest approach (POCA) between the T tracks accounting for the trajectory curvature (via RK transport). This allows a two step seeding: first the POCA and then the vertex fit. A similar numerical optimization algorithm to that used for the POCA is also used to de-

Figure 3.30: Efficiency comparison of DTF and FTF with J/ψ and Λ mass constraints applied in both algorithms, on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays.

termine the impact parameter of T tracks with respect to the origin or the PVs, which can be used for signal selection. The extensive usage of the RK propagation required the implementation of a dedicated and fast RK extrapolator. All algorithms use as input the five-dimensional track-state vectors and their covariance matrices, as they come out directly from track reconstruction.

The effect on the efficiency can be seen in Fig. 3.30. Looking at the DTF efficiency as a function of the z coordinate, it is clear that the old assumptions were becoming more and more imprecise when increasing the distance from the T stations and therefore increasing the propagation distances. This explains why, in the previous studies, events were considered only for z above 6 m. In contrast, the FTF demonstrates a higher and more stable efficiency across the z range. It is crucial to examine its impact on the $m(J/\psi \Lambda)$ invariant mass. As shown in Fig. 3.31 (left), the effect is particularly significant for $z < 6$ m, while for the events analyzed so far with $z > 6$ m, the resolution remains comparable. The invariant mass resolution, estimated using the 68% confidence interval, is presented in Fig. 3.31 (right) as a function of the z position of the vertex, confirming that the FTF allows for an extended analysis of Λ decays from 3 m to 8 m. It is important to notice that not only the FTF allows the reconstruction of events which decay before 6 m, but their invariant mass resolution is improved. This expansion of the z range in which T tracks are reconstructible increases the available statistics by approximately a factor of three before the selection. In addition, the FTF allows the instantaneous estimation of the final and initial polarization of the long-lived Λ baryons.

A comparative performance study of the DTF and FTF algorithms has been conducted in three distinct ranges: $3 < z < 5$ m, $5 < z < 6$ m and $6 < z < 8$ m. The FTF improves momentum resolution across all three regions, with a particularly significant impact for $z < 6$ m, as pictured in Fig. 3.32.

For $\cos \theta_p$, the resolution remains comparable in the $6 < z < 8$ m range but improves with the FTF in the lower ranges, as outlined in Figs. 3.36, 3.37, 3.38.

As previously explained, the measurement of electromagnetic dipole moments is in-

Figure 3.31: $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ invariant mass distribution obtained from FTF (left). Comparison of the mass resolution between DTF and FTF (right), on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.32: Proton momentum resolution comparison of DTF and FTF in different z ranges: $3 < z < 5$ m (left), $5 < z < 6$ m (center), $6 < z < 8$ m (right), on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

fluenced by the resolution of the helicity angles and the integrated magnetic field, which in turn depends on the vertex position resolution. Regarding the angular resolution, we observe an improvement in all three ranges for the ϕ angle, see Figs. 3.33, 3.34, 3.35. Additionally, the vertex resolution shows significant changes, see the comparison reported in Fig. 3.39. It is important to highlight that for **Good** events the improvement with FTF is huge and that the resolution stays approximately constant in the full z range considered. The bias becomes more symmetric for both **Good** and **Ghost** events. In the case of **Ghost** events, the upstream and downstream components become more balanced, and overall, their fraction decreases across all three ranges thanks to the FTF algorithm, Fig. 3.40.

These performance studies lead to the conclusion that the FTF achieves results comparable to the DTF when analyzing particles decaying beyond 6 m. More importantly, it enables the reconstruction of long-lived particles decaying between 3 and 6 m and reconstructed with T tracks, which was not possible with the previous vertexing algorithms. The same conclusions hold when repeating the study for $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays. In the next chapter, the impact of these additional reconstructed decays on the measurement of electromagnetic dipole moments will be discussed.

Figure 3.33: Proton helicity angle ϕ resolution comparison of DTF (left) and FTF (right) with $3 < z < 5$ m on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.34: Proton helicity angle ϕ resolution comparison of DTF (left) and FTF (right) with $5 < z < 6$ m on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.35: Proton helicity angle ϕ resolution comparison of DTF (left) and FTF (right) with $6 < z < 8$ m on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.36: Proton helicity angle $\cos \theta$ resolution comparison of DTF (left) and FTF (right) with $3 < z < 5$ m on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.37: Proton helicity angle $\cos\theta$ resolution comparison of DTF (left) and FTF (right) with $5 < z < 6$ m on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.38: Proton helicity angle $\cos\theta$ resolution comparison of DTF (left) and FTF (right) with $6 < z < 8$ m on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.39: Relative resolution on the z vertex component as a function of the z position. Comparison of DTF (left) and FTF (right) on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

Figure 3.40: Vertex bias from FTF with Good and Ghost categories in different z ranges: $3 < z < 5$ m (left), $5 < z < 6$ m (center), $6 < z < 8$ m (right), on simulated signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays.

Measurement of the Λ electric and magnetic dipole moments

4.1 Signal candidate selection for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays

The selection process for signal candidates leverages the knowledge gained from the previous performance studies, applying similar but optimized procedures wherever possible. These optimizations aim to enhance the efficiency of each step and expand the signal candidate sample, thereby increasing sensitivity to the measurement of the electric and magnetic dipole moments. A key distinction lies in the dataset: while the studies presented in Chapter 3 exclusively focused on the Run 2 dataset, the final measurement incorporates both Run 1 and Run 2 data to maximize the statistical power. The inclusion of the 3 fb^{-1} Run 1 dataset, in addition to the 6 fb^{-1} from Run 2, brings the total dataset to 9 fb^{-1} . In addition, after the FTF development, we have considered Λ and K_S^0 reconstructed with T tracks with a decay positions from 3 m from the interaction point, with respect to starting from 6 m as in the past. Moreover, Monte Carlo (MC) simulation have been generated separately for each data taking year to account for the differences in detector conditions and configurations across the different periods. The online selection is common for the two decays considered, $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$. For the offline selection, a different optimization for the two channels is performed, maintaining similar criteria but keeping in mind the topological differences between the two, due to the different kinematics involved.

4.1.1 Preselection

An additional development in this analysis is related to the trigger selection. While the performance studies discussed in Chapter 3 did not require the full application of all trigger levels, it is now essential to ensure a robust comparison between MC simulations and data. The trigger strategy focuses on identifying the J/Ψ decay into two muons, a decay mode that LHCb can efficiently reconstruct and trigger. As a result, we take advantage of this trigger, compensating for the absence of a dedicated trigger for T tracks during Run 1 and Run 2 data taking.

Table 4.1 outlines the various trigger steps applied in the analysis, differentiating between Run 1 and Run 2. The table also includes the corresponding efficiency estimates obtained from simulations. In Run 2, the overall efficiency reaches 78.6%, representing a notable drop compared to previous selections where this trigger step was omitted (see Sec. 3.1). To mitigate this loss, further optimizations were introduced. At the hardware level, data were collected using the L0Muon and L0DiMuon trigger lines, which require one or two tracks, respectively, with a transverse momentum (p_T) exceeding a certain threshold and having a trajectory aligned with an energy deposit in the muon stations.

The L0-muon trigger identifies straight-line tracks in the muon stations and uses this information to estimate the transverse momentum (p_T) of the muon candidates. Depending on the configuration, the p_T requirement is applied either to the highest- p_T muon candidate (L0Muon) or to the product of the two highest- p_T candidates (L0DiMuon). The cut is $p_T > 200$ MeV/ c . To streamline event complexity and speed up the reconstruction process, a selection criterion based on the number of hits in the Scintillating Pad Detectors (SPD) of the calorimeter system is applied, requiring it to be lower than 20.

At HLT1 stage, muon lines are generally divided into single and dimuon categories, both utilizing the `isMuon` identification algorithm [110]. Further cuts are applied based on track kinematics and quality metrics. For Run 1, at least one track had to meet the threshold on p_T and χ^2_{IP} to pass the HLT1 selection. However, in Run 2, this decision-making process was replaced by a multivariate classifier (MVA) incorporating the same variables. At the final stage, the HLT2 lines used for the measurement select two, three, or four-track topologies, consistent with decays originating from heavy objects such as B mesons or Λ_b^0 baryons. The requirement imposed by the trigger lines dedicated to select J/ψ decays are detailed in Table 4.1. A logical *OR* is applied across the lines at the same trigger level, and a logical *AND* is applied between the L0, HLT1, and HLT2 levels.

After the trigger selection, data undergo additional processing through the so-called `Stripping` line, which reruns the event reconstruction, applying further selection criteria and computing derived variables required for analysis. These additional requirements are applied on the mass of the J/ψ , the p_T of the muon and its PID to mitigate misidentification with the pion ($\Delta \log L_{\mu-\pi}$), and the decay length significance computed with respect to the best PV (Best PV $\parallel DLS \parallel$), measuring how significantly the secondary vertex is displaced from the best PV. During Run 1 the additional requirement that the maximum muon χ^2/ndf of the track fit was present. A comparison between the HLT2 and the `Stripping` requirements can be performed having a look at the Tables 4.2 and 4.3.

Table 4.1: Efficiencies and trigger lines for the different runs and stages.

Stage	Run I			Run II		
L0	L0Muon L0DiMuon			L0Muon L0DiMuon		
HLT1	Hlt1TrackAllL0 Hlt1TrackMuon Hlt1DiMuonHighMass Hlt1DiMuonLowMass			Hlt1TrackMVA Hlt1TrackMuon Hlt1DiMuonHighMass Hlt1DiMuonLowMass		
HLT2	Hlt2Topo{2,3,4}BodyBBDT Hlt2TopoMu{2,3,4}Body Hlt2DiMuonDetached Hlt2DiMuonDetachedJPsi			Hlt2Topo{2,3,4}Body Hlt2TopoMu{2,3,4}Body Hlt2DiMuonDetached Hlt2DiMuonDetachedJPsi		
efficiency	2011	2012	2015	2016	2017	2018
	76.7%	73.4%	69.6%	77.4%	82.6%	76.8%

The first major improvement compared to previous studies concerns the vertex reconstruction procedure. In this analysis, we chose to employ the FTF to exploit its superior performance and to expand the region where T track vertices are reconstructed,

Selection	Criteria
DiMuonDetached	$p_T > 600 \text{ MeV}/c$ p_T (at least one μ) $> 300 \text{ MeV}/c$ Vertex $\chi^2 < 9$ IP $\chi^2 > 9$ Decay length $\chi^2 > 7$
DiMuonDetachedJpsi	DiMuonDetached $m(J/\psi) < 120 \text{ MeV}/c^2$

Table 4.2: HLT2 trigger selection criteria focusing on the $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ decay.

Variable	Requirement
Best PV $\ DLS\ $	> 3
Min. $\Delta \log L_{\mu-\pi}$	> 0
Min. $p_T(\mu)$	$> 500 \text{ MeV}/c$
Max. $\chi_{tr}^2/\text{ndf}(\mu)$	< 5
χ_{vtx}^2/ndf	< 20
$ m(\mu^+\mu^-) - m(J/\psi) $	$< 100 \text{ MeV}/c^2$

Table 4.3: Requirements for $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ in the Stripping selection. The variables are described in the text.

as discussed in the previous section. We require the convergence of the fitting algorithm configured with both the J/ψ and Λ invariant mass constraints (see Table 4.8), imposing the reconstructed invariant mass to be identical to the nominal mass, while recomputing the final-state particle momenta.

Regarding the preselection cuts, most thresholds have been retained (see Tables 3.1 and 4.8); however, modifications have been made to enlarge the allowed z -ranges for the true and reconstructed Λ end-vertex positions. The updated requirement is $3000 \text{ mm} < z_{\text{reco}}(\Lambda) < 8500 \text{ mm}$. This adjustment enlarges the decay volume, allowing the reconstruction of more particles decaying inside the magnetic field region. Although not all Λ baryons achieve maximal spin precession, the event-by-event calculation of the precession ensures that all events are appropriately accounted for in the maximum likelihood fit for the electric and magnetic dipole moments extraction, as well as for the initial polarization measurement.

In the context of this thesis, a study on the use of Particle Identification (PID) information for T tracks has also been performed. Previously, such information was unavailable for T tracks. To enable the use of PID variables, the offline reconstruction sequence was reprocessed, exploiting the full persistency of the stripping line, meaning that the complete information of the event had been stored. However, this reprocessing was only possible for real data, as the simulation format does not allow to have the full information stored consistently across all data-taking years. For real data, the Brunel [90] reconstruction was rerun, followed by DaVinci [91], allowing the PID variables for electrons, kaons, pions, and protons to be saved. To maintain consistency between simulation and real data, while still taking advantage of the available PID information, a loose cut on electrons was considered to suppress background from material interactions in data. This kind of background is underestimated in simulation. The requirements imposed

Figure 4.1: (Left) reconstructed invariant mass $m(p\pi^-)$ distribution before and after applying the cut on the PID of the electron, using 2018 data only with down magnet polarity. Mass reconstructed by FTF with J/ψ mass constraint. (Right) effect of applying the additional PID cuts on the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ reconstructed mass distribution to suppress the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ background, with J/ψ and Λ mass constraints by FTF.

are on the electron misidentification as proton and pion respectively,

$$\text{PID}_e(p) < 5 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{PID}_e(\pi) < 3. \quad (4.1)$$

These cuts have an efficiency of 98.7%, and their effect in removing background from material interactions is shown in Fig. 4.1 (left). However, due to their minimal impact and the imbalance introduced between data and simulation, we ultimately decided not to apply these selection criteria. Additional requirements were explored to suppress background from B^0 decays:

$$\text{PID}_K(p) > -10 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{PID}_p(p) > -1 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{PID}_K(\pi) < 15. \quad (4.2)$$

However, the efficiency of this selection was only 80%, and a peaking misidentified $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0 (\rightarrow \Lambda)$ background still remained in the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ invariant mass distribution, as seen in Fig. 4.1 (right). Given the low efficiency, in line with maintaining maximum consistency between simulation and real data, no requirement on the PID variables is applied to remove physical background or to distinguish between Λ and K_S^0 candidates. Consequently, it remains necessary to rely on the AP method to suppress the physical background from $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0 (\rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-)$ decays, as done in the performance studies. The AP selection criteria are detailed in Table 4.5. In the earlier analyses, an additional veto was applied to reduce physical background; however, it was found that this veto introduced a modification of the invariant mass distribution, as shown in Fig. 4.2, especially on the left of the peak. To avoid artificially distorting the mass shape, a better approach is proposed: training a multivariate classifier with three categories, one specifically designed to suppress this background, as will be described in the next section.

All the steps of the preselection described above are summarized in Fig. 4.3, where the corresponding efficiencies are reported. As can be observed, the efficiency shows no strong dependence on the z -position of the Λ decay vertex, in contrast to what was seen in the previous analysis.

Figure 4.2: Effect of B^0 veto application on the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ reconstructed mass distribution, mass from FTF with J/ψ and Λ mass constraint.

Table 4.4: Loose preselection requirements.

Variable	Selection criteria
pim.P: pion momentum	$2 \times 10^3 < \text{pim.P} < 5 \times 10^5 \text{ MeV}/c$
p.P: proton momentum	$1 \times 10^4 < \text{p.P} < 5 \times 10^5 \text{ MeV}/c$
p_PT: proton transverse momentum	$\text{p_PT} > 400 \text{ MeV}/c$
L.M_VTX: Λ reconstructed mass by the VF	$600 < \text{L.M.VTX} < 1800 \text{ MeV}/c^2$
L_BPVDIRA: direction angle between the Λ momentum and the vector pointing from the PV to the decay vertex	$\text{L.BPVDIRA} > 0.9997$
L_BPVIPCHI2: Impact parameter χ^2 of the particle w.r.t. the PV	$\text{L.BPVIPCHI2} < 100$
L_BPVVDCHI2: χ^2 of the vertex displacement between the PV and the decay vertex	$\text{L.BPVVDCHI2} < 2.5 \times 10^6$
L_VFASPF_CHI2_VDOF: vertex fit quality expressed by χ^2 over number of degrees of freedom (NDF)	$\text{L.VFASPF.CHI2.VDOF} < 120$
L_PT: Λ transverse momentum	$\text{L.PT} > 450 \text{ MeV}/c$
Jpsi.M: J/ψ reconstructed mass	$ \text{Jpsi.M} - 3096.9 < 90 \text{ MeV}/c^2$
Lb_BPVDIRA: see above, referred to Λ_b^0	$ \text{Lb.BPVDIRA} > 0.9994$
Lb_BPVIPCHI2: see above, referred to Λ_b^0	$\text{Lb.BPVIPCHI2} < 40$
Lb_BPVVDCHI2: see above, referred to Λ_b^0	$\text{Lb.BPVVDCHI2} < 1.2 \times 10^4$
Lb_VFASPF_CHI2_VDOF: see above, referred to Λ_b^0	$\text{Lb.VFASPF.CHI2.VDOF} < 40$
FTF_FixJPsiLambda_status: FTF convergence status, with constraints on J/ψ and Λ masses	$\text{FTF.FixJPsiLambda.status} \leq 1$
FTF_FixJPsiLambda.L_ENDVERTEX.Z: z coordinate of Λ vertex from FTF	$3 < \text{FTF.FixJPsiLambda.L.ENDVERTEX.Z} < 9 \text{ m}$
FTF_FixJPsiLambda.Lb.M: Λ_b^0 invariant mass from FTF	$4860 < \text{FTF.FixJPsiLambda.Lb.M} < 6530 \text{ MeV}/c^2$

Table 4.5: Armenteros-Podolanski selection criteria, variable defined in Eq. (3.16).

Variable	Cut Applied
FTF_FixJPsi_p_asymm	$ \text{FTF_FixJPsi_p_asymm} \geq 0.5$

Figure 4.3: Efficiency of the different steps of the preselection as a function of the decay vertex coordinate z of the Λ baryons.

Figure 4.4: $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ reconstructed invariant mass distribution of proxies used to train the HBDT: Λ_b^0 signal is taken from simulation, $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ peaking background from simulation, and combinatorial background from the data sidebands.

4.1.2 Multivariate classifier for the selection of $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ signal decays

To effectively discriminate signal from background, the same Histogram Boosted Decision Tree (HBDT) approach as in previous analyses (Chapter 3) is retained, but now incorporating additional variables to enhance the separation power. The signal selection strategy employs two sequential HBDTs. The first, HBDT1, is used to extract a dataset of signal candidates from data, which cannot otherwise be cleanly identified through the invariant mass distribution alone. Once a clear signal peak emerges in the data, the SPlot technique [111] is employed to statistically separate signal and background candidates. The extracted signal candidates are then used to reweight the simulation, meaning that a weight is assigned to align the simulation with the real data distributions. This reweighted simulation sample is subsequently used to train the second HBDT2, resulting in an improved description of the signal distributions. A final selection is then performed by applying a requirement on the output of HBDT2, with the optimal threshold determined by maximizing the significance (3.15) figure of merit (FoM).

HBDT Training

As previously discussed, the application of the B^0 veto has been removed to avoid distortions in the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ reconstructed invariant mass distribution. However, the B^0 background peak overlaps with the Λ_b^0 signal, particularly for events where the Λ decays beyond 6 m from the pp interaction point, with looser mass resolution. To address this, the HBDT is trained to distinguish among three categories: signal, combinatorial background, and B^0 peaking background. The procedure is described in detail in the following sections. As a proxy for combinatorial background, events from both the upper and lower mass sidebands (UMSB and LMSB) are used, defined respectively by $6230 < m(J/\psi\Lambda) < 6530 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ and $4860 < m(J/\psi\Lambda) < 5010 \text{ MeV}/c^2$. Truth-matched simulated $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays serve as the signal proxy, while for the B^0 peaking back-

ground, a dedicated proxy from truth-matched $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ simulations is employed. The adopted ratio for training events is 10:1:10 (signal:background: B^0), which after testing, shows the best performance across the three categories, based on the significance FoM. The corresponding normalized distributions for the three categories is shown in Fig. 4.4. The simulated dataset is divided into two parts: 70% for training and 30% for testing.

The input variables to the HBDT include:

- The logarithms of the momenta and transverse momenta obtained from the FTF reconstruction, $\log p^{FTF}$ and $\log p_T^{FTF}$, for the J/Ψ , Λ_b^0 , and Λ candidates.
- The impact parameter variables, $\text{IP}^{\text{RK}}(\Lambda_b^0)$ and $\text{IP}^{\text{RK}}(\pi^-)$, representing the distance of closest approach to the "best" (closer) primary vertex, computed using a Golden Section algorithm with Runge-Kutta trajectory transport.
- Direction angle variables, DIRA^{VTX} , for Λ_b^0 and Λ candidates, which measure the alignment between the Λ momentum vector and the vector connecting the Λ production and decay vertices.
- The transverse displacement of Λ_b^0 and Λ decay vertices relative to the beamline, expressed by $\text{vrho}(\Lambda_b^0)$ and $\text{vrho}(\Lambda)$.
- Vertex fit qualities, encoded in $\ln(\chi^2/\text{ndof})^{\text{VTX}}(\Lambda_b^0)$ (natural logarithm of the vertex fit χ^2 per degree of freedom) and $\ln \Sigma \chi^2(\Lambda_b^0)$ (cumulative fit quality across all tracks).
- The distance of closest approach between daughter tracks forming the Λ candidates, denoted $\text{DOCA}^{\text{RK}}(\Lambda)$, using a Golden Section algorithm with Runge-Kutta trajectory transport.
- A variable assessing track reconstruction consistency, $\ln(\chi^2(\text{FTF2})/\chi^2(\text{FTF2} - \text{PIDSubs}))$, which is particularly useful for suppressing B^0 peaking background.
- The transverse momentum asymmetry between decay products ($p_{\text{asymm}}^{\text{FTF1}}$), defined as $(p_{T1} - p_{T2})/(p_{T1} + p_{T2})$, using the FTF fit, with only the J/Ψ mass constraint.

The relative importance of each variable for both the training and testing samples is shown in Fig. 4.5. Applying a logarithmic transformation to these input variables was found to improve their discrimination power. Unless explicitly stated otherwise, all figures reporting HBDT performance refer to the second HBDT, to avoid redundancy.

A comprehensive grid search was conducted to optimize the hyperparameters of the first HBDT, including the learning rate, the maximum number of leaf nodes, and the maximum number of iterations, as discussed in the previous Chapter. The algorithm used is `GridSearchCV` of the *scikit-learn* package [112]. The figure of merit adopted for the optimization is the *F1 score*, also known as the *balanced F-score* or *F-measure*. The F1 score combines precision and recall into a single metric, defined as their harmonic mean, making it particularly useful in scenarios characterized by class imbalance, such as the present case. Its value ranges from 0 (worst performance) to 1 (best performance). The F1 score is mathematically expressed as

$$F1 = \frac{2 \cdot TP}{2 \cdot TP + FP + FN},$$

where:

Figure 4.5: Feature importance of HBDT for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays.

Figure 4.6: F1 score of the grid scan points, on the x axis for the test set, while on the y axis the difference of the F1 score on the train and test sets. The best hyperparameters chosen are those giving the red cross.

Figure 4.7: ROC curves of the HBDT1.

- TP is the number of true positives,
- FP is the number of false positives,
- FN is the number of false negatives.

In cases where all TP , FP , and FN are zero, the F1 score is conventionally defined as zero. The optimal working point is determined by maximizing the F1 score on the test dataset while simultaneously minimizing the difference between the F1 scores obtained on the training and test samples, thereby mitigating overtraining risks. The results of the grid search and the selected working point are shown in Fig. 4.6. To further validate the absence of overtraining, a Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test [113] was performed, yielding p-values exceeding 5% for both the signal and background classes.

The performance of the trained HBDT is assessed through the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, which illustrates the trade-off between the true positive rate and the false positive rate. An area under the ROC curve (AUC) close to 1 indicates a highly performant classifier. Given the multiclass nature of the problem, separate ROC curves are produced for each class against the remaining ones. These are displayed in Fig. 4.7. The peaking background from $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays exhibits the lowest AUC, consistent with the fact that it constitutes the most challenging background to suppress. Nevertheless, the overall classifier performance is satisfactory. The output of the HBDT consists of three variables, one for each class, with their sum constrained to unity. These HBDT outputs are utilized to distinguish signal from background in the subsequent data analysis. It was found that applying a requirement on two of these outputs provides an effective strategy to identify signal candidates while suppressing both combinatorial and peaking backgrounds. Initially, loose selection criteria are imposed to enhance the signal visibility in the $m(J/\psi \Lambda)$ invariant mass spectrum, requiring the output of the background to be < 0.8 . Following this, a fit to the mass distribution is performed, and the SPlot technique is employed to statistically disentangle signal and background events, setting the foundation for better training of HBDT2.

4.1.3 Calibration of the simulated sample

To enhance the performance of the HBDT, it is necessary to have distributions in simulation close to those in data, thus a calibration (correction) of the simulated sample is required. This calibration is not only critical for improving the signal selection efficiency

Figure 4.8: Distributions of the variables used in the HBDT before (raw MC) and after (weighted MC) the simulation correction, compared to their distributions in background-subtracted signal data.

but also plays an essential role in the subsequent fitting procedure for the dipole moments measurement, in particular the determination of the acceptance and resolution effects. The primary motivation lies on the fact that the simulation does not perfectly replicate experimental conditions, where detector effects introduce distortions that must be accounted for.

For this purpose, a reweighting procedure is implemented using a multivariate algorithm, specifically the `GBreweighter` tool from the `hep_ml` package [114]. This tool, based on a Gradient Boosted Decision Tree (GBDT) model, is particularly suited for capturing correlations among input variables and for learning the multidimensional discrepancies between MC and data samples, for this reason it is well suitable to our case. During the training phase, the background-subtracted signal data are treated as the target distribution, while the MC simulation represents the source. The algorithm learns the differences between the two samples, subsequently assigning a weight to each simulated event: higher weights to events that resemble the data and lower weights to events that deviate. These weights are then applied to the MC events to correct their distributions and achieve better agreement with the real data.

The features employed in the reweighting procedure include,

- $\log p(\Lambda_b^0)$ (FTF),
- $\log p_T(\Lambda_b^0)$ (FTF),
- $\log p(J/\psi)$ (FTF),
- $\log p_T(J/\psi)$ (FTF),
- $\log p_T(\Lambda)$ (FTF),
- $\log p_T(\Lambda)$ (FTF),
- $\ln \Sigma \chi^2 (\Lambda_b^0)$,
- p_{asymm}^{FTF} ,

with the FTF configured with the J/ψ and Λ mass constraints in all variables except for p_{asymm}^{FTF} , that uses only the J/ψ mass. These variables were selected because they are uncorrelated with the angular observables used in the final fit for the EMDMs, ensuring that the reweighting procedure does not bias the physics measurement, see Appendix.

Figure 4.8 compares the distributions of the selected variables before and after the reweighting procedure, showing a significant improvement in the agreement between simulation and data. From this point onward, the correction factors produced by the `GBreweighter` are systematically applied to the MC events, resulting in a more accurate and data-representative simulated sample.

4.1.4 HBDT2 after the simulation calibration

Once the MC sample accurately reproduces the data distributions through the reweighting procedure outlined above, it is employed as a proxy for retraining the HBDT2 to refine the event selection. The algorithm is retrained, with its hyperparameters optimized again via a grid search. The updated performance, illustrated in Fig. 4.9, demonstrates a slight improvement in the AUC values compared to those obtained previously in Fig. 4.7.

After determining the optimal hyperparameters, the HBDT is applied to the data. The working point is selected by maximizing the signal significance. Although several

Figure 4.9: ROC curves of the HBDT2 for signal (left), peaking background (center) and combinatorial background (right).

figures of merit were evaluated, the significance was chosen as it best suits the needs of the final measurement. For instance, the comparison with the significance times purity FoM has been explored with pseudoexperiments and the sensitivity on the electric and magnetic dipole moment has been considered as FoM. This study showed the significance optimization leads to a better sensitivity. Since the HBDT outputs three response variables corresponding to the signal and two backgrounds, a two-dimensional threshold is applied on the signal output (HBDT2_sig_out) and the peaking background output (HBDT2_B0_out): $\text{HBDT2_sig_out} > 0.27 \ \& \ \text{HBDT2_B0_out} < 0.05$. The optimized requirement result in a signal efficiency of 70 % and a background rejection rate of 56%, evaluated on the simulation. For the evaluation of the significance, the signal region is defined within a $\pm 3\sigma$ window around the mean of the Λ_b^0 invariant mass distribution.

4.1.5 Invariant mass fit

Following the event selection, the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ invariant mass is fitted separately for the Run 1 and Run 2 datasets. The fits are shown in Figs. 4.10, 4.11, using a double Crystall Ball for the signal shape, with only the sigma let float on data, while the other parameters are fixed from the fit to simulation, Fig. 4.12 (left). For the combinatorial background a Chebychev polynomial [115] of order one is employed, while the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ background shape is taken from the fit on simulation, see Fig. 4.12 (right). Other background contributions from partially reconstructed backgrounds have been considered, such as $B^+ \rightarrow J/\psi K_s^0 \pi^+$, $B_S^+ \rightarrow J/\psi K_s^0 \pi^+$, $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K^*$, $B_S^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K^*$ and $\Xi_b^- \rightarrow J/\psi \Xi^- (\rightarrow \Lambda \pi^-)$ decays. None of them showed any variation in the fit quality, since their contribution is negligible.

The Run 2 dataset is further subdivided into three regions based on the decay position z : 3–5 m, 5–6 m, and 6–8 m. The corresponding mass resolutions are found to be 16.2 ± 0.3 , 27.4 ± 0.7 , and 48 ± 2 MeV/ c^2 , respectively. For this reason the fit are kept separated in the three z regions. The observed increase in resolution with z is consistent with expectations from simulation, reflecting the effect of improved momentum resolution at smaller z due to longer tracking lever arms inside the magnetic field. The number of signal candidates identified within a 3σ window in each z -region, along with the background candidates, purity and significance are reported in Table 4.7.

For the Run 1 sample, consistent results are obtained, summarized in Table 4.6 and plotted in Fig. 4.10 . The inclusion of Run 1 data notably improves the statistical precision and enhances the sensitivity to the electromagnetic dipole moment measurements.

Figure 4.10: $m(J/\psi \Lambda)$ invariant mass fit on Run 1 dataset in the different z regions: (top left) 3–5 m, (top right) 5–6 m, (bottom) 6–7.6 m.

Figure 4.11: $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ invariant mass fit on Run 2 dataset in the different z regions: (top left) 3–5 m, (top right) 5–6 m, (bottom) 6–7.6 m.

Figure 4.12: $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ invariant mass fit on simulation for signal (left) and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ peaking background (right). The fit results are reported on the figures and the blue dotted lines define the 3σ region.

Table 4.6: Fit results in 3σ window in the three z regions, on Run 1 data for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ candidates.

	$3 < z < 5$ m	$5 < z < 6$ m	$6 < z < 8$ m
Signal yield	2887 ± 82	1298 ± 80	1704 ± 203
B^0 Peaking background yield	379 ± 29	327 ± 66	165 ± 82
Combinatorial background yield	1985 ± 21	1519 ± 35	4540 ± 70
Purity	55%	41%	27%
Significance	40	23	21

Table 4.7: Fit results in 3σ window in the three z regions, on Run 2 data for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ candidates.

	$3 < z < 5$ m	$5 < z < 6$ m	$6 < z < 8$ m
Signal yield	10438 ± 141	5205 ± 124	5877 ± 254
B^0 Peaking background yield	1532 ± 46	1289 ± 82	2818 ± 439
Combinatorial background yield	3625 ± 33	3061 ± 48	7334 ± 267
Purity	67%	54%	37%
Significance	84	53	46

The improvement from switching from the DTF to the FTF has been validated on data, confirming expectations from simulation. Applying the BDT optimized on the full range (3–8 m), and selecting events with $z > 5$ m, the invariant mass resolution improves from 46 ± 2 MeV/ c^2 with DTF to 32 ± 1 MeV/ c^2 with FTF, using identical mass constraints on J/ψ and Λ particles. A doubled signal yields is obtained, with purities of 53% and 51% and significances of 54 and 74, respectively. These results demonstrate significant improvements in both resolution and signal efficiency. The comparison for $z < 5$ m cannot be performed since the DTF efficiency is very poor in this region.

Since the events with Λ baryons decaying above 6 m in z give the highest sensitivity to the EMDMs, we considered to train a dedicated HBDT for these events. Afterwards we compared the results obtained before, training on the full range and subsequently apply the cut $z > 6$ m. The results obtained are compatible within uncertainties, therefore we decided to train a unique HBDT for all the events.

4.1.6 Ghost decay vertex

At this stage, a new BDT is trained to effectively distinguish between Good and Ghost vertices, as it became evident that the presence of Ghost vertices degrades the resolution and thus impacts the sensitivity of the final dipole moment measurement. The challenge in differentiating these two categories lies on the fact that their topological and kinematic distributions show minimal distinctions. A multivariate method that captures correlations across several variables is necessary for separating them. The chosen algorithm is a Graph Neural Network (GNN), which showed the best performance among others algorithms tried, like CatBoost and BDTs. We introduced additional variables to enhance the separation process. Both the signal and background proxies were derived from the simulation dataset, utilizing the true information to classify events into the two categories,

Figure 4.13: ROC curve for the GNN trained to distinguish between Good and Ghost events.

Figure 4.14: Residual distribution of z_{vtx} (left) before applying any GNN requirement, (right) after selecting 10% of Ghost with the GNN.

as previously described. The variables used in input are the proton and pion track state, meaning position and slope at the first measurement point, then the vertex position and associated error given by the FTF of Λ_b^0 and Λ baryons, the output position of the DOCA for all the composite particles Λ_b^0 , J/ψ , Λ ; the IP of all the particles; p_{asymm}^{FTF} ; pseudorapidity of the Λ baryon; the ghost probability of proton and pion; $\chi^2/ndof$ of the tracks and the horizontality h . Other variables have been computed propagating the trajectories of the reconstructed particles to the reconstructed vertex and computing the number of intersections and the angle between the pion and proton at the vertex.

The classifier performance was evaluated on a subset of the MC data, specifically 10% of the total, achieving an AUC of 0.76, as observed from the ROC curve displayed in Fig. 4.13. The optimization of the cut was based on a pseudoexperiments studies to maximize the sensitivity on the EMDMs, they will be detailed in the following. In this scenario, the objective is to retain the maximum number of signal events to maintain sensitivity to the measurement, while simultaneously removing as many Ghost events as possible to improve resolution. Simulations are in place to explore different working points and identify the optimal configuration. These pseudoexperiments studies will be used in the future to set the requirement on the GNN output. In Fig. 4.14, the vertex bias

is plotted both before and after the GNN cut, demonstrating a reduction in the Ghost fraction from 30% to 10% and most importantly a more symmetrical distribution after the GNN requirement. The optimal cut has to be still found and subsequently applied to the real data, followed by a final fit to the invariant mass of the Λ_b^0 baryon. For the very first measurement presented in this thesis, no GNN requirement is applied and the Ghost are retained.

4.2 Control sample: $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_s^0$ decays

For the selection of the control sample candidates from $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_s^0$ decays, we followed a strategy similar to that adopted for the signal channel. This ensures minimal differences due to the selection procedures. However, since the decay topology is different and this channel serves as a control sample, simplifications were applied where possible to the selection procedure, as discussed in this section.

4.2.1 Preselection

Table 4.8: Loose preselection requirements.

Variable	Selection criteria
pim_P: negative pion momentum	$2.5 \times 10^3 < \text{pim_P MeV}/c$
pip_P: positive pion momentum	$2.5 \times 10^3 < \text{pip_P MeV}/c$
KS0_BPVDIRA: direction angle between the K_s^0 momentum and the vector pointing from the PV to the decay vertex	$\text{KS0_BPVDIRA} > 0.9997$
KS0_BPVIPCHI2: Impact parameter χ^2 of the particle w.r.t. the PV	$\text{KS0_BPVIPCHI2} < 100$
KS0_BPVVDCHI2: χ^2 of the vertex displacement between the PV and the decay vertex	$\text{KS0_BPVVDCHI2} < 2.5 \times 10^6$
KS0_VFASPF_CHI2_VDOF: vertex fit quality expressed by χ^2 over number of degrees of freedom (NDF)	$\text{KS0_VFASPF_CHI2_VDOF} < 120$
Jpsi_PT: J/ψ transverse momentum	$\text{Jpsi_PT} > 250 \text{ MeV}/c$
Jpsi_P: J/ψ transverse momentum	$\text{Jpsi_P} > 1.8 \times 10^4 \text{ MeV}/c$
Jpsi_M: J/ψ reconstructed mass	$ \text{Jpsi_M} - 3096.9 < 90 \text{ MeV}/c^2$
B0_BPVDIRA: see above, referred to B^0	$ \text{B0_BPVDIRA} > 0.9994$
B0_BPVIPCHI2: see above, referred to B^0	$\text{B0_BPVIPCHI2} < 40$
B0_BPVVDCHI2: see above, referred to B^0	$\text{B0_BPVVDCHI2} < 1.2 \times 10^4$
B0_VFASPF_CHI2_VDOF: see above, referred to B^0	$\text{B0_VFASPF_CHI2_VDOF} < 40$
FTF_FixJPsiKaon_status: FTF convergence status, with constraints on J/ψ and K_s^0 masses	$\text{FTF_FixJPsiKaon_status} \leq 1$
FTF_FixJPsiKaon_KS0_ENDVERTEX_Z: z coordinate of K_s^0 vertex from FTF	$3 < \text{FTF_FixJPsiKaon_KS0_ENDVERTEX_Z} < 9 \text{ m}$
FTF_FixJPsiKaon_B0_M: B^0 invariant mass from FTF	$4500 < \text{FTF_FixJPsiKaon_B0_M} < 6200 \text{ MeV}/c^2$

Figure 4.15: $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ invariant mass distributions with and without the AP requirement, in the different z ranges: with $3 < z < 5$ m (left), with $5 < z < 6$ m (center), and with $6 < z < 8$ m (right).

The preselection steps for $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays closely mirror those used for the Λ_b^0 signal channel. In particular, the trigger requirements are identical, as both decays involve a J/ψ in the final state. The applied preselection criteria are listed in Table 4.8, with analogous requirements imposed on the corresponding particles of the B^0 decay. The AP requirement is also applied,

$$|\text{FTF_FixJPsi_p_asymm}| \leq 0.5, \quad (4.3)$$

although its efficiency is lower compared to the case of Λ signal events, as previously discussed in the performance studies. While the Λ candidate contamination is negligible for K_S^0 mesons decaying beyond 6 m, it becomes significant for upstream decays, with $3 < z < 5$ m, as illustrated in Fig. 4.15. The efficiency of the preselection as a function of the z component of the K_S^0 decay vertex is shown in Fig. 4.16. A comparison with the Λ_b^0 channel reveals similar behavior, except for the impact of the AP cut as previously discussed.

Figure 4.16: Efficiency of the preselection steps of the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_s^0$ control sample.

Figure 4.17: Feature importance of B^0 HBDT2 for Run 2 data.

4.2.2 Multivariate selection

An HBDT classifier is also trained for this decay. However, only two categories (signal and combinatorial background) are needed. As seen in Fig. 4.15, after the AP cut, the physical background from Λ is sufficiently suppressed, leaving no overlap with the B^0 mass peak. A structure on the left side of the B^0 peak remains, attributed to partially reconstructed events, which will be modeled using simulation templates and included in the invariant mass fit. Since no clear B^0 signal is visible before the multivariate classifier selection, two consecutive HBDTs are employed. The simulation is reweighted according to signal data extracted using the first HBDT (HBDT1), and a second HBDT (HBDT2) is trained on this corrected dataset.

The HBDT1 and HBDT2 training uses signal proxies from simulated $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays, in the range $5020 < m(J/\psi K_S^0) < 6220$ MeV/c², and background proxies from the data sidebands, defined between $4860 < m(J/\psi K_S^0) < 5010$ MeV/c² and $6230 < m(J/\psi K_S^0) < 6530$ MeV/c² in the invariant mass. The input variables are selected similarly to those used for Λ_b^0 decays, excluding features specifically designed to suppress peaking backgrounds and those of negligible importance. Final variables included:

- the logarithm of the longitudinal momenta ($\log p_T^{\text{FTF}}$, $\log p_Z^{\text{FTF}}$) of the two pions from the FTF reconstruction without mass constraints;
- the logarithm of the transverse momentum of the B^0 and K_S^0 candidates,
- the direction angle for the B^0 ;
- the logarithm of the B^0 vertex χ^2 ;
- the impact parameter (IP), distance of closest approach (DOCA), and pseudorapidity η of the K_S^0 meson.

The feature importance for both training and test sets is shown in Fig. 4.17. Care is taken to avoid using FTF outputs with mass constraints, preserving them for subsequent helicity angle measurements. Hyperparameters were optimized using a grid search. Overtraining was checked with a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test applied to the HBDT outputs, resulting in p-values of 28% (signal) and 77% (background). The HBDT achieved an AUC of 0.994 on the test set.

Given that the mass resolution varies across the z regions, with better resolution at smaller z values, a dedicated HBDT was trained on events with $z > 6$ m. However, no significant improvement was observed compared to the HBDT trained over the full range. Similarly, no difference was found whether the AP cut is applied before or after the HBDT training; to reduce the dataset size, the selection is applied beforehand.

After a loose requirement on the HBDT1 output, the invariant mass distribution shown in Fig. 4.19 (left) is obtained. Before extracting sWeights, the partially reconstructed backgrounds ($B^+ \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0 \pi^+$ and $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K^*$) are parametrized using RooKeyPdf [116] and double Crystal Ball functions respectively, fitted to simulation samples. Their relative normalizations were fixed according to the ratio of their branching fractions ($(1.1 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-3}$ and $(1.43 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-3}$ [16]) times selection efficiencies, equals to 0.28% and 0.24% respectively, after the selection steps. Thus the ratio equals 0.66. The combined model was fitted to the data, as shown in Fig. 4.19 (right). The fitted signal yield is 40918 ± 577 , for the peaking background 83 ± 8 candidates are found, and for the combinatorial background 65556 ± 283 candidates. A purity of 38% and a significance of 125 are obtained after the selection criteria. At this stage, the goal is to accurately model the distributions for sWeight computation, not to extract final yields.

Figure 4.18: Invariant mass distribution of partially reconstructed background $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ from $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K^*$ (magenta dotted) and $B^+ \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0 \pi^+$ (light blue dotted) decays. The shape is parametrized with a double Crystal Ball added to a RooKeyPdf [116]. Their ratio is fixed from the efficiency estimation and the measured branching ratio.

Figure 4.19: (Left) distribution of $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ invariant mass before the selection and after loose selection on HBDT1 output. (Right) fit of the $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ invariant mass after loose requirement on the HBDT1, Run 2 dataset. The partially reconstructed backgrounds are listed in the plot (light blue and green dotted line) and the combinatorial background is reported (blue dotted line).

Figure 4.20: Distributions of the variables used in the HBDT before (raw MC) and after (weighted MC) the simulation reweighting, compared to their distributions in sWeighted data.

For simulation calibration, the same procedure as for the signal channel is adopted. The variables used for reweighting include:

- Number of tracks (nTracks);
- Logarithm of the transverse momentum and total momentum of the B^0 ;
- z -position of the K_S^0 vertex from FTF fits with J/ψ and K_S^0 mass constraints.

Comparisons of the variables before and after reweighting are shown in Fig. 4.20.

Following the calibration, the HBDT2 is trained using the reweighted simulation as the signal proxy. The combinatorial background proxy and the training procedure remain unchanged. The AUC improves to 0.997 on the test set, with KS test p-values of 67% (signal) and 72% (background), confirming the absence of overtraining. The optimized HBDT2 selection criteria, chosen based on maximizing the significance, is set at 0.9616. Applying this cut to the partially reconstructed backgrounds and fitting their shapes again, the final mass fits to data for Run 1 and Run 2 are shown in Fig. 4.21. The final fitted yields are:

- **Run 1:** 6620 ± 117 signal, 1.6 ± 0.1 partially reconstructed background, 2887 ± 33 combinatorial background,
- **Run 2:** 32309 ± 278 signal, 60 ± 4 partially reconstructed background, 9920 ± 128 combinatorial background.

Figure 4.21: Fit of $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ invariant mass distributions for Run 1 (left) and Run 2 (right) dataset after the selection.

Figure 4.22: Fit of $m(J/\psi K_S^0)$ invariant mass distributions for Run 2 dataset after the selection, in the three different ranges of z_{vtx} , with (top) $3 < z < 5$ m, (center) $5 < z < 6$ m, (bottom) $6 < z < 8$ m.

Figure 4.23: Helicity frame definition, indicated with Λ rest frame, [117].

The corresponding significances are 68 and 157, with purities of 70% and 76%, respectively.

4.3 Angular fit

After selecting the candidates for the two decay modes under study, the next step is to extract the electric and magnetic dipole moments of the Λ baryon from the angular distribution of the proton. This requires first defining the helicity frame in which the measurement is performed, followed by a detailed description of the fitting strategy. The procedure is then validated using simulated data and the control channel before being applied to the signal sample.

4.3.1 Angular basis

As explained in Chapter 1, the measurement of the electric and magnetic dipole moments relies on the angular distribution of the proton produced in Λ decays. Therefore, the definition of the angular variables is an essential step of the analysis. These angles are defined in the helicity frame, where the polarization is maximal along the direction of the baryon momentum. In particular, the helicity frame is the Λ rest frame constructed from the Λ_b^0 rest frame, as described below and illustrated in Fig. 4.23. Starting from the laboratory frame, we define the normal vector \mathbf{n} to the production plane, which is perpendicular to the plane defined by the incident proton momentum \mathbf{p}_{inc} and the Λ_b^0 momentum $\mathbf{p}_{\Lambda_b^0}$ in the center-of-mass system,

$$\mathbf{n} = \frac{\mathbf{p}_{\text{inc}} \times \mathbf{p}_{\Lambda_b^0}}{|\mathbf{p}_{\text{inc}} \times \mathbf{p}_{\Lambda_b^0}|}. \quad (4.4)$$

To determine \mathbf{p}_{inc} , we consider the beam direction with positive p_z in the LHCb coordinate system. The axes of the Λ rest frame (the helicity frame) are then defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\mathbf{z}}^\Lambda &= \hat{\mathbf{p}}_\Lambda^{\Lambda_b^0}, \\ \hat{\mathbf{y}}^\Lambda &= \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \hat{\mathbf{p}}_\Lambda^{\Lambda_b^0}, \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}^\Lambda &= \hat{\mathbf{y}}^\Lambda \times \hat{\mathbf{z}}^\Lambda.\end{aligned}\tag{4.5}$$

Here, superscripts denote the reference frame, while subscripts indicate the particle being described. For example, $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_\Lambda^{\Lambda_b^0}$ is the unit vector of the Λ momentum in the Λ_b^0 helicity frame. In the Λ rest frame, we compute the helicity angles of the proton, which is also boosted in the Λ_b^0 and then Λ rest frames. The polar angle θ_p is defined between the proton momentum and the $\hat{\mathbf{z}}^\Lambda$ axis:

$$\cos \theta_p = \cos \theta_p^\Lambda = \hat{\mathbf{z}}^\Lambda \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}}_p^\Lambda = \hat{\mathbf{p}}_\Lambda^{\Lambda_b^0} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}}_p^\Lambda.\tag{4.6}$$

The azimuthal angle ϕ_p is given by:

$$\phi_p = \phi_p^\Lambda = \text{atan2}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}^\Lambda \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}}_p^\Lambda, \hat{\mathbf{y}}^\Lambda \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}}_p^\Lambda).\tag{4.7}$$

To ensure that the angular distributions are CP-symmetric for both Λ and $\bar{\Lambda}$ decays, the azimuthal angle is transformed under CP conjugation as:

$$\phi_p \rightarrow -\phi_p.$$

4.3.2 Fitting strategy

The theoretical angular distribution from which we can extract the electric and magnetic factors is described in Eqs. 1.52 and 1.66 and does not account for experimental effects. In particular, detector reconstruction, event selection, and geometrical acceptance introduce modifications to the signal acceptance that must be taken into account. Moreover, as can be seen in the invariant mass distribution after ghost vertex suppression (see Figs A.7, A.8, A.5, A.6), a residual background remains. This must also be taken into consideration in the data fitting procedure. We consider two approaches to handle the background: one used as the nominal method, and the other as an alternative for cross-checking. The nominal method uses the *sPlot* technique to statistically subtract the background via *sWeights* computed from a fit to the invariant mass distribution. In this case, the p.d.f. used in the fit is:

$$p_{s,\text{tot}}(\cos \theta_p, \phi_p, \mathbf{P}) = \frac{p_s(\cos \theta_p, \phi_p, \mathbf{P})\epsilon(\cos \theta_p, \phi_p)}{I(\mathbf{P})},\tag{4.8}$$

where $p_s(\cos \theta_p, \phi_p, \mathbf{P})$ is the theoretical angular distribution of the Λ decay, as defined in Eq. 4.10. The term $\epsilon(\cos \theta_p, \phi_p)$ represents the efficiency, which will be discussed in detail in the following section. The normalization factor $I(\mathbf{P})$ ensures that the p.d.f. is correctly normalized:

$$I(\mathbf{P}) = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 p_s(\cos \theta_p, \phi_p, \mathbf{P})\epsilon(\cos \theta_p, \phi_p) d \cos \theta_p d \phi_p.\tag{4.9}$$

While this formulation requires an explicit model for the efficiency function, we adopt a data-driven approach using a `GBreweighter` algorithm, as will be discussed in the

following. This technique assigns an event-by-event weight that effectively corrects for the efficiency variations. The weighted dataset results in the efficiency corrected distribution, and the angular fit can be performed using only the signal p.d.f. $p_s(\cos\theta_p, \phi_p, \mathbf{P})$, without explicitly including the efficiency term in the fit model.

In the alternative method, the background is not removed using sWeights. Instead, we fit the full data distribution using a composite p.d.f. that includes both signal and background components:

$$p_{tot}(\cos\theta_p, \phi_p, \mathbf{P}) = \frac{p_s(\cos\theta_p, \phi_p, \mathbf{P})\epsilon(\cos\theta_p, \phi_p)}{I(\mathbf{P})} \frac{N_{sig}}{N_{tot}} + p_{bkg}(\cos\theta_p, \phi_p) \frac{N_{bkg}}{N_{tot}}, \quad (4.10)$$

where N_{sig} , N_{bkg} , and N_{tot} are the number of signal, background, and total events, respectively, as obtained from the fit to the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ invariant mass distribution (see Tab. 4.6 and 4.7). The background p.d.f. $p_{bkg}(\cos\theta_p, \phi_p)$ is determined using a kernel density estimate based on events in the upper sideband of the $m(J/\psi\Lambda)$ distribution. Both approaches use an extended maximum likelihood fit implemented using the RooFit toolkit [116]. The negative log likelihood is minimized using the Minuit algorithm. For N observed events with variables $\mathbf{x}_i = (\cos\theta_{p_i}, \phi_{p_i}, \mathbf{P}_i)$, the likelihood function is defined as

$$\mathcal{L} = \prod_{i=1}^N p(\mathbf{x}_i).$$

For the nominal sWeighted fit, substituting the signal component of the p.d.f. ($p_{tot}(x)$), we get

$$\mathcal{L} = \prod_{i=1}^N \frac{p_s(\mathbf{x}_i)\epsilon(\mathbf{x}_i)}{I}.$$

Taking the logarithm of the likelihood yields

$$\ln \mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=1}^N \ln[p_s(\mathbf{x}_i)\epsilon(\mathbf{x}_i)] - \sum_{i=1}^N \ln I.$$

Since the normalization factor I is independent of the event index i , it can be factored out:

$$\ln \mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=1}^N \ln[p_s(\mathbf{x}_i)\epsilon(\mathbf{x}_i)] - N \ln I.$$

4.3.3 Sensitivity studies

Before fitting the real data with the p.d.f. just presented, we need to be sure that it is correctly defined and use it to predict the sensitivity to electromagnetic dipole moments achievable with the available data. This study specifically focuses on measuring the parameters g and d , previously introduced in Eqs. 1.28 and 1.30, respectively. Our goal is to identify the conditions that maximize the sensitivity and to assess the impact of the resolution and acceptance on the fitted values. Additionally, we tested the p.d.f. by fitting the simulation dataset to validate its applicability to the data. For this study, we fixed the parameters at $g = 1.226$ and $d = 0$. Initially, we attempted to fit g and d separately, as well as simultaneously. Since no significant difference in sensitivity is observed, we perform a fit to both the parameters simultaneously. Thanks to the development of the FTF, we expanded the reconstruction of T tracks to include long-lived particles decaying

Figure 4.24: Pseudoexperiment results for the simplest pdf, with constant integrated magnetic field fixed to 4 Tm. The Λ decay position z in the range $5 < z < 8$ m.

from a distance of 3 m from the interaction point. Using pseudoexperiments, we assessed the impact of incorporating these events on the resolution of the dipole moment parameters and also on the initial polarization measurement. The ability to fit g , d , and P_0 simultaneously enables a more comprehensive analysis. Furthermore, it allows us to confirm, using the same dataset employed to measure g and d , that the Λ baryons are fully polarized along the \hat{z} axis in the helicity frame. We begin with a basic probability density function and progressively introduce additional complexities. The details of this process are outlined in the following.

As an initial step, we examine the simplest precession scenario in which Λ baryons travel along the z -axis in the laboratory frame. In this condition, no rotation is required to transition from the laboratory frame to the helicity frame. We assume an initial polarization $P_0 = (0, 0, P_0)$ and a magnetic field $B = (0, B_y, 0)$. For this case, we generated 1000 pseudoexperiments, each containing 10 000 events, following the angular distribution in Eq. 1.52, with polarization described by Eq. 1.51. The parameters used include $\beta = 1$ for each particle, $P_0 = 1$, and $D_y = 4$ Tm. Figure 4.24 presents the distribution of the fitted values for g , along with the corresponding uncertainty distribution. The mean uncertainty provides an estimate of the achievable sensitivity, which in this case is found to be 0.041. To validate the accuracy of our generation and fitting procedure, we also examine the pull distribution, defined as the difference between the fitted value and the generated one, divided by the uncertainty obtained from the fit. The pull distribution is expected to be centered around zero with a standard deviation of 1, in this case the central value and the uncertainty of the fitted parameter can be considered correctly estimated.

Thus, we extend the p.d.f. according to Eq. 1.66 to account for event-by-event rotation, computed using momenta with all possible directions. The results, shown in Fig. 4.25, indicate that this approach achieves a sensitivity comparable to that of the simplest case. This confirms that the inclusion of a per-event rotation matrix does not introduce any significant degradation in sensitivity.

Figure 4.25: Pseudoexperiment with initial momentum direction different from zero in all the directions and constant integrated magnetic field fixed to 4 Tm. The Λ decay position z in the range $5 < z < 8$ m.

To assess whether the obtained sensitivity is reasonable, we compare our results with existing literature, particularly the most precise measurement to date performed at Fermilab, as discussed in Sec. 1.2.4. The sensitivity to the parameter g is expected to scale as

$$\sigma_g \propto \frac{1}{P_0 \sqrt{N}}, \quad (4.11)$$

where N denotes the number of signal events. In the Fermilab experiment, P_0 was 8%, and $N = 3 \times 10^6$, leading to a sensitivity of $\sigma_g = 0.7\%$, consistent with the findings in Eq. 1.68.

Applying the same scaling relation to the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ case, with $P_0 = 100\%$ and $N = 10000$, we estimate a sensitivity of approximately 1%. This is about a factor of four lower than the sensitivity obtained from our pseudoexperiments. The discrepancy arises from the need to account for the effect of the integrated magnetic field in the sensitivity formula. By considering error propagation, it follows that

$$\frac{\sigma_g}{g} \propto \frac{1}{D}, \quad (4.12)$$

where D represents the magnitude of the integrated magnetic field $\mathbf{D} = \int \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{l}$. This relationship is illustrated in Fig. 4.26 (left), where we computed the relative resolution as a function of D . The plot confirms that at $D = 15$ Tm, corresponding to the conditions at Fermilab, a relative precision of approximately 1% is achieved. This agreement validates our simulation results and confirms their reliability.

To further refine the simulation and better approximate real data, we incorporate the full kinematics of the decay. Specifically, we utilized RapidSim [118] to simulate the decay process $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ within the LHCb acceptance. Once the kinematic distributions are generated, we compute the helicity angles and apply an accept-reject method to ensure that their distribution follow our theoretical p.d.f., assuming an initial polarization of $P_0 = (0, 0, 1)$. We then fit the generated dataset using the same p.d.f. employed for the generation and repeat the process for 500 pseudoexperiments. The results show an increase in the uncertainty on the g and d factors as expected due to the different kinematics of each decay, as shown in Fig. 4.27.

Figure 4.26: (Left) Relative precision on g as a function of the integrated magnetic field D . (Right) Integrated field as a function of the Λ flight length in the LHCb detector.

Figure 4.27: 500 pseudoexperiments for general initial momentum direction, decay generated with RapidSim and constant integrated magnetic field fixed to 4 Tm. The Λ decay position z in the range $5 < z < 8$ m.

Figure 4.28: 110 pseudoexperiments for general initial momentum direction, decay generated with RapidSim, integrated magnetic field computed event-per-event from the particle flight length and LHCb magnetic field map. The Λ decay position z in the range $5 < z < 8$ m.

Next, we assess the impact of the magnetic field on our measurements. Initially, we assumed a constant integrated magnetic field of 4 Tm, representing the maximum field strength that Λ baryons can experience. However, in practice, this maximum field is not always reached, as Λ baryons might decay before traversing the entire magnet and we need to take into account event-per-event the decay position of the Λ baryon. As illustrated in Fig. 4.26 (right), the integrated magnetic field varies with the decay length l . For instance, for Λ baryons decaying from a starting point of 5 m, a fraction of them will experience a lower integrated magnetic field than the maximum of 4 Tm. To properly account for the Λ decay length, we constructed a p.d.f. that incorporates event-by-event variations in both the integrated magnetic field and the momentum of the Λ baryons. The results of these simulations, presented in Fig. 4.28, show an approximate 30% increase in uncertainty. This worsening is consistent with expectations, given that a substantial portion of the dataset corresponds to regions with lower integrated magnetic fields. At this stage, the most comprehensive scenario has been considered for the signal. Allowing the initial polarization to float did not affect the sensitivity on g and d , while an achievable precision of 0.02 was found for the initial polarization components, as shown in Fig. 4.29.

Following the development of the FTF algorithm, we start to include Λ baryons decaying from as early as 3 m. Therefore, we repeat the pseudoexperiments, each containing 25000 events with Λ decaying between 3 and 8 m from the interaction point, as illustrated in Fig. 4.30. The increase in signal yield was estimated based on simulations after applying the preselection criteria and then confirmed by the fit on data. The pri-

Figure 4.29: Initial polarization obtained from pseudoexperiments for general initial momentum direction, decay generated with RapidSim, integrated magnetic field computed event-per-event from the particle flight length and LHCb magnetic field map. For each pseudoexperiment, 10000 events are considered, with Λ decay position z in the range $5 < z < 8$ m.

mary improvement is observed in the sensitivity of P_0 , whose uncertainty is reduced by more than 60%. In contrast, the sensitivity on the dipole moment parameters improves by 10%, as the Λ baryons decaying at smaller z experience smaller precession in the magnetic field and, therefore, contribute less to the determination of the dipole moments.

Having established the achievable sensitivity with only signal events, we proceed to evaluate the impact of resolution effects on the measurements of g and d , focusing primarily on angular resolution and the uncertainty introduced by the integrated magnetic field. To account for angular resolution effects, we apply a smearing to the magnitude and direction of the pion and proton momenta as generated by RapidSim. The smearing is derived from the residual distributions obtained from full simulation and modeled using Crystal Ball functions fitted to these residuals. After applying the smearing to the momenta, all kinematic variables, including the helicity angles, are recalculated accordingly. Fitting the smeared dataset directly with the theoretical signal p.d.f. introduced a noticeable bias, highlighting the necessity to account for resolution effects in the analysis. To correct for this, we generate two large datasets of one million events each—one using the true kinematic variables and the other using the smeared ones. We then employ a `GBreweighter` to map the smeared angular distribution to match the true distribution. Applying this reweighting procedure to each pseudoexperiment allows the pull distributions to become more similar to a standard normal distribution, indicating that angular resolution effects must be included as part of the acceptance correction. Anyway, the mean of the pull is not yet compatible with zero and a bias of -0.4 on P_{0z} and -1.5 on g is still present, see Fig. 4.31. After many dedicated studies it seems that this residual bias is due to resolution introduced in the precession part of the p.d.f., which is not taken into account with the angular correction applied with the `GBreweighter`. We are further investigating to solve this issue. The smearing is based only on the residuals of well-reconstructed `Good` vertices. To extend the study, the impact of `Ghost` events is going to be incorporated by varying the relative contribution of `Good` and `Ghost` categories in the resolution function for the smearing. This will enable us to evaluate the optimal selection threshold on the `Ghost` GNN output to minimize resolution-induced biases. For the time being, we introduce a systematic error induced by the bias due to the not perfect description of the angular resolution in the p.d.f..

A new strategy has been developed to address the bias observed in the resolution study. Instead of neglecting resolution effects, the p.d.f. explicitly incorporates them by convolving the theoretical distribution, $f(\cos\theta', \phi')$, previously used in all fits, with Gaussian smearing functions, $G(x; \sigma)$, applied to each helicity angle:

$$f_{\text{conv}}(\cos\theta, \phi) = \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(\cos\theta', \phi') G(\cos\theta - \cos\theta'; \sigma_{\theta}) G(\phi - \phi'; \sigma_{\phi}) d(\cos\theta') d\phi', \quad (4.13)$$

$$G(x; \sigma) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}\right). \quad (4.14)$$

Pseudoexperiments are generated directly from this modified distribution, f_{conv} , and subsequently fitted with the same model. As a validation step, small Gaussian widths are first used to reproduce the results obtained without resolution effects. Next, constant resolution values are assumed for all events, adopting conservative choices of $\sigma = 0.15$ for $\cos\theta$ and $\sigma = 0.5$ for ϕ . Finally, the resolution dependence on both the helicity angles and the z coordinate of the Λ vertex is taken into account, as illustrated in Figs. 3.33–3.38. In this configuration, the Gaussian widths are determined on an event-by-event basis. As expected, the sensitivity improves when moving from constant to event-by-event

Figure 4.30: Results of the pseudoexperiments for general initial momentum direction, decay generated with RapidSim, integrated magnetic field computed event-per-event from the particle flight length and LHCb magnetic field map. For each pseudoexperiment, 25000 events are considered, with Λ decay position z in the range $3 < z < 8$ m.

Figure 4.31: Results of the pseudoexperiments for general initial momentum direction, decay generated with RapidSim, integrated magnetic field computed event-per-event from the particle flight length and LHCb magnetic field map, using reconstructed momenta and introducing angular resolution effect. For each pseudoexperiment, 25000 events are considered, with Λ decay position z in the range $3 < z < 8$ m.

resolutions. The study has been performed both with only **Good** events and without applying the **Ghost** removal. The results of the pseudoexperiments, shown in Fig. 4.32, confirm that the biases are no longer present. We conclude that incorporating angular resolution directly into the p.d.f. is essential.

Next, we evaluate the impact of the flight length resolution, which is influenced by the endvertex position resolution of the Λ baryon. This effect was previously detailed in Fig. 3.40. To model this, we use a **Crystal Ball** function to parameterize the **Good** distribution while disregarding the **Ghost** contribution, assuming its successful removal. We parameterize the resolution across different ranges of the z vertex coordinate. As shown in Fig. 4.33 (left), the variations are minimal. Therefore, we adopt the most conservative resolution for the entire dataset. Using this parameterization, we applied a smearing to the z -position of the Λ endvertex by sampling random values from the modeled distribution. Subsequently, we recompute the integrated magnetic field, on which the smearing effects is propagated, see Fig. 4.33 (right), and generate new events according to the p.d.f. evaluated with the smeared value of the integrated magnetic field. The fitting procedure is carried out without incorporating a resolution function in the p.d.f.. The results, summarized in Fig. 4.34, demonstrate that the pull distributions remain consistent with a normal distribution, while the sensitivity shows only a negligible deterioration. This confirms that adding a resolution function to the p.d.f. is unnecessary, as it does not significantly impact the results. Then we introduce the effect of having the **Ghost** contribution, to understand their impact on the measurement. No change is observed in the sensitivity of the initial polarization, neither on the gyroelectromagnetic factors, see Fig. 4.35.

After establishing the sensitivity through the simulation of the signal distribution, the final step is to evaluate the impact of the background. By selecting **sWeighted** data representing the background under the peak, we parameterize the angular distribution using a **RooKeysPdf**, as pictured in Fig. 4.36. This model is then incorporated into the simulation alongside the signal p.d.f., modifying the relative fraction accordingly. The results reveal that the presence of background degrades the sensitivity of the electromagnetic dipole moment measurements. Consequently, we leverage this simulation to determine the optimal BDT cut to apply to the data, following the selection of a set of hyperparameter points. We also used these simulation to understand that the significance is the best FoM to have the best sensitivity to the dipole moments.

To complement this study with a non-phase-space sample, we proceed with the independent generation of a simulated dataset that incorporates the effects of an initial polarization, with $\mathbf{P}_0 = (0,0,-1)$, following the polarization model available in **EventGen**. This allows us to validate the method under more realistic signal conditions. The generated dataset has 88 000 signal events. The fit results, shown in Fig. 4.37, confirm that the extracted values are consistent with the expected ones, validating the reliability of the p.d.f. with an initial polarization different from zero. The results of the fit are in fact compatible within less than 2σ with the generated values of the polarization.

4.3.4 Signal reconstruction efficiency

Since the simulation accurately reflects the data thanks to the application of the reweighting procedure, we can now use the simulated dataset to evaluate the reconstruction efficiency, defined as

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\text{acc}} \cdot \epsilon_{\text{reco}} \cdot \epsilon_{\text{trigg}} \cdot \epsilon_{\text{sel}} = \frac{N_{\text{acc}}}{N_{\text{tot}}} \cdot \frac{N_{\text{reco}}}{N_{\text{acc}}} \cdot \frac{N_{\text{trigg}}}{N_{\text{reco}}} \cdot \frac{N_{\text{sel}}}{N_{\text{trigg}}}, \quad (4.15)$$

Figure 4.32: Results of the pseudoexperiments for general initial momentum direction, decay generated with RapidSim, integrated magnetic field computed event-per-event from the particle flight length and LHCb magnetic field map. Resolution effect introduced using the theoretical p.d.f. convoluted with Gaussian resolution functions for both generation and fitting. For each pseudoexperiment, 25000 events are considered, with Λ decay position z in the range $3 < z < 8$ m.

Figure 4.33: (Left) residual distribution parametrization of vertex z position from FTF algorithm in different z regions, considering only Good events. (Right) effect of the z vertex smearing on the integrated magnetic field along the y direction.

where N_{tot} represents the initial number of generated signal events, N_{acc} is the number of events within the experimental acceptance, N_{reco} is the number of successfully reconstructed events, N_{trigg} refers to those events passing the trigger requirements, and N_{sel} corresponds to the events that meet the final offline selection criteria. Since signal events are generated uniformly in the available phase space, the distribution of reconstructed events across this space becomes directly proportional to the total efficiency.

To determine the efficiency as a function of the angular variables, we employ a multivariate algorithm that assigns a weight to each event and shapes the observed distribution after reconstruction and selection to the uniform phase-space distribution. The algorithm used is the `GBReweighter` from the `hep_ml` Python package [114]. Once trained, this model serves as a functional representation of the efficiency: given an input dataset, it outputs the corresponding efficiency as event-per-event weight. It has been considered since it takes into account the correlations between the reweighting variables. Figure 4.38 shows the helicity angle distributions before and after the application of the full selection. After applying the weights produced by the `GBReweighter`, the reweighted distributions closely match the post-selection shapes. In the case of the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0 (\rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^-)$ decays, an additional fiducial cut of $|\cos \theta_\pi| < 0.7$ is applied to exclude poorly populated regions. Without this cut, the `GBReweighter` would not be able to reliably assign weights due to limited statistics at the edges.

4.4 Null test of polarization on the control channel

The control channel $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0 (\rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^-)$ provides a valuable validation of the fitting strategy. Since the K_S^0 meson is a pseudoscalar, it carries no intrinsic polarization, thus the angular fit should yield parameters consistent with zero.

As an initial test, we split the simulated sample of $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0 (\rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^-)$ decays randomly into two halves. The first half is used to train the `GBReweighter` model to learn the efficiency, and the second half is used to evaluate this efficiency. This second subset is then used in a null test, where we fit the angular distribution using the p.d.f. defined in Eq. 4.10. The fitted distribution is shown in Fig. 4.39. The extracted values of the initial polarization from the control channel fit are:

$$P_{0x} = 0.020 \pm 0.013, \quad P_{0y} = 0.010 \pm 0.013, \quad P_{0z} = 0.004 \pm 0.015.$$

Figure 4.34: Results of the pseudoexperiments for general initial momentum direction, decay generated with RapidSim, integrated magnetic field computed event-per-event from the particle flight length and LHCb magnetic field map, smearing the z vertex position, with only Good events. In each pseudoexperiment, 25000 events are considered, with Λ decay position z in the range $3 < z < 8$ m.

Figure 4.35: Results of the pseudoexperiments for general initial momentum direction, decay generated with RapidSim, integrated magnetic field computed event-per-event from the particle flight length and LHCb magnetic field map, smearing the z vertex position, with Good and Ghost events. In each pseudoexperiment, 25000 events are considered, with Λ decay position z in the range $3 < z < 8$ m.

Figure 4.36: Parametrization of the angular distributions of the background with `RoKeysPdf` for the proton helicity angles, $\cos \theta_p$ and ϕ_p .

Figure 4.37: Fit to privately generated simulation with polarization model, $P_0 = (0,0,1)$.

Figure 4.38: Efficiency estimation for $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ (top) and $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ (bottom) decays obtained comparing the helicity angles distribution of one pion (top) and proton (bottom) of the final state before (raw MC) and after the selection (target) in simulation. After the GBReweighter, the first matches the latter (weighted MC).

Figure 4.39: Helicity angles fit on phase space simulation of $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decay.

These results are consistent with zero, as expected, providing a first validation of the fitting procedure. The gyromagnetic and gyroelectric factors g and d can also be floated in the fit; however, given the absence of initial polarization, the sensitivity to these parameters is poor. Consequently, the fit yields values consistent with zero but with large associated uncertainties.

Following this validation, the measurement is extended to $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0 (\rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^-)$ decays reconstructed on data. The efficiency is again estimated using the `GBRweighter` method, trained on the simulation and applied directly to the data. Each event is corrected by the efficiency, and the angular distribution is fitted using the `sWeighted` dataset. The resulting fit is shown in Fig. 4.40, and the extracted initial polarization components are:

$$P_{0x} = -0.003 \pm 0.009, \quad P_{0y} = 0.003 \pm 0.009, \quad P_{0z} = -0.010 \pm 0.010.$$

Figure 4.40: Angular fit to `sWeighted` data for the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ control channel.

These results are again compatible with zero polarization, in agreement with theoretical expectations for the control channel. This provides a strong consistency check and further validation of the full fitting procedure, including efficiency correction and background subtraction.

4.5 Measurement of Λ dipole moments in $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays

As for the control sample, we start fitting the simulated sample to have an additional check of the fitting procedure. The signal decays are generated according to phase-space distributions, meaning that no polarization model has been included. For this reason we can do another null test of the polarization on this sample. We consider only the Good events for this test and we divide the sample in two parts: one has 29 000 events, as the selected candidates in Run 1 and Run 2 data, the second dataset is the remaining MC simulation, with 1 million events. The efficiency is estimated training the `GBreweighter` on the second sample and matching it to the distribution of simulated signal events before applying any selection step. Then we apply the algorithm to the 29 000 signal decays of the dataset and we get an estimation of the efficiency. At this point we fit this dataset corrected with the efficiency and we find results for P_0 compatible with zero, as expected, see Fig. 4.41:

$$P_{0x} = 0.002 \pm 0.014, \quad P_{0y} = 0.000 \pm 0.014, \quad P_{0z} = 0.001 \pm 0.015.$$

We repeat this procedure considering the two categories of Good and Ghost events. Both in the training and test set we keep the fraction of the two categories equal to 30%. Again getting results compatible with zero, see Fig. 4.42,

$$P_{0x} = -0.019 \pm 0.014, \quad P_{0y} = -0.019 \pm 0.014, \quad P_{0z} = 0.018 \pm 0.015.$$

The sensitivity to the polarization component is actually comparable to what predicted by the pseudoexperiments. The efficiency estimation performed from the simulation fit can be directly used for data correction as well, assuming simulation describe well data and therefore the fraction of Ghost is the same.

The effect of Ghost decays on the results has to be further investigated to determine the optimal requirement of the Ghost GNN. We first perform a measurement on data without removing any Ghost, see Fig. 4.43. The fit result on data for the initial polarization is:

$$P_{0x} = XXX \pm 0.02, \quad P_{0y} = XXX \pm 0.02, \quad P_{0z} = XXX \pm 0.02.$$

Simultaneously, we extract the gyroelectric and gyromagnetic factors,

$$g = XXX \pm 0.06, \quad d = XXX \pm 0.06,$$

where the central values remain blind for this document, due to the LHCb policy on the results publication. The dipole moment sensitivity agrees with that expected from the pseudoexperiments studies.

While the optimal cut to remove the Ghost has to be determined, we apply a cut that leave around 10% of Ghost events and we repeat the fit on data. This choice is taken because simulation studies show that the residual resolution is symmetric when the Ghost contribution is kept at that level, see Fig 4.14. The signal yield, integrated over the z coordinate from 3 to 8 m and in 3σ window centered on the Λ_b^0 peak, are 1681 ± 88 and 6695 ± 141 for Run 1 and Run 2, respectively. The combinatorial background yields to 1792 ± 23 and 3644 ± 33 , while the $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ peaking background contributes with 225 ± 19 and 841 ± 30 candidates. This condition is a conservative scenario, since the statistics is reduced to about one-third of the candidates selected without any Ghost removal. The simultaneous angular fit results on Run 1 and Run 2 data are reported in Fig. 4.44, for the initial polarization,

$$P_{0x} = XXX \pm 0.04, \quad P_{0y} = XXX \pm 0.04, \quad P_{0z} = XXX \pm 0.03,$$

Figure 4.41: (Top) Efficiency estimation for Good events in simulation for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays. (Bottom) Fit to 29 000 signal decays in simulation, with only Good events.

Figure 4.42: Fit to 29 000 signal decays in simulation, with Good and Ghost events.

Figure 4.43: Fit to signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decays reconstructed using Run 1 and Run 2 data, with blind central values.

Figure 4.44: Fit to signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays reconstructed using Run 1 and Run 2 data with 10% of Ghost events, with blind central values.

while for the gyroelectric and gyromagnetic factors,

$$g = XXX \pm 0.1, \quad d = XXX \pm 0.1,$$

The statistical error increases due to the lower statistics left after the Ghost GNN requirement.

The measurement just presented includes Λ and $\bar{\Lambda}$ baryons together, to perform a test of CPT symmetry. We now proceed separating decays and anti-decays. In this case, we use a different value of α : for Λ decays $\alpha_- = 0.746 \pm 0.008$ and for the $\bar{\Lambda}$ decays $\alpha_+ = -0.758 \pm 0.005$ [16]. We divide the data and perform the background subtraction and acceptance estimation separately, the $m(J/\psi \Lambda)$ invariant mass fits are reported in Appendix, shown in Figs. A.5, A.6, A.7 and A.8, and the fit results are in Tables A.1, A.2, A.3, A.4. The results obtained from the angular fit showed in Fig. 4.45 are:

$$g = XXX \pm 0.2, \quad d = XXX \pm 0.2,$$

$$\bar{g} = XXX \pm 0.2, \quad \bar{d} = XXX \pm 0.2,$$

for the initial polarization in both cases the fit result are:

$$P_{0x} = XXX \pm 0.06, \quad P_{0y} = XXX \pm 0.06, \quad P_{0z} = XXX \pm 0.05.$$

As expected, since the two dataset have the same statistics, the sensitivity reached are compatible.

4.5.1 Most recent developments

In the treatment of detector effects, two strategies can be followed. A traditional approach is to correct the data directly by applying event-by-event weights derived from the efficiency as a function of the reconstructed helicity angles, as done in the previous reported results. This method is often adequate because, in most cases, the angular resolution is sufficiently good that the difference between reconstructed and true angles can be neglected. However, for T tracks the resolution is not negligible, and applying the correction at the reconstructed level could lead to a systematic bias. For this reason, in the latest updates the acceptance is incorporated directly into the p.d.f.. The efficiency is parametrised as a function of the theoretical helicity angles and multiplied with the underlying angular distribution at truth level. The resulting function is then convoluted with the angular resolution, yielding a prediction for the reconstructed variables. The new p.d.f considered is therefore:

$$f(\cos \theta, \phi) = \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \epsilon(\cos \theta', \phi') f(\cos \theta', \phi') G(\cos \theta - \cos \theta'; \sigma_{\theta}) G(\phi - \phi'; \sigma_{\phi}) d(\cos \theta') d\phi', \quad (4.16)$$

In this way the model correctly accounts simultaneously for both acceptance and resolution effects, ensuring that the fitted p.d.f. describes what is actually observed in data. The integration over the theoretical helicity angles is computed numerically, since the presence of the acceptance factor does not allow to compute an analytical integration. The bins on which the convolution integrals are computed are the same on which the efficiency $\epsilon(\cos \theta', \phi')$ is defined. To determine the efficiency map we still use the `GBRweighter` but with the opposite target: the distribution after the selection. We apply it to theoretical bins in the helicity angles domain, finding the plot in Fig. 4.46. To parametrize the resolution function we simultaneously fit the theoretical angle with the residual, i.g. $(\cos \theta'; \cos \theta - \cos \theta')$ with the sum of three Gaussians. We realized that the Gaussians are not describing well the behavior at the border, so it was understood that the use of *truncated Gaussians* for the $\cos \theta$ resolution was needed. They are defined as Gaussians restricted to the physical interval $[-1, 1]$ and normalized accordingly, so that their integral over the allowed domain is unity. Explicitly, the truncated Gaussian distribution for a variable $x = \cos \theta$ with mean μ and width σ is given by

$$G_T(x | \mu, \sigma) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{\exp\left[-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right]}{\Phi\left(\frac{1-\mu}{\sigma}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{-1-\mu}{\sigma}\right)}, & -1 \leq x \leq 1, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (4.17)$$

where $\Phi(z)$ denotes the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution. This modification ensures that the probability density does not extend outside the physical region of $\cos \theta$, where the standard Gaussian would otherwise assign non-zero probability. The need for such a treatment arises because the angular variable $\cos \theta$ is bounded, and events close to the kinematic limits ($\cos \theta \approx \pm 1$) are otherwise distorted by the artificial leakage of the Gaussian tail beyond the boundary. By truncating the resolution model, the p.d.f. correctly accounts for the finite domain and provides a faithful description of the data, particularly in the regions where the acceptance is steep and the

Figure 4.45: Fit to to signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays reconstructed using Run 1 and Run 2 data with 10% of Ghost events, with blind central values. (Top) for Λ baryons, (bottom) $\bar{\Lambda}$ antibaryons.

Figure 4.46: Acceptance map, with 80x80 bins.

Figure 4.47: Resolution functions fit on Good simulations, projected on the residuals, (left) for $\cos\theta$, (right) for ϕ .

resolution smearing plays a non-negligible role. For the azimuthal angle ϕ , which is a periodic variable defined in the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$, a different treatment is required because standard Gaussians do not account for the circular nature of the variable. A standard Gaussian would artificially split probability near the boundaries at $-\pi$ and π , leading to distortions in the resolution. To address this, a *wrapped Gaussian* is used. A wrapped Gaussian is obtained by summing the standard Gaussian over all its 2π -shifted images, effectively “wrapping” the distribution around the circle

$$G_{wrap}(\phi | \mu, \sigma) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{(\phi - \mu + 2\pi k)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right], \quad \phi \in [-\pi, \pi]. \quad (4.18)$$

This ensures that the resolution function respects the periodicity of ϕ , assigning the correct probability density near the boundaries and avoiding artificial discontinuities. In practice, the sum converges quickly because the Gaussian tails become negligible for sufficiently large $|k|$. The evaluation of the resolution and efficiency is computed on a subset of the polarized MC sample and then the remaining part of the sample is used to fit the initial polarization with Eq. 4.16. Another aspect that became clearer is the contribution of the Ghost. Since the resolutions of Good and Ghost differ, they must be described with distinct resolution functions. To address this, we separate the two classes

Figure 4.48: Fit to simulation, Good events selected with the true tag.

in simulations using the true tag and fit them independently, with resolution functions and acceptances determined for each case. The most challenging part is modeling the Ghost resolution in ϕ , which cannot be accurately parametrized with a sum of wrapped Gaussians or any standard functional form. When only Good events are selected, the fit shown in Fig. 4.48 yields

$$P_{0x} = -0.025 \pm 0.015, \quad P_{0y} = 0.022 \pm 0.015, \quad P_{0z} = -1.02 \pm 0.13.$$

When only Ghost events are selected, the fit shown in Fig. 4.49 yields

$$P_{0x} = -0.08 \pm 0.03, \quad P_{0y} = 0.05 \pm 0.03, \quad P_{0z} = -0.8 \pm 0.02.$$

When the two samples are combined and fitted simultaneously, the misdescription of the Ghost resolution biases the measurement. The fitted distributions obtained using the true tag to separate the two categories are shown in Fig. 4.50, yielding the following initial polarization values

$$P_{0x} = -0.039 \pm 0.019, \quad P_{0y} = 0.036 \pm 0.019, \quad P_{0z} = -1.00 \pm 0.12.$$

It is evident that the agreement with the generated polarization values improves when only the Good class is considered, also the error is lower even if the dataset reduces by a 30%. The fit to the Ghost shows that we cannot rely on these events to extract the

Figure 4.49: Fit to simulation, Ghost events selected with the true tag.

Figure 4.50: Simultaneous fit to Good and Ghost simulated events, tagged with true tag.

Figure 4.51: Fit to simulation, Good events selected with GNN output.

physics parameters. The discrepancy becomes even more important when using the GNN output to separate the classes. For instance, requiring a GNN score > 0.75 , the simultaneous fit to Good and Ghost events gives

$$P_{0x} = -0.44 \pm 0.19, \quad P_{0y} = 0.41 \pm 0.019, \quad P_{0z} = -0.991 \pm 0.012,$$

while selecting only Good events with the same GNN requirement yields, the fit is showed in Fig.

$$P_{0x} = -0.03 \pm 0.02, \quad P_{0y} = 0.01 \pm 0.02, \quad P_{0z} = -0.98 \pm 0.017.$$

We therefore conclude that the measurement should be performed exclusively on Good events, since badly reconstructed Ghost could induce a bias in the fitted parameters. This is straightforward in simulations, where the true tag is available, while in data the separation relies on the Ghost GNN output. A first measurement on data has been performed using a subsample of the complete dataset, unblinding the initial polarization. The fit, reported in Fig. 4.52 results in the following results

$$g = XXX \pm 0.4, \quad d = XXX \pm 0.4,$$

$$P_{0x} = -0.06 \pm 0.08, \quad P_{0y} = -0.07 \pm 0.08, \quad P_{0z} = -0.98 \pm 0.04.$$

Figure 4.52: Fit to data, Good with GNN selection.

The error are large because only a subset of the full Run 1 and Run 2 has been considered. The result shows a compatibility with the expected initial polarization giving a good starting point for the final fit that will be performed to the full dataset to extract the EDM and MDM measurements.

4.6 Systematic uncertainties

Since the measurement is statistically limited, the systematic uncertainties are expected to be smaller with respect to the statistical one. The identified systematic uncertainties which mostly affect the Λ polarization and the dipole moments measurements are related to:

- the acceptance modeling;
- the angular resolution;
- the effect of Ghost events;
- the effect of the integrated magnetic field evaluation;
- the assumed value of the α parameter (0.746 ± 0.008 [16]) in the fit;
- the background;
- the limited size of the simulation sample;
- the discrepancy between MC sample and signal in data.

4.6.1 Acceptance modeling

The modeling of the acceptance is primarily performed using the `GBreweighter` algorithm, as previously described. To assess the systematic uncertainty associated with this modeling choice, an alternative method is implemented. Specifically, a two-dimensional histogram is constructed using the two helicity angles. For each bin, the acceptance is computed as the ratio between the number of generated events before selection and the number of reconstructed events that pass the full selection. This yields a binned acceptance map that parametrizes the detector and reconstruction efficiency across the angular phase space. The two-dimensional grid used for this purpose consists of 30×30 bins. Other binning schemes were tested to evaluate bin-size dependence, but no significant variation in the resulting uncertainties was observed, confirming the robustness of the binning choice.

To estimate the systematic uncertainty associated with the acceptance, it is important to separate this effect from that of the angular resolution. As previously discussed, the angular resolution introduces a bias in the pseudoexperiments. For this reason, we currently cannot rely on pseudoexperiments to evaluate the acceptance-related uncertainty. Instead, a data-driven approach is adopted for the estimation. We fit the data using the alternative 2D histogram-based acceptance correction instead of the nominal `GBreweighter` model. The two-dimensional acceptance map is computed on the full signal simulation (Fig. 4.53) and then applied to real data. The average statistical uncertainties from the fit are compared between the two methods, as well as the central values. The systematic uncertainty is defined as the maximum between difference in

Figure 4.53: Acceptance 2-dimensional histogram computed on the simulated $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ decay sample.

quadrature between the mean uncertainties obtained with each method, and the difference of the central values (bias):

$$\sigma_{\text{syst}} = \max\{\text{bias}, \sqrt{|\sigma_{\text{GBreweighter}}^2 - \sigma_{\text{histogram}}^2|}\}.$$

The results of the two approaches show a negligible bias of the central values. The extracted errors are $\sigma_{\text{GBreweighter}} = 0.012$ and $\sigma_{\text{histogram}} = 0.011$ for the polarization component, leading to a $\sigma_{\text{syst}} = 0.005$. For both the gyroelectric and gyromagnetic factors, $\sigma_{\text{GBreweighter}} = 0.043$ and $\sigma_{\text{histogram}} = 0.032$, which result in $\sigma_{\text{syst}} = 0.03$. These values are assigned as systematic uncertainties associated with the acceptance modeling approach.

4.6.2 Angular resolution

To evaluate the systematic uncertainty associated with angular resolution effects, the pseudoexperiments previously described (Fig. 4.31) are compared to the case without the resolution smearing (Fig. 4.30). As already mentioned, the distribution of pull values in the smeared case exhibits a mean different from zero, indicating the presence of a bias in the parameter estimation introduced by the angular smearing. Since a complete resolution of the bias in the presence of angular precession is still under investigation, a conservative approach is adopted. A systematic uncertainty is assigned equal to the product of the observed pull bias and the corresponding statistical uncertainty. This ensures that any unresolved effects linked to angular resolution are properly accounted for in the total uncertainty estimation. Interestingly, this bias disappears when the parameter g is artificially set to zero in the p.d.f.. This behavior suggests that the angular precession term in the p.d.f., governed by the magnetic dipole interaction, is the main source of the observed bias. The assigned systematic uncertainty on g is equal to 0.1, while on the initial polarization z coordinate is 0.005. This estimated systematic uncertainty is conservative and preliminary, further study is in progress to correct the bias and therefore this uncertainty will reduce in the future. Neither the gyroelectric factor

nor the P_{0x} and P_{0y} components of the initial polarization show any bias, therefore no systematic is added.

4.6.3 Ghost vertices

The resolution effects observed in pseudoexperiments obtained using only Good events already exhibit a bias. A data-driven approach is adopted to estimate the potential systematic uncertainty associated with Ghost contamination. This method involves performing the full fit on signal candidates in data without applying any selection cut on the Ghost classifier (see Fig. 4.43), and comparing the resulting statistical uncertainty and mean values with that obtained from the fit on data after applying the Ghost GNN requirement that leaves a contribution of only 10% of Ghost (see Fig. 4.44). The maximum between the central values and the difference in quadrature between the two uncertainties is taken as an estimate of the systematic uncertainty due to the presence of Ghost events. The estimated systematic uncertainty attributed to the Ghost contribution is found to be 0.03 on both g and d factors and 0.01 on the initial polarization components. It is important to note that, once the pseudoexperiments with the resolution will be available, this estimation will be repeated with pseudoexperiments comparing the cases with different contributions of Ghost.

4.6.4 Integrated magnetic field

As discussed earlier in 2.2.4, the relative uncertainty on the LHCb magnetic field map is 4×10^{-4} . To quantify the impact of this uncertainty, 100 pseudoexperiments are generated in which the nominal magnetic field is smeared event-by-event with a Gaussian of width $\sigma_B/B = 4 \times 10^{-4}$. Each pseudo-experiment is then fitted with the full signal p.d.f. and compared with an otherwise identical ensemble that uses the unmodified field values. The resulting estimates of the g and d factors, as well as the initial polarization components, are statistically consistent, indicating that the global field normalization uncertainty alone is negligible. Because the p.d.f. contains the magnetic field integrated along the flight path of the Λ baryon, the resolution on the production and decay vertices must also be considered. Previous studies in this thesis show that the z coordinate of the Λ decay vertex has the largest uncertainty. The pseudoexperiments taking into account the resolution on Λ z vertex (Fig. 4.35) are compared to the ones without the resolution (Fig. 4.30). The parameter estimates obtained with and without the z smearing are compared. The systematic uncertainty is assigned

$$\sigma_{\text{syst}} = \max\{\text{bias}, \sqrt{|\sigma_{\text{smear}}^2 - \sigma_{\text{true}}^2|}\}.$$

The result for g and d is 0.01, while for the initial polarization it is negligible, lower than 10^{-4} .

4.6.5 Decay asymmetry parameter

Another potential source of systematic uncertainty arises from the experimental uncertainty in the value of the decay asymmetry parameter α . The current world average, based on experimental measurements, is $\alpha = 0.746 \pm 0.008$ [16]. To evaluate the impact of this uncertainty, pseudoexperiments are generated using $\alpha^- = \alpha - 1\sigma = 0.738$, employing true kinematic information, meaning without applying detector resolution effects, as resolution is not relevant for this specific check. The entire procedure is then repeated using α shifted by $+1\sigma$ from the central value, $\alpha^+ = 0.754$. The systematic

uncertainty is estimated by computing the semi difference of the fitted parameters (r) in the two approaches. Specifically,

$$\sigma(r)_{\text{syst}, \alpha} = \frac{|r_{\alpha^-} - r_{\alpha^+}|}{2}.$$

The result shows that the effect is negligible within the statistical precision of the analysis, we find 0.001 for d , while for g and for the initial polarization the uncertainty is lower than the statistical one. Therefore, no additional systematic uncertainty is assigned due to the uncertainty on the α parameter.

4.6.6 Background

To estimate the impact of the background on the measurement, the signal-to-background ratio is varied in pseudoexperiments. Instead of relying on the significance-based selection threshold, an alternative figure of merit, defined as the product of significance and purity, is used to define a new working point. The corresponding signal and background yields are extracted and used to generate a new ensemble of pseudoexperiments. The difference in sensitivity to the parameters is then quantified by comparing the statistical uncertainties and the central values difference (*bias*) obtained in the two configurations, we then consider the maximum between the two,

$$\sigma_{\text{syst}} = \max\{\text{bias}, \sqrt{|\sigma_{\text{Sig}}^2 - \sigma_{\text{Sig}^* \text{pur}}^2|}\}.$$

We consider Run 2 data, with the full range on z , in the nominal case the signal yield is 19 000 candidates with a purity of 62%, the alternative case, obtained optimizing significance times purity gives 15 700 signal candidates with a purity of 72%. The resulting change in sensitivity to the gyroelectric and gyromagnetic factors is found to be 0.01 and assigned as systematic uncertainty. The change in sensitivity for the initial polarization components is 0.004.

4.6.7 Data - simulation discrepancy

Another potential source of systematic uncertainty originates from residual discrepancies between data and MC simulation. Although a data-driven approach is employed to mitigate such effects, the modeling may still introduce a systematic bias, particularly in the acceptance corrections. To quantify this uncertainty, an alternative reweighting scheme is used in place of the nominal one. Specifically, two modifications are introduced: first, the number of input variables used in the `GBreweighter` is changed; second, the hyperparameters of the reweighting algorithm are allowed to float. These changes are intended to probe the sensitivity of the results to different configurations of the reweighting model. The impact of these variations is evaluated by repeating the full fit on data with the modified reweighting and comparing the outcome to the nominal fit. These alternative approaches will be tested in the future to determine this effect. To estimate the maximal possible effect, a brute-force approach can be tested as well: the efficiency is computed using MC without applying any weights, providing a conservative upper bound on the discrepancy-induced uncertainty. The resulting variations in the extracted observables are interpreted as systematic uncertainties due to imperfect data–MC agreement in the modeling of kinematic and detector-related variables.

4.6.8 Limited size of the simulation sample

An additional systematic uncertainty to be considered, arises from the limited number of MC simulated events used to model the detector acceptance. Due to the finite sample size, statistical fluctuations in the acceptance function can propagate into the measurement of physical observables. The method involves splitting the available simulation sample into two statistically independent halves of equal size. Each half is used to estimate the acceptance function independently, and two separate sets of pseudo-experiments are performed using these estimates. The systematic uncertainty is then defined as half the difference in the fitted parameter values obtained from the two sets. Since the available simulation dataset is twice the size used in each half sample, the final systematic uncertainty is scaled by a factor of $1/\sqrt{2}$ to account for the increased statistical power. This method provides a robust estimate of the uncertainty introduced by MC statistical limitations. Although it has not yet been carried out in this thesis, it is part of the planned future studies to complete the full systematic uncertainty evaluation. We expect this contribution to be negligible since the available simulation is 34 times more than the signal candidates.

4.6.9 Conclusion

As part of future plans, a control check is foreseen to assess the impact of the magnet polarity. The strategy involves dividing the dataset according to the polarity of the magnetic field and comparing the results obtained under each configuration.

Table 4.9: Summary of systematic uncertainties on the gyroemagnetic and gyroelectric factors (g , d) and initial polarization components (P_{0x} , P_{0y} , P_{0z}). The contribution with – have to be defined. *preliminary and conservative estimation.

Systematic Source	g	d	P_{0x}	P_{0y}	P_{0z}
Acceptance modeling	0.03	0.03	0.005	0.005	0.005
Angular resolution *	0.1	$< 10^{-4}$	$< 10^{-4}$	$< 10^{-4}$	0.005
Ghost contamination	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01
Magnetic field map	$< 10^{-4}$	$< 10^{-4}$	$< 10^{-4}$	$< 10^{-4}$	$< 10^{-4}$
Λ z vertex resolution	0.01	0.01	$< 10^{-4}$	$< 10^{-4}$	$< 10^{-4}$
Decay parameter α	0.001	$< 10^{-3}$	$< 10^{-3}$	$< 10^{-3}$	$< 10^{-3}$
Background contribution	0.01	0.01	0.004	0.004	0.004
Data/simulation discrepancy	–	–	–	–	–
Limited simulation size	–	–	–	–	–
Total	0.1	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.01

The most important contributions to the systematic uncertainty are the acceptance modeling and the Ghost contamination. Regarding the angular resolution, the assigned uncertainty is likely an overestimate, further studies are needed to deal with the resolution effects and this preliminary value is expected to significantly reduce. Table 4.9 reports the estimated systematic uncertainties linked to every effect for the fitted parameters, the total value is computed as the sum in quadrature of all the estimated effects.

LHCb Upgrade I and the Upstream Tracker

5.1 LHCb detector: Upgrade I

The LHCb detector operating during Run 1 and Run 2 posed limitations on statistical improvements and broadening of accessible final states (in particular hadronic decays and BSM signatures) due to the presence of the L0 hardware trigger, which would have prevented the signal yields to be proportional to the luminosity and therefore it would have been poorly efficient at higher luminosity. Addressing the challenge of increasing the instantaneous luminosity by a factor five, reaching $\mathcal{L} = 2 \times 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (see Fig. 5.1), necessitated a substantial upgrade of the apparatus [119], [120]. This involved the implementation of a fully software trigger operating at the LHC rate of 30 MHz, allowing an event selection more precise and flexible than in the past. To accommodate this change, all the readout electronics and the tracking system have been upgraded, and a new data acquisition system has been deployed. Most of the subdetectors have been upgraded. Most of the sensors, with the only exception of calorimeters and muon chambers, have been replaced, while the overall geometry of the detector has been kept. The upgrade took place during the Long Shutdown 2 (LS2), from 2019 to 2021, and the taking data started in 2022, with some detector elements still in commissioning. The detector became fully operational in 2024. A brief description of the new detector will follow, with a focus on the Upstream Tracker (UT), since the author of this thesis has contributed to its installation, commissioning and operation phases.

The detector layout is schematically reported in Fig. 5.2, where it is visible that the new tracking system is composed by the upgraded VELO, the TT has been replaced with the UT, while in place of the T stations there is now the Scintillating Fiber (SciFi) Tracker. The VELO sensors now utilize advanced pixel hybrid silicon sensors, enhancing hit resolution and simplifying track reconstruction. These sensors feature a pixel size of $55 \mu\text{m} \times 55 \mu\text{m}$ and require permanent cooling at approximately -20°C throughout their operational lifetime, necessitating a redesign of the cooling system. The two detector halves are arranged in a rotated 'L' configuration, positioned closer to the beam axis at a distance of only 5.1 mm, resulting in a significant improvement in impact parameter resolution with respect to the original LHCb detector. A total of 52 modules are used to cover the full LHCb acceptance, with the enhanced proximity, new pixel geometry, and reduced material contributing to superior performance compared to the previous version.

Additionally, the connection between the VELO detector boxes and the beam pipe within the LHC vacuum system has been modified to integrate a storage cell for the SMOG system, comprising two cylindrical halves, attached to the upstream end of each VELO detector half and moving in sync mode with the detector components. The SMOG system itself has been upgraded to SMOG2, featuring this newly developed storage cell

Figure 5.1: LHCb luminosity as a function of time [121].

that allows for the automated injection of various gaseous targets and enables more precise determination of the target density. The separation of the beam-gas interaction region, now defined by the cell, from the beam-beam collision region allows for simultaneous operation of beam-gas and beam-beam collisions.

Downstream of the magnet, the IT and OT have been replaced by the SciFi, which aims at the reconstruction of momentum resolution comparable with the past runs, but copying with an higher occupancy. It covers the full acceptance, with a size of $6 \text{ m} \times 5 \text{ m}$ in the xy plane. The technology chosen is plastic scintillating fibers, with a diameter of $250 \mu\text{m}$ arranged in multilayered fiber mats. There are still three stations, called T1 T2 and T3, with 4 layers each, in the X-U-V-X orientation, as in the previous detector, to improve the reconstruction of the vertical track coordinates. The detector modules are constructed using a honeycomb structure sandwiched between carbon-fiber layers, incorporating eight SciFi mats, each about 2.4 meters in length and 13 centimeters in width. These mats are arranged in six staggered layers of scintillating fibers. To enhance light collection, a thin mirror is attached to the end of each fiber, reflecting additional light towards the readout side. These mirrors are positioned near the $y = 0$ plane within the experiment, with four fiber mats extending upward and four downward, covering a total height of almost 5 meters. In the vicinity of the $x = 0$ plane, certain modules are specifically designed to accommodate the beam pipe, with one mat being shortened to fit around the pipe. The scintillating fibers optical signals are captured by 128-channel Silicon Photomultiplier (SiPM) arrays, featuring a channel pitch of $250 \mu\text{m}$. At the readout end of each module, 16 SiPM arrays are mounted onto a 3D-printed titanium alloy cooling bar, which is precisely aligned with the four fiber mats and housed within a cold-box.

The RICH detectors have been upgraded, ensuring that PID information is provided with the same precision as in Run 1 and Run 2 while achieving improved single-photon resolution. PID information is also vital for trigger decisions. Although the overall layout of the RICH system has remained the same, the entire photon detection chain has been replaced due to the limitations of the previous hybrid photon detectors, which had embedded front-end electronics restricted to a 1 MHz output rate. These have been re-

Figure 5.2: Side view of the Upgrade I LHCb detector.

placed with multi-anode photomultiplier tubes (MaPMTs) equipped with new front-end electronics. Additionally, due to increased occupancy, the optical system of RICH1 has been redesigned, while the RICH2 system has been left unchanged.

To adapt to the new LHCb readout architecture, the front-end (FE) and readout electronics for the electromagnetic (ECAL) and hadronic (HCAL) calorimeters have undergone a complete redesign and replacement. Additionally, two subdetectors from the previous calorimeter system, the Scintillating Pad Detector (SPD) and the PreShower (PS), have been removed due to their poor relevance in the new LHCb all-software trigger system. The overall configuration of both the ECAL and HCAL remains unchanged to minimize the scope of modifications: the calorimeter modules, photomultiplier tubes (PMTs), Cockcroft Walton (CW) bases, and coaxial cables have been retained without alteration, based on the assumption that they can operate effectively at the radiation levels corresponding to the expected integrated luminosity. However, to maintain the same average anode current in the PMTs under higher luminosity, their HV has been reduced, leading to an increase in the gain of the amplifier-integrator in the FE cards. The FE electronics boards have been completely redesigned to support the 40 MHz readout frequency, while their number and format have been chosen to ensure compatibility with existing crates and racks.

As already anticipated, the most important change performed during the Upgrade is the removal of the L0 trigger, which has fundamentally transformed the data acquisition process at LHCb. Now, the entire detector must be read out at the full 40 MHz LHC rate, with event selection managed by a fully software-based trigger system. The new dataflow structure is illustrated in Fig. 5.3. On average, only 30 MHz of the input

Figure 5.3: Data flow of Run 3, from LHC bunch crossing rate of 40 MHz to data storage and offline data processing.

corresponds to non-empty proton-proton collisions, which are the input for the trigger decisions at LHCb. The massive 4 TB/s of incoming data is processed by the event builder (EB) CPU farm, which aggregates the data from each subdetector and transfers it to the high-level trigger. The first trigger stage, HLT1, is entirely software-based and optimized for graphic processing units (GPUs). HLT1 conducts a partial reconstruction of events to identify those of interest, reducing the data rate by a factor of 30 and producing an output rate of 1 MHz. In the Allen framework [122], real-time partial event reconstruction and selection on the input data are developed, utilizing 162 NVIDIA RTX A5000 GPU cards, one per EB node during the 2022 data taking, two during 2023 and three from August 2024. GPUs are particularly well-suited for the HLT1 tasks, as each physics event is independent, allowing for parallel processing across the threads of the graphics card while maintaining high throughput. The Allen algorithms take full advantage of GPU parallelism, even when reconstructing single tracks within an event.

These selected events are temporarily stored in a 40 PB buffer while the detector undergoes real-time alignment and calibration. Afterward, the events are processed by the second trigger stage, HLT2, where a full event reconstruction is performed using the most up-to-date detector parameters. HLT2 employs optimized reconstruction algorithms that run on a CPU farm to select events using information from the entire LHCb detector. Finally, the events chosen by HLT2 are saved to disk, with a writing bandwidth limit of 10 GB/s, and further processed offline by LHCb software to generate the final datasets for analysis.

5.2 Upstream Tracker

The UT [120] is a the silicon strip subdetector in place of the previous TT subdetector. The latter contained gaps due to non-overlapping sensors, misalignment between the top and bottom detector halves, and the beam pipe and its necessary clearance. To improve the performance, the new subdetector is required to cover the full LHCb acceptance and reach a 99% single hit efficiency. The role of the UT in the LHCb experiment is crucial in the software trigger for the reconstruction of charged particle trajectories. The UT hits are combined with the VELO tracks and a first estimate of the momentum is obtained, with a relative resolution of about 15%, which helps in speeding up the matching with SciFi hits, since only for particles with $p_T > 0.2 \text{ GeV}/c$ the momenta is computed.

Figure 5.4: Picture of UT, the staves, a module and a sensor.

When building Long tracks, it is possible that the VELO and T tracks do not match and consequently create false tracks, called ghost tracks, since they are several meters apart. The UT plays an important role in the ghost rate reduction, decreasing it by a factor of two. Finally, it is also fundamental to reconstruct particles which decay after the VELO, such as long-lived particles, mainly Λ and K_S^0 .

The installation of the UT began in 2019 and extended over the Long Shutdown 2, continuing until 2023. The installation was successfully completed in March, marking the beginning of data acquisition for the year. Following this, the UT underwent a commissioning phase to ensure its readiness for effective data collection. The author actively participated in the on-site installation at CERN, contributing to the assembly of various peripheral electronics, particularly the DCBs, high voltage (HV) connectors, and service connectors between the interior and exterior of the UT box. Additionally, the author was involved in mounting the staves inside the box in the cleanroom at CERN (Fig. 5.5) and preparing a substantial portion of the power system, including HV and low voltage (LV) cables. To provide a better understanding of the different parts involved in the contributions, the following section will detail the structure of the detector and its electronics.

The UT is composed of four layers, each one divided into two halves which close around the beampipe, the so called A-side and C-side, the first closest to the access to the cavern and the latter on the opposite side, closer to the cooling plant. The silicon sensors are arranged on carbon fiber structures called staves, with dimensions of 99.5 mm x 1640 mm, as pictured in Fig. 5.4. In the first and last layers the staves and therefore the strips are vertically oriented, while in the central layers they are tilted by $\pm 5^\circ$, in order to increase the resolution on the vertical coordinate. Each stave has modules on both sides, alternating the modules and the readout electronics, with the aim of covering the full vertical acceptance. A z -staggered arrangement of the staves with horizontal overlaps

Figure 5.5: Completed mounting of the UT A-side in the clean room with part of the UT team. The author of this thesis is the first from the right [123].

of 10 mm ensures complete horizontal coverage. Additionally, specialized sensors are employed in the innermost region to maximize the active area near the beam pipe. The 2 most upstream layers host 16 staves each, while the other layers have 18 staves each. The staves are enclosed in a box in order to keep them thermally insulated and protected from light and air. To prevent condensation, dry nitrogen is used and each staff is equipped with a dedicated cooling loop. A CO₂ cooling system connects to the box with an S-shaped titanium cooling pipe running inside the staves. It cools down the sensors with a target working-point temperature (-5° C), to prevent thermal runaway in presence of radiation damage, to reduce the leakage current, and extracts the power dissipated by the read-out chips (Table 5.1).

Table 5.1: SALT ASIC specifications.

Variable	Specification
Input / Output pitch	80 μ m / 140 μ m
Total power dissipation	< 768 mW
Radiation hardness	0.3 MGy
Sensor input capacitance	1.6–12 pF
Noise	$\approx 1000 e^{-}$ @10 pF + $50 e^{-}$ /pF
Maximum cross-talk	Less than 5% between channels
Signal polarity	Both electron and hole collection
Dynamic range	Input charge up to $\approx 30,000 e^{-}$
Linearity	Within 5% over dynamic range
Pulse shape and tail	$T_{peak} \approx 25$ ns, amplitude after $2 \times T_{peak} < 5\%$ of peak
Gain uniformity	Uniformity across channels within $\approx 5\%$
ADC bits	6 bits (5 bits for each polarity)
ADC sampling rate	40 MHz
DSP functions	Pedestal and MCM subtraction, zero suppression
Output formats	Non-zero suppressed, zero suppressed
Calibration modes	Analogue test pulses, digital data loading
Output serialiser	Three to five serial e-links, at 320 Mbit/s
Slow controls interface	I2C
Fast digital signals interface	Differential, SLVS

Figure 5.6: 3D view of the UT system [119].

The box is itself divided into two halves and mounted on rails so that the two parts can be opened at need. To allow the opening without putting strain on electronic cables, optical fibers and cooling fluid pipes, four movable cable chains are mounted, which host the mentioned services. They are connected to four service bays on the fixed racks, located on both sides of the detector, house the low voltage boards that supply power to the near detector electronics and hybrids, as well as patch panels that distribute HV to the silicon detectors. A schematic picture of the system is reported in Fig. 5.6.

Following their assembly, the UT staves were transported to CERN, where a dedicated clean room was prepared. This facility was equipped with a frame designed for mounting the staves onto the structure. The staves were stored in a special cabinet with a controlled environment, maintained with dry air, and kept in a vertical orientation to minimize mechanical stress. The installation process involved progressively mounting the staves by sub-layers, ensuring that they passed quality tests before being blocked. Each layer underwent thorough testing after installation to verify the connectivity of e-links, I2C communication, LV and HV. The actual mounting process involved transferring the staves from the 'stave mount,' a high-precision stainless steel structure, to the box structure. The frame without the installed staves can be seen in Fig.5.7 (left), taken during the installation of services on the box. The fully installed periphery electronics processing interface (PEPI) and staves on the A-side are shown in Fig.5.7 (right), within the clean room.

The staves are made by UT modules which are composed of silicon sensors and front-end readout electronics, glued and bonded to dataflex cables [124]. The silicon microstrip sensors have been developed in 4 different types, employed depending on their position in the layer to cope with different occupancy. The A-type have a p-in-n technology to be used in the outer region of the detector, with 512 strips and $187.5 \mu\text{m}$ pitch; the hybrids host 4 ASICs. All the other types use the n-in-p technology since they are displaced around the beam pipe and can handle more extreme radiation doses, with 1024 strips and a pitch of $93.5 \mu\text{m}$. The type C and D have a length which is half that of the other types. The D-type have a circular cut-out to fit around the beam pipe, as visible in Fig.5.7

Figure 5.7: (Left) the author installing the services for the box. (Right) one side of the UT in the clean room, after the completion of the staves installation.

(right).

The front end ASIC is the Silicon ASIC for LHCb Tracking (SALT), which uses a CMOS 130 nm technology chip with 128 channels. The SALT incorporates an analog processor along with a low-power (less than 1 mW/channel), high-speed (40 MSps) 6-bit ADC per channel. This is followed by a digital signal processor (DSP) block, a data formatting block and a serializer block. The DSP performs pedestal subtraction, mean common mode subtraction and zero suppression. More precisely, the processing chain starts assigning masks to the channels to identify the ones which are faulty or noisy. These masks are established during dedicated noise calibration runs. The following step involves processing the raw ADC samples through a pedestal subtraction block to determine the baseline position for each channel. Since implementing pedestal calculation directly within the ASIC is challenging, the actual pedestal values will instead be calculated using high-level emulation software based on noise calibration data. These values are then uploaded to the ASIC memories for baseline determination. Following pedestal subtraction, a common mode suppression algorithm is applied, specifically utilizing the simplest version of Mean Common Mode Suppression, which assumes consistent common mode noise across the ASIC. This algorithm uses all 128 channels (excluding masked ones) to estimate the common noise value. The final processing step involves zero-suppression, which aims to efficiently reject false hits. The SALT zero-suppression algorithm uses a discrimination threshold, individually tuned for each channel based on noise run data. Careful studies are required to properly select these thresholds, balancing the suppression factor of raw data with hit detection efficiency. Setting thresholds too low could lead to an unmanageable data stream, while overly high thresholds might reject channels with weaker signals, possibly due to charge sharing, thereby degrading single hit resolution and potentially impacting the UT hit efficiency. After processing, the data is encoded and formatted into a raw bank structure that includes a header and a data body. Then, data packets are stored in a local on-chip memory, which acts as a derandomizing buffer and serialized through multiple data links known as e-links. The

Figure 5.8: High voltage and low voltage cables preparation, installation on the backplanes and in the cable chains.

number of active e-links, ranging between 3 and 5, is determined by optimizing the use of the available output bandwidth while preventing persistent memory overflow. In the UT detector, the number of active e-links for each chip is fixed based on the anticipated data rate. The ASIC is controlled via two different interfaces. One is the timing and fast signal control (TFC), which distributes clocks and fast and beam-synchronous commands. The TFC delivers the 40 MHz clock and other commands synchronised with the experiment clock. The second one is the ECS, the experiment control system, which configures and monitors back-end and front-end electronics, in particular for the UT, the ASIC through an I2C interface. The specifications of the SALT chip are in Table 5.1.

The power subsystem is organized into five separate areas for sourcing and distribution. The counting room houses the HV bulk power rack along with the housekeeping power. HV cables are fed through the detector box wall end directly connect to the staves thanks to HV connectors. The UT sensors require a bias voltage between 300 and 500 V, with the expected leakage current being below 1 mA in the central region and under 0.5 mA for the rest of the detector. To minimize the maximum current and the associated voltage drop over the approximately 150-meter cable path from the counting room to the cavern, the HV is divided into 16 ground-isolated paths, one dedicated to each quadrant, meaning one fourth of each layer.

The cavern is equipped with the bulk LV units and PEPI unit signal conditioners. The LV power for the UT hybrids and on-detector readout chain electronics is provided by 12 power supplies, providing 144 8V/50A channels to four service bays situated around the UT detector. Due to the cable length (approximately 80 meters for power supplies in the counting room and 20-30 meters for those on the balcony racks) and the substantial expected current load, the voltage drop in the cables is significant and cannot be ignored. To address this, the MARATON (MAGnetic field and RADIATION TOLerant) system from

Figure 5.9: Author on the right mounting a DCB.

W.I.E.N.E.R is used. These power supplies are known for providing low noise, low ripple floating channels, and feature remote sensing capability. They have been extensively used in high-energy physics applications and have demonstrated high reliability.

The assembly of both LV and HV cables took place at CERN during the LS2 and the author contributed to their construction, some picture are reported in Fig. 5.8.

Read-out chain

The UT hybrids are thin flex circuits, hosting the front-end electronics, the SALT ASICs, and the sensors. The latter are glued and wire bonded to the front-end electronics and come in two different types. The VERA hybrids, containing 4 SALT chips, are used across most of the detector. In contrast, the SUSI hybrids, each equipped with 8 chips, are specifically designed for the central region, where the strip density is twice as high. To fully cover the UT, 888 VERA hybrids and 80 SUSI hybrids are required. They have been designed and built by INFN Milano, of which the author is part. To power the hybrids and to bring the signal out, two types of passive flex cables are used: directly on the stave we find the dataflex cables which are then connected to ‘pigtailed’ which connect the stave to the PEPI. The last one is housed in the so called PEPI boxes, which is responsible for the control and readout of the detector thanks to 24 backplanes, 24 pigtail power breakout boards (P2B2s), and 248 data and control boards (DCBs). Each DCB supports one master GBTx, one GBT-SCA, six data GBTx chips, one VTRx, and two or three VTTx chips; the assembly on the DCB was accomplished through the use of optical mezzanines and took place at CERN along with their test and the addition of a thermal paste. The author was involved in their preparation and pictures are reported in Fig. 5.9. The master GBTx allows the DCB not only to bring out the signal from the detector but also to bring in information and commands, making the communication bidirectional. A GBTx can handle up to ten e-links in 80-bit mode, creating a GBT data frame.

The final step of the data processing chain is the creation and serialization of transport frames using the GBT data protocol, which are converted into optical signals and transmitted via fibers to the back-end TELL40 electronics boards for further processing [124]. The TELL40 is designed to house four identical, autonomous mezzanine cards called AMC40. Each AMC40 card processes data from 24 optical links. The FPGA on the AMC40 decodes and aligns the data from these links according to the BCID, constructing each event data packet. The event data is then processed through a UT-specific data processing block before being transmitted to the computer farm. The firmware has been developed in five different flavours to cope with different occupancy in the detec-

tor, reading a different number of ASICs and e-links depending on the position in the layer. It can work both in zero-suppressed and non-zero-suppressed mode, the last one is useful to take calibration data or during special runs.

5.2.1 UT commissioning and integration in global LHCb data taking

The author participated in the UT commissioning phase and contributed to the data acquisition within the LHCb global system. This section will outline the key aspects of the initial phase of commissioning and present the early performance results of the UT.

The commissioning process can be categorized into three primary objectives: ensuring the detector safety, optimizing data readout procedures, and maintaining high data quality. Successful completion of these steps is critical for the UT to operate effectively and fulfill its role in physics data collection.

To maintain the detector safety and ensure it operates under nominal conditions, a comprehensive alarm system was implemented. This system monitors critical parameters such as humidity inside the detector box, the temperature of the staves and electronics, as well as current and voltage levels. Custom monitoring panels were developed, with alarms directly linked to sensors embedded within the detector. Moreover, a Detector Control System (DCS) is in place to automatically respond if any monitored parameter deviates from the set thresholds. The staves are cooled using a CO₂ system, while water cooling is employed for the peripheral electronics, maintaining the temperature within the required nominal range.

With the detector stability assured, the next focus was on efficient data extraction. A major task during commissioning was the development and optimization of the firmware, which is crucial for smooth and efficient data acquisition. Simultaneously, the Experiment Control System (ECS) was developed to manage and configure both back-end and front-end electronics, providing a robust debugging tool throughout the commissioning period.

Lastly, it is crucial to develop tools for assessing the quality of the detector. To this end, we analyzed noise levels and identified any noisy channels. During the initial stages of commissioning, numerous datasets were collected in bypass mode, meaning without the serialization of the Tell40, for the purpose of hybrid characterization and to demonstrate the detector behavior. These tests were conducted both before and after the installation in the cavern, allowing us to carefully compare the results.

The data collected consists of ADC (Analog to Digital Converter) values for each channel (strip), referred to as raw ADCs. From these values, we can calculate the pedestal (Ped) for each channel j , which is defined as

$$Ped_j = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N S_{ji},$$

where S_{ji} represents the ADC value of the channel j in event i , and N is the total number of events. The pedestal provides an average value of the noise in the channel, essentially representing the baseline noise level in the absence of a signal.

Additionally, we define the Mean Common Mode (MCM) noise, which reflects the fluctuation in the signal baseline over time, calculated as

$$MCM = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n (S_j - Ped_j),$$

where S_j and Ped_j are the signal and pedestal values of channel j in the event i , respectively, and n is the total number of channels considered. In our study, an ASIC served as the unit of analysis to identify any variations among the chips, thus n equals 128. We further define the ADC Common Mode Subtracted (CMS) noise as the raw ADC value with the pedestal and MCM value subtracted,

$$\text{CMS} = \text{ADC} - \text{Ped} - \text{MCM},$$

this adjustment centers the distribution around zero.

As anticipated, the noise across the 128 channels follows a Gaussian distribution, consistent with the central limit theorem, which states that the sum of numerous independent, random noise sources tends to form a normal distribution. Comparative tables were generated to evaluate the raw and CMS noise levels across different detector layers, with an example shown in Fig. 5.10. Notably, the noise in the innermost part of the detector is generally lower compared to the outer regions, where it typically ranges between 0.7 and 1.3 ADC units, provided no issues are detected. When comparing the noise of the same chip in tests conducted both in the cavern and in the clean room on the surface, the results were consistent, confirming that no significant changes occurred. This compatibility was also observed for the pedestal values.

After calculating the CMS noise, we determine the mean value across events, excluding outliers and ensuring at least 50 events per channel. Channels with noise levels exceeding twice the mean or falling below half the mean are flagged as bad channels, with the latter criterion specifically targeting dead channels. We verified that this selection remains stable even with reasonable adjustments to the thresholds. Additionally, we impose a requirement on the pedestal value, excluding any channels with a pedestal exceeding ± 25 ADC units to prevent saturation issues. Examples of identified noisy channels are shown in Fig. 5.11.

In total, approximately 0.16% of the channels are classified as bad, primarily due to noticeable pedestal shifts or elevated noise levels. Within this subset, 72% are located on the A side, with 20% concentrated in channel 0 of the first chip, a commonly observed phenomenon. Notably, 27% of chips containing at least one bad channel actually have more than two, with 89% of these being SUSY-type chips on the first stave.

Accurate information about pedestal, noise, and bad channels is essential for maintaining a well-calibrated detector during data acquisition. As previously mentioned, the pedestal and noise values must be input into the SALT ASIC to facilitate pedestal subtraction and CMS calculation. These parameters are also critical for setting the thresholds for each module to enable effective zero suppression. Bad channels, on the other hand, need to be masked to prevent the collection of irrelevant data. To automatize these processes, a specialized software tool called VETRA [125] has been developed and integrated into the official LHCb software framework. Beyond offline analysis, VETRA automates calibration tasks, such as computing pedestals and thresholds from End of Fill data—non-zero suppressed data gathered in the absence of the LHC beam. These parameters are subsequently updated in the ASICs via the ECS, ensuring that zero-suppressed data are acquired with precise noise characterization. The author developed the bad channel tagging software, which has been incorporated into VETRA to mask identified bad channels during data acquisition, preventing them from overloading storage or skewing results. Proper data collection also necessitates both spatial and temporal alignment of the detector. The latter is crucial to ensure synchronisation of the experiment with the LHC clock, while the first is needed to have a correct position information. Data collected with proper zero suppression are used to compute the alignment, first a

Figure 5.11: (Left) identified bad channel in Chip 3 of module UTbX_4AB_M2, (right) Chip 2 of module UTaX_4AT_M2 with only good channels. (Top) Noise as function of the 129 channels in the chip, (bottom) ADC values as a function of the channels in the chip.

Figure 5.12: Monitoring plots: (left) hitmap of one UT layer, (right) Landau distribution of ADC counts in all UT layers.

fine timing alignment followed by a coarse timing alignment using a larger dataset, with the resulting configuration being imported into the ECS.

Real-time monitoring is a crucial tool for assessing data quality. A sample of the captured data is sent to the computing farm to monitor key metrics in real-time, such as the number of hits per sensor, error information, and analog response. This process utilizes the MONET software [126] developed within the LHCb framework. The plots in Fig. 5.12 illustrate the expected Landau distribution and the UT hit map, which are regularly reviewed during data acquisition to ensure the detector optimal performance.

5.3 Dipole moment measurement prospects with LHCb Upgrade I

As previously discussed, the most significant advancement in Upgrade I is the implementation of the fully software-based trigger. This new system provides the flexibility needed to select new channels, which can be leveraged for measuring electromagnetic dipole moments. As previously outlined, during Run 1 and Run 2, no dedicated trigger using T tracks was available, limiting the potential to utilize charm decays despite their higher cross-section compared to beauty decays. Consequently, we focused on the $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decay, benefiting from the highly efficient trigger on muons tracks.

For Run 3, we have developed specific HLT2 lines that directly target T tracks, although at the time of writing, the HLT1 stage is still under development. The following lines, which involve charm decays, have already been integrated into the LHCb trigger system:

- $\Xi_c^0 \rightarrow \Xi^- \pi^+, \Xi^- \rightarrow \Lambda \pi^-$
- $\Xi_c^+ \rightarrow \Xi^- \pi^+ \pi^+, \Xi^- \rightarrow \Lambda \pi^-$
- $\Xi_c^0 \rightarrow \Xi^- \pi^- \pi^+ \pi^+, \Xi^- \rightarrow \Lambda \pi^-$
- $\Xi_c^0 \rightarrow \Lambda K^- \pi^+$
- $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda \pi^- \pi^+ \pi^+$
- $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda K^- \pi^+ \pi^+$

Among these decays, those involving two-body final states are expected to exhibit the highest polarization, as polarization is less diluted across multiple resonance decay chains.

Therefore, the first and second channels are anticipated to be the most promising. Additionally, other lines have been implemented to enhance the results presented in this thesis by increasing statistical power, as well as to explore additional channels:

- $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$
- $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$
- $J/\psi \rightarrow \Lambda \bar{\Lambda}$
- $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow \Lambda_c^+ \mu^- \bar{\nu}_\mu$, $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda X$

5.3.1 HLT2 trigger for Long-living particles

A brief description of the trigger strategy for T tracks follows[127]. To select $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ and $K_S \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays within the magnet region three steps are required: track selection, identification of secondary vertices, and fitting of these secondary vertices. Initially, tracks are preselected based on momentum and track quality criteria. For Long and Downstream tracks, vertex candidates can be identified by the sum of the reconstructed invariant masses of the daughter particles, as measured at their first point of detection. This method provides a good approximation of the mother particle's mass when the decay occurs close to the first measurement, making it an effective way to filter potential vertex candidates. However, when dealing with T tracks, the decay can take place several meters away from the first measurement, requiring different selection criteria. It is exploited the fact that the dipole magnet only bends in the xz plane and is nearly linear in the yz plane. First, roughly 50% of possible candidates are removed imposing that the daughter particles have the same sign in t_y to exclude track pairs with large opening angles. Secondly, track pairs that do not intersect at least 1 m from the interaction point are further rejected, reducing the number of candidates by an additional 60%.

The vertex position is determined by a χ^2 fit, where tracks are initially extrapolated to a starting point. For Long and Downstream tracks, this point is the closest approach of the trajectories, which is generally well approximated throughout the entire tracking system. In the case of T tracks, however, the states are only defined at their first and last measurements within the SciFi detector. To extrapolate these states to a point within the magnet, a 5th-order Runge-Kutta method is employed for the first iteration, with subsequent iterations using polynomial interpolation. Although performing a full extrapolation in every iteration would improve vertex resolution, it would significantly reduce the throughput, making it unsuitable for use in the real time trigger system. The vertex resolution is significantly enhanced by using the yz intersection as the starting point for the fit instead of the default closest approach point. Further improvement in vertex resolution can be achieved through offline fitting.

For various modes, the flexibility of HLT2 can be leveraged by requiring the reconstruction of a signal decay signature before running the remaining reconstruction and selection procedures. For example, in the decay $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$, where $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ is reconstructed as Long tracks and $\Lambda \rightarrow p\pi^-$ is reconstructed using T tracks, it can be mandated that the $J/\psi \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ must be identified first before fitting the T tracks and calculating their PIDs. This method helps reducing the impact on throughput. However, in modes without a clear signature, it is necessary to filter the tracks first to minimize the significant effects of track fitting, PID calculation, and combinatorial complexity. To achieve this, a pair of CatBoost binary classifiers is employed: the first classifier identifies potential signal tracks, and the second classifier pinpoints track pairs likely originating

from a common vertex within the magnet region. A single track MVA selection is used to identify probable signal tracks, i.e., tracks originating from a Λ or K_S^0 decay that itself originates from a prompt weak decay. This method offers enhanced background rejection and signal efficiency, although it introduces a greater dependency on the decay channel. The training sample consists of simulated $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ events. For training, tracks are labeled as signal if they are truth-matched to a proton or pion produced in a Λ decay at least 2.5 m from the interaction point and have a Λ_b^0 grandparent. The tracks must also be within acceptance ($2 < \eta < 5$) and have $p_T > 75$ MeV, resulting in 38457 signal tracks. To ensure that the signal and background samples are of equal size, a random selection of 38457 background tracks is used for training. A quarter of the sample is set aside for evaluation, while the remaining 75% is used for training.

Initially, all track variables were utilized as input features for training the BDT. However, to reduce the model's complexity, the number of features was later limited to the five most influential ones, which are:

1. transverse momentum,
2. radial distance from the beam pipe,
3. momentum in the z-direction,
4. y -position of the first measurement,
5. pseudorapidity.

After selecting individual tracks, they are paired in a second MVA. Tracks that are unlikely to originate from a common vertex in the magnet region are excluded. Several derived discriminating variables serve as features for the track pair BDT, including:

1. the z and y positions of the straight-line intersections of the tracks in the yz plane, leveraging the approximate straight-line behavior of tracks in this plane,
2. the absolute differences in the y and x slopes,
3. the separation of the tracks in y ,
4. the radial separation of the tracks,
5. the product of the signs of the y slopes.

The same $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\Lambda$ sample is used for training the track pair selection, with any track pair corresponding to a true K_S^0 or Λ considered as signal. Λ originating from the hard scatter account for roughly 10% of the training sample, which comprises approximately 44000 signal pairs, with a randomly selected 44000 background pairs used for training. The model is trained using 100 iterations per tree.

The working point for the single track MVA is set to a BDT score > 0.3 , which eliminates about 57% of the background while retaining 84% of the signal. For the track pair MVA, the working point is set to a BDT score > 0.75 , rejecting 91.5% of track pairs and 51.1% of single tracks, while retaining 75-90% of the signal, depending on the mode. Applying the track filtering reduces the impact on throughput by approximately 80%. The lower background rejection is attributed to increased background under 2023 conditions. Performance remains relatively consistent across the momentum range considered, with decreased performance at lower momentum, primarily affecting signal pions. Under

nominal conditions, the filter is expected to reduce the number of T tracks considered from 50 to 5 per event. For 2024, the model will be expanded with additional modes to reduce channel dependency. In the future, performance might be further enhanced using a more sophisticated model, such as a GNN. With the deployment of the new vertexing and kinematic fitting frame, there is the plan to integrate in HLT2 during the 2025 run the new DOCA and IP computations, after having proved at offline level that they are very effective.

5.3.2 Sensitivity

Anticipating the opportunities presented by the Upgrade I detector, we can estimate the sensitivity for measuring electromagnetic dipole moments by the conclusion of Run 4, which will take place after the Long Shutdown 3 period and is scheduled from 2029 to 2032, as shown in Fig. 5.1. This phase, known as the high-luminosity-LHC (HL-LHC), will operate at a luminosity of $2 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, which is 7.5 times greater than the original design specification. By the end of this period, LHCb is expected to accumulate up to 50 fb^{-1} of data, allowing for the study of known phenomena with unprecedented precision and the potential discovery of extremely rare events.

For the Λ MDM, our projections indicate an uncertainty of the order of $10^{-4} \mu_N$, representing one order of magnitude improvement over current measurements [46]. This level of precision will enable the first CPT symmetry test at the per mille level using Λ baryons. Regarding the Λ EDM, we anticipate two orders of magnitude enhancement in sensitivity, reaching an accuracy of approximately 10^{-18} e cm .

Conclusions

This thesis presents the first measurement of the electric and magnetic dipole moments of the Λ baryon performed at a collider experiment, using data collected by the LHCb collaboration during Run 1 and Run 2 of the LHC, corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 9 fb^{-1} . Moreover, it includes the first-ever measurement of the magnetic dipole moment of the $\bar{\Lambda}$ antibaryon, which, combined with that of the Λ baryon, enables an unprecedented test of the CPT symmetry in this particle-antiparticle system. These measurements contribute to the search for CP violation beyond the SM and provide valuable experimental input for QCD-based models of baryon structure. When the contribution of an electric dipole moment is included, and it is assumed to be equal in magnitude but opposite in sign for the particle and antiparticle, the preliminary (blinded) results for the adimensional gyromagnetic and gyroelectric factors are

$$\begin{aligned}g_{\Lambda} &= xxx \pm 0.2 \pm 0.1, \\g_{\bar{\Lambda}} &= xxx \pm 0.2 \pm 0.1, \\d &= xxx \pm 0.2 \pm 0.05,\end{aligned}$$

corresponding to the following magnetic and electric dipole moments, expressed in units of the nuclear magneton:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_{\Lambda} &= xxx \pm 0.08 \pm 0.04, \\\mu_{\bar{\Lambda}} &= xxx \pm 0.08 \pm 0.04, \\\delta &= xxx \pm 0.08 \pm 0.02,\end{aligned}$$

The first uncertainties are statistical and the second systematic. In all cases, the total uncertainties are dominated by the limited size of the data sample. Therefore, these measurements can be significantly improved in the future with the addition of Run 3 data currently being recorded by the LHCb detector, and beyond. The results presented here are obtained under a conservative scenario, where the contribution from Ghost events is limited to 10%, even though this requirement reduces the usable statistics to roughly one-third of the available candidates. This compromise was chosen because simulation studies show that the residual resolution is symmetric when the Ghost contribution is kept at that level. A dedicated optimization of the Ghost suppression criteria is planned, with the aim of retaining a larger signal yield while still controlling resolution effects, thereby maximizing the sensitivity to both the electric and magnetic dipole moments.

The methodology developed for this thesis is thoroughly described and lays the groundwork for future improvements and developments. Its validity is supported by

studies on pseudoexperiments, on full Monte Carlo simulations, and on the control sample of $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$ decays, which exhibits, as expected, no significant polarization. The systematic uncertainties, below current and future statistical uncertainties, are not expected to be a limiting factor, and will be possible to improve by using additional Monte Carlo simulations and refinements in the analysis procedure.

The Λ baryons, from $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays, are reconstructed at distances between 3.0 m and 7.6 m from the primary pp collision point. This study marks the first use of the extended decay volume of the LHCb detector for physics measurements, demonstrating the feasibility of utilizing tracks solely reconstructed with hits in the final tracking stations, the so-called T tracks, for a wide variety of other LHCb analyses. A key enabler of this enhancement of the detector performance is the development of a new decay tree reconstruction algorithm, the Forward Tree Fitter, which performance on Run 2 data is presented here for the first time. The FTF achieves an efficiency exceeding 80% with significantly reduced dependence on the Λ decay z coordinate, a very significant improvement over the standard Decay Tree Fitter extensively used in LHCb, which limited the usable decaying volume. Enhanced momentum and vertex resolutions further strengthen the sensitivity to the dipole moment measurements. To ensure reliability, ad hoc techniques have been introduced to evaluate the detector and reconstruction performance directly on data and compare it with simulations.

Lastly, the thesis reports on the Upgrade I of the LHCb detector, with a particular focus on the Upstream Tracker, to which the author contributed during its assembly, installation, and commissioning phases. This new detector opens the way for new and more precise measurements, and higher data throughput during Run 3 and beyond. The measurement of the Λ electric and magnetic dipole moments can be significantly improved with the data collected during Run 3 of the LHC, taking profit of the dedicated trigger lines that have been implemented specifically for largely displaced decays exploiting T tracks. The increased dataset, combined with improved trigger efficiency, is expected to enhance sensitivity not only through higher statistics in the same decay channel, but also by including additional decay modes involving Λ baryons originating from more abundant charm baryon decays. These future improvements will enhance the precision and scope of Λ baryon and $\bar{\Lambda}$ antibaryon dipole moment measurements, along with the fundamental test of the (cornerstone) CPT symmetry in this particle-antiparticle system, further advancing our understanding of fundamental symmetries in particle physics.

Conclusion in Spanish

Esta tesis presenta la primera medida de los momentos dipolares eléctrico y magnético del barión Λ realizada en un experimento de colisionador, utilizando datos recolectados por la colaboración LHCb durante el Run 1 y Run 2 del LHC, correspondientes a una luminosidad integrada de 9 fb^{-1} . Además, se incluye la primera medida nunca realizada anteriormente del momento dipolar magnético del antibarión $\bar{\Lambda}$, la cual, combinada con la medida correspondiente del barión Λ , permite realizar una prueba sin precedentes de la simetría CPT en este sistema de partícula-antipartícula. Estas medidas contribuyen a la búsqueda de la ruptura de la simetría de CP más allá del Modelo Estándar (SM), y proporcionan información experimental valiosa para los modelos de estructura bariónica basados en QCD.

Cuando se incluye la contribución del momento dipolar eléctrico, suponiendo que sea igual en magnitud pero de signo opuesto para partícula y antipartícula, los resultados preliminares (ocultos) de los factores giromagnéticos son:

$$\begin{aligned}g_{\Lambda} &= xxx \pm 0.2 \pm 0.1, \\g_{\bar{\Lambda}} &= xxx \pm 0.2 \pm 0.1, \\d &= xxx \pm 0.2 \pm 0.05,\end{aligned}$$

correspondientes a los momentos dipolares magnético y eléctrico siguientes:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_{\Lambda} &= xxx \pm 0.08 \pm 0.04, \\ \mu_{\bar{\Lambda}} &= xxx \pm 0.08 \pm 0.04, \\ \delta &= xxx \pm 0.08 \pm 0.02.\end{aligned}$$

Las primeras incertidumbres son estadísticas y las segundas sistemáticas. En todos los casos, las incertidumbres totales están dominadas por el tamaño limitado de la muestra de datos. Por lo tanto, se espera que estas medidas puedan mejorar significativamente en el futuro con la inclusión de los datos de Run 3 que actualmente está registrando el detector LHCb, así como con los conjuntos de datos futuros. Los resultados presentados aquí se han obtenido bajo un escenario conservador, en el que la contribución de eventos Ghost se limita al 10%, aunque esta condición reduce la estadística útil a aproximadamente un tercio de los candidatos disponibles. Esta decisión se basa en estudios de simulación que muestran que la resolución residual permanece simétrica cuando la contribución de Ghost se mantiene en ese nivel. Está prevista una optimización específica de los criterios de supresión de Ghost, con el objetivo de conservar una mayor fracción

de señal sin comprometer el control sobre los efectos de resolución, maximizando así la sensibilidad tanto al momento dipolar eléctrico como al magnético.

La metodología desarrollada en esta tesis se ha descrito ampliamente y establece las bases para futuras mejoras y desarrollos. Su validez está respaldada por simulaciones rápidas (pseudoeperimentos) y completas de Monte Carlo, y el uso de la muestra de control de desintegraciones $B^0 \rightarrow J/\Psi K_S^0$, que, como se espera, no muestra polarización significativa. Las incertidumbres sistemáticas, que se encuentran por debajo de las incertidumbres estadísticas actuales y futuras, no se esperan que constituyan una limitación, y podrán mejorarse con simulaciones adicionales y mejoras del procedimiento de análisis. Los bariones Λ , provenientes de procesos de desintegración $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\Psi \Lambda$, se reconstruyen a distancias de entre 3.0 m y 7.6 m del punto de colisión primario protón-protón. Este estudio representa el primer uso del volumen extendido de desintegración del detector LHCb para medidas físicas, demostrando la viabilidad de utilizar trazas reconstruidas exclusivamente con señales en las estaciones de reconstrucción de trazas más alejadas del punto de interacción, las llamadas trazas T, para una amplia variedad de análisis en LHCb. Un elemento clave de esta mejora en el rendimiento del detector es el desarrollo de un nuevo algoritmo de reconstrucción de cadenas de desintegración, el *Forward Tree Fitter* (FTF), cuya aplicación en los datos del Run 2 se presenta aquí por primera vez. El FTF logra una eficiencia superior al 80% y reduce significativamente la dependencia respecto a la coordenada z de la desintegración del barión Λ , una mejora notable respecto de la herramienta estándar utilizado hasta la fecha en LHCb. Las mejoras asociadas en las resoluciones de momento y vértice aumentan aún más la sensibilidad de las medidas de los momentos dipolares. Para garantizar la fiabilidad, se han desarrollado técnicas específicas para evaluar el rendimiento del detector y de la reconstrucción directamente en los datos y compararlo con simulaciones.

Finalmente, la tesis presenta el *Upgrade I* del detector LHCb, con especial atención al *Upstream Tracker*, en el cual la autora de esta tesis ha participado activamente durante las fases de montaje, instalación y puesta en marcha. Este nuevo detector abre el camino a medidas nuevas y más precisas, y a un mayor rendimiento de adquisición de datos durante el Run 3 y más allá. La medida de los momentos dipolares eléctrico y magnético del barión Λ podrá mejorarse considerablemente con los datos recogidos en el Run 3 del LHC, aprovechando las nuevas líneas de *trigger* dedicadas a desintegraciones desplazadas que usan las trazas T. El aumento de la muestra de datos, combinado con una mayor eficiencia de *trigger*, permitirá mejorar la sensibilidad no solo en el mismo proceso de desintegración sino también incluyendo otros procesos que involucran bariones Λ provenientes de desintegraciones de bariones de encanto, mucho más abundantes. Estas mejoras futuras permitirán aumentar la precisión y el alcance de las medidas de los momentos dipolares del barión Λ y antibarión $\bar{\Lambda}$, así como de la prueba fundamental de ruptura de la simetría CPT (piedra angular del Modelo Estándar) en este sistema de partícula-antipartícula, contribuyendo aún más a nuestro conocimiento de las simetrías fundamentales en la física de partículas.

Conclusion in Italian

Questa tesi presenta la prima misura dei momenti di dipolo elettrico e magnetico del barione Λ effettuata in un esperimento presso un collisore, utilizzando i dati raccolti dalla collaborazione LHCb durante il Run 1 e il Run 2 del LHC, corrispondenti a una luminosità integrata di 9 fb^{-1} . Inoltre, include la prima misura in assoluto del momento di dipolo magnetico dell'antibarione $\bar{\Lambda}$ che, combinata con quella del barione Λ , consente un test senza precedenti della simmetria CPT in questo sistema particella-antiparticella. Queste misure contribuiscono alla ricerca di violazioni di CP oltre il Modello Standard (SM), e forniscono importanti indicazioni sperimentali per i modelli della struttura barionica basati sulla QCD.

corrispondenti ai seguenti momenti magnetici, espressi in unità del magnetone nucleare:

Includendo la possibile presenza di un momento di dipolo elettrico, ipotizzato uguale modulo ma segno opposto tra particella e antiparticella, i risultati preliminari (oscurati) dei fattori giromagnetici adimensionali sono:

$$\begin{aligned}g_{\Lambda} &= xxx \pm 0.2 \pm 0.1, \\g_{\bar{\Lambda}} &= xxx \pm 0.2 \pm 0.1, \\d &= xxx \pm 0.2 \pm 0.05,\end{aligned}$$

corrispondenti ai momenti di dipolo magnetici ed elettrici, espressi in unità di magnetone nucleare:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_{\Lambda} &= xxx \pm 0.08 \pm 0.04, \\ \mu_{\bar{\Lambda}} &= xxx \pm 0.08 \pm 0.04, \\ \delta &= xxx \pm 0.08 \pm 0.02.\end{aligned}$$

Le prime incertezze sono statistiche e le seconde sistematiche. In tutti i casi, le incertezze totali sono dominate dalla dimensione limitata del campione di dati. È quindi previsto che queste misure possano essere migliorate significativamente in futuro grazie all'aggiunta dei dati del Run 3 attualmente in acquisizione dal rivelatore LHCb e nei successivi periodi di raccolta. I risultati qui presentati sono ottenuti in uno scenario conservativo, in cui il contributo degli eventi Ghost è limitato al 10%, sebbene questa selezione riduca la statistica utilizzabile a circa un terzo dei candidati disponibili. Questa scelta è motivata da studi sulle simulazioni che mostrano come la distribuzione della risoluzione resti simmetrica mantenendo la componente Ghost a quel livello. È prevista

un'ottimizzazione dedicata dei criteri di soppressione degli eventi Ghost, con l'obiettivo di trattenere una frazione maggiore del segnale pur mantenendo sotto controllo gli effetti di risoluzione, in modo da massimizzare la sensibilità sia al momento di dipolo elettrico che a quello magnetico.

La metodologia sviluppata in questa tesi è descritta in dettaglio e costituisce la base per futuri miglioramenti e sviluppi. La sua validità è confermata da studi condotti su pseudoesperimenti, simulazioni Monte Carlo, e sull'analisi di un campione di controllo di decadimenti $B^0 \rightarrow J/\psi K_S^0$, che, come atteso, mostra una polarizzazione nulla. Le incertezze sistematiche, inferiori alle attuali e future incertezze statistiche, non rappresentano un limite per la misura, e potranno essere ulteriormente ridotte mediante simulazioni aggiuntive e perfezionamenti della procedura di analisi. I barioni Λ , provenienti dai decadimenti $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$, sono ricostruiti a distanze comprese tra 3.0 m e 7.6 m dal punto primario di interazione pp . Questo studio segna il primo utilizzo del volume di decadimento esteso del rivelatore LHCb per misure di fisica, dimostrando la fattibilità di utilizzare tracce ricostruite esclusivamente attraverso le stazioni di tracking successive al campo magnetico, le cosiddette T tracks. Un fattore abilitante essenziale di questo miglioramento delle prestazioni del rivelatore è lo sviluppo di un nuovo algoritmo di ricostruzione della catena di decadimento, il Forward Tree Fitter, il cui comportamento sui dati del Run 2 viene qui presentato per la prima volta. L'algoritmo FTF raggiunge un'efficienza superiore all'80% e riduce significativamente la dipendenza dalla coordinata z del decadimento del Λ , migliorando sensibilmente le prestazioni rispetto al Decay Tree Fitter standard utilizzato in LHCb. Miglioramenti nella risoluzione in momento e vertice accrescono ulteriormente la sensibilità nella misura dei momenti di dipolo. Per garantire l'affidabilità delle misure, sono state introdotte tecniche dedicate per valutare le prestazioni del rivelatore e della ricostruzione direttamente sui dati, e confrontarle con le simulazioni.

Infine, la tesi riporta una descrizione dell'Upgrade I del rivelatore LHCb, con particolare attenzione al sottosistema Upstream Tracker, al quale l'autrice ha contribuito durante le fasi di assemblaggio, installazione e messa in servizio. Questo nuovo rivelatore aprirà la strada a misure più precise e a una maggiore capacità di raccolta dati durante Run 3 e nei successivi periodi di attività. La misura dei momenti di dipolo elettrico e magnetico del barione Λ potrà essere significativamente migliorata con i dati raccolti durante Run 3 del LHC. Durante questo periodo sono state implementate linee di trigger dedicate ai decadimenti che sfruttano le T tracks. L'aumento della statistica, combinato con una maggiore efficienza di trigger, permetterà di accrescere la sensibilità non solo per lo stesso canale di decadimento, ma anche includendo nuovi canali che coinvolgono barioni Λ provenienti da decadimenti di barioni di charm più abbondanti. Questi miglioramenti futuri permetteranno di incrementare la precisione della misure sui momenti di dipolo del barione Λ , contribuendo a migliorare la nostra comprensione delle simmetrie fondamentali nella fisica delle particelle.

Some additional plots concerning the selection of signal $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ decays are reported here.

Figure A.1: Comparison of HBDT input variables among the three different classes: signal, B^0 peaking background and combinatorial background.

Figure A.3: Caption

Figure A.4: PID variables distributions comparison of (top) proton, (bottom) pion on data and simulation.

Figure A.5: $m(J/\psi\bar{\Lambda})$ invariant mass fit with only antiparticles on Run 2 dataset in the different z regions: (top left) 3–5 m, (top right) 5–6 m, (bottom) 6–7.6 m.

Table A.1: Fit results in 3σ window in the three z regions, on Run 2 data for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\bar{\Lambda}$ candidates, after GNN requirement, only particles decays.

	$3 < z < 5 \text{ m}$	$5 < z < 6 \text{ m}$	$6 < z < 8 \text{ m}$
Signal yield	1719 ± 57	833 ± 47	1351 ± 115
B^0 Peaking background yield	297 ± 23	163 ± 30	447 ± 141
Combinatorial background yield	596 ± 15	468 ± 18	2021 ± 84
Purity	66%	57%	35%
Significance	34	22	22

Table A.2: Fit results in 3σ window in the three z regions, on Run 2 data for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi\bar{\Lambda}$ candidates, after GNN requirement, only antiparticles decays.

	$3 < z < 5 \text{ m}$	$5 < z < 6 \text{ m}$	$6 < z < 8 \text{ m}$
Signal yield	1695 ± 57	840 ± 49	1383 ± 141
B^0 Peaking background yield	286 ± 20	260 ± 48	594 ± 251
Combinatorial background yield	683 ± 14	427 ± 24	1685 ± 154
Purity	64%	55%	38%
Significance	33	21	23

Figure A.6: $m(J/\psi \Lambda)$ invariant mass fit with only particles on Run 2 dataset in the different z regions: (top left) 3–5 m, (top right) 5–6 m, (bottom) 6–7.6 m.

Table A.3: Fit results in 3σ window in the three z regions, on Run 1 data for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda$ candidates, after GNN requirement, only particles decays.

	$3 < z < 5$ m	$5 < z < 6$ m	$6 < z < 8$ m
Signal yield	458 ± 33	230 ± 26	396 ± 73
B^0 Peaking background yield	85 ± 14	15 ± 9	73 ± 62
Combinatorial background yield	346 ± 9	278 ± 8	1011 ± 40
Purity	51%	44%	27%
Significance	15	10	10

Table A.4: Fit results in 3σ window in the three z regions, on Run 1 data for $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow J/\psi \bar{\Lambda}$ candidates, after GNN requirement, only antiparticles decays.

	$3 < z < 5$ m	$5 < z < 6$ m	$6 < z < 8$ m
Signal yield	401 ± 34	206 ± 34	376 ± 66
B^0 Peaking background yield	90 ± 20	67 ± 32	50 ± 53
Combinatorial background yield	288 ± 11	241 ± 15	663 ± 33
Purity	51%	40%	35%
Significance	14	9	11

Figure A.7: $m(J/\psi\bar{\Lambda})$ invariant mass fit with only antiparticles on Run 1 dataset in the different z regions: (top left) 3–5 m , (top right) 5–6 m , (bottom) 6–7.6 m .

Figure A.8: $m(J/\psi\lambda)$ invariant mass fit with only particles on Run 1 dataset in the different z regions: (top left) 3–5 m, (top right) 5–6 m, (bottom) 6–7.6 m.

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Acknowledgments

My PhD has been a journey as rich as it was non-linear. I have learned—at least a little—what it means to do research: to try again and again in different ways, and to feel great satisfaction when something finally makes sense. But I have also learned how to communicate with people, how to organize my time, and even how to dine alone in a restaurant. I learned a new language, and how to face a last-minute move with only a few days' notice. From an academic perspective, this journey has led to the results that make up this thesis, the fruit of much effort and commitment. I discovered that, even when something seems impossible, there is often a way to make it happen.

Yet this PhD has also been a journey of life and change, which would not have been the same without the people I met along the way, as well as those who were already by my side and never stopped being there. I had to face many challenges, not only with the T tracks, but also losing my code and data due to a heavy rain in Milan, and frequent changes of plan for my defense during the past year. After all this, I think I can say that I was forced to learn how to be flexible. So many things happened, and I am proud that I managed to handle them—(perhaps) without going crazy—but it would not have been possible if I had been alone.

First of all, I must thank my two supervisors, without whom this thesis would not have been possible. Thank you, Nicola, for guiding me from my very first steps into research, and for always encouraging me to do better. I have learned so much from you: I treasure your teachings as both a guide to becoming a good researcher and a reminder that nothing is truly impossible. Thank you for giving me so many different experiences over these years... and also for indirectly making me collect the record of four moves in four years! A very special thank you to Fernando, who was in practice my supervisor even before it was official. Thank you for fighting bureaucracy to make my stay possible, for welcoming me with open arms in Valencia, and for making me feel at home in a completely new place. I have always admired your passion and perseverance. Sharing the office with you was a real pleasure: our conversations always filled me with enthusiasm and confidence for the future. I also know I can always count on you for sincere advice and genuine support. I feel lucky not to have had just one supervisor, but two, from whom I have learned both a great love for research and a constant drive for deep understanding. Our discussions have been a source of motivation, and I will always carry with me your example as researchers.

I would also like to thank my colleagues around the world, who have always supported me: those in Milan, Valencia, and Geneva. Thank you, Andrea, for your always brilliant ideas, and a truly special thanks to my Milan desk neighbor, Ziyi, without whom

this analysis would have been much longer and more complicated. When I lost data and code, I don't know how I would have managed without you—always ready to help and to produce countless tuples. Thanks also for your fascinating insights into China and its traditions.

During my year in Valencia, I had wonderful moments. Thank you, Fer, for memories of things I would never have imagined doing, and to my dear friend Aurora, with whom I found someone to laugh (a lot) and also to cry with.

When I moved to CERN I didn't have great expectations, but I found a group of people who truly made me feel at home. We shared nights in the control room, days in the office, countless breaks at R1, but also house parties at Fede's or Chiara's place, trips and sports. With you I didn't just spend precious time inside and outside of work—I felt part of a group, understood, and loved. The support that everyone gives each other is the most precious thing I will carry with me forever. Thank you, Fede, Chiara, Chiara, Sara, Eugi, Lori, Andre, Fede, Simo, Shini and Pietro. The most beautiful thing has been sharing—so many laughs and also a few tears. Thank you, Fede, for understanding me so well. Thank you, Chiara, for always driving us into the most fun adventures. Thank you, Chiara, for always being there. And thank you, Sara, for always having good advice at the right time. I am so grateful to be able to say that I met such good friends.

Through this journey I also met a very special person. Thank you, Ale, for listening to me endlessly and for making me laugh just as much. You always make me feel supported, and it is wonderful to share life with you. For you, many more words would be needed—but maybe on other pages.

Thanks to my friends in Milan and from LCM: between one trip and another, it was wonderful to spend time together in this beautiful city. Thanks also to my lifelong friends, who have always supported me, and to my family, who keep wondering where in the world I am while always making me feel loved and understood. A big hug to Adri and Mario, who have always kept me close to their hearts.

Finally, I would like to sincerely thank all the referees who dedicated their time to reading my thesis and came to Milan to discuss its results. Many of you are part of the LHCb collaboration, and I am very proud and honored to be part of it. Over these years, I have learned what the word collaboration truly means, and every time I think about it I feel both lucky and amazed. Each of us does our own job, but at the same time we are all part of something bigger. In LHCb, differences are not a cause of division, but a source of strength and enrichment. This spirit of collaboration is what I will always carry with me from LHCb.

The author acknowledges support from the ERC Consolidator Grant SELDOM G. A. 771642.

Ringraziamenti

Il mio dottorato è stato un percorso tanto ricco quanto non lineare. Ho imparato (almeno un po') cosa significa fare ricerca: provare e riprovare in tanti modi diversi per poi avere una grande soddisfazione quando finalmente qualcosa ha senso. Ho anche imparato come comunicare meglio con le persone, come organizzarmi, e perfino come cenare da sola in un ristorante. Ho imparato una nuova lingua e anche come affrontare un trasloco con pochi giorni di anticipo. Dal punto di vista accademico, questo viaggio mi ha portato ai risultati che compongono questa tesi, frutto di molta fatica e determinazione. Ho imparato che, anche quando qualcosa sembra impossibile, in realtà si può spesso trovare un modo per realizzarlo.

Ma questo dottorato è stato anche un percorso di vita e di cambiamento, che non sarebbe stato lo stesso senza le persone che ho incontrato lungo questo cammino e senza chi era già al mio fianco e ha continuato ad esserci. Ho affrontato molte sfide, non solo con le T tracks, ma anche perdendo il mio codice e i dati per un temporale a Milano e a causa dei molti cambi di programma per la mia difesa durante quest'ultimo anno. Dopo tutto questo, penso di poter dire di aver imparato ad essere flessibile. Sono successe così tante cose diverse e sono fiera di essere riuscita ad affrontarle senza (forse) impazzire, ma non sarebbe però stato possibile se fossi stata sola.

In primo luogo, non posso non ringraziare i miei due supervisori, senza i quali questa tesi non sarebbe stata possibile. Grazie a Nicola, che mi ha accompagnata sin dai primi passi nel mondo della ricerca, incoraggiandomi a dare sempre il meglio. Ho imparato moltissimo: custodisco i suoi insegnamenti come guida per diventare una buona ricercatrice e per ricordarmi che nulla è davvero irrealizzabile. Grazie per avermi offerto così tante esperienze diverse in questi anni... e anche per avermi indirettamente fatto collezionare il record di quattro traslochi in quattro anni! Un grazie speciale a Fernando, che di fatto è stato il mio supervisore ancora prima di esserlo ufficialmente. Grazie per aver combattuto con la burocrazia pur di permettermi di arrivare lì, per avermi accolta a Valencia a braccia aperte e per avermi fatto sentire a casa in un luogo nuovo e sconosciuto. Ho sempre ammirato la tua passione e la tua perseveranza. Condividere l'ufficio con te è stato un piacere: le nostre conversazioni mi hanno sempre trasmesso entusiasmo e fiducia nel futuro. So di poter sempre contare su di te per consigli sinceri e per un sostegno autentico. Da entrambi i miei supervisori ho imparato l'amore per la ricerca e la spinta verso una comprensione profonda. Le discussioni con voi mi hanno ispirata e motivata, e porterò sempre con me il vostro esempio come ricercatori.

Un ringraziamento ai miei colleghi sparsi per il mondo, che mi hanno sempre supportata: quelli di Milano, di Valencia e di Ginevra. Grazie ad Andrea, per le idee sempre brillanti, e un grazie davvero speciale al mio vicino di scrivania Ziyi, senza il quale

questa analisi sarebbe stata molto più lunga e complicata. Quando ho perso dati e codice, non so come avrei fatto senza di te, sempre pronto ad aiutarmi e a produrre un'infinità di entuple. Grazie anche per avermi affascinata con le tradizioni e il cibo cinese.

Durante il mio anno a Valencia ho vissuto momenti indimenticabili. Grazie a Fer, con cui ho condiviso esperienze che non avrei mai immaginato, e alla mia cara amica Aurora, in cui ho trovato un'amica con cui ridere (tanto) e anche piangere.

Quando mi sono trasferita al CERN non avevo grandi aspettative, ma lì ho incontrato un gruppo di persone che mi ha fatto sentire davvero a casa. Abbiamo condiviso notti in control room, giornate in ufficio, tante pause a R1, ma anche feste da Chiara e da Fede, gite e sport. Con voi non solo ho trascorso tempo prezioso, dentro e fuori dal lavoro, ma mi sono sentita parte di un gruppo: capita, accolta e voluta bene. Il supporto che ognuno dà all'altro, sia nei giorni felici sia in quelli più difficili, è la parte più preziosa che porterò per sempre con me. Grazie a Fede, Chiara, Chiara, Sara, Eugi, Lori, Andre, Fede, Simo, Shini and Pietro. La cosa più bella è stata condividere: tante risate e anche qualche piantino. Grazie Fede per capirmi sempre così bene; grazie Chiara per coinvolgerci sempre in pazze avventure; grazie Chiara per esserci sempre stata e grazie Sara per avere sempre il consiglio giusto al momento giusto.

Durante questo percorso ho incontrato anche una persona davvero speciale. Grazie Ale, per ascoltarmi per ore e ore e per farmi ridere altrettanto. Mi fai sempre sentire supportata ed è davvero bello condividere con te le mie giornate. Per te servirebbero tante altre parole, ma forse su altre pagine.

Grazie ai miei amici di Milano e a quelli di LCM: tra un viaggio e l'altro è stato bello stare insieme. Grazie alle mie amiche storiche, che da sempre mi supportano, e alla mia famiglia, che si chiede sempre da quale parte del mondo mi trovi e mi fa sentire amata e capita. Un abbraccio speciale ad Adri e Mario, che mi tengono stretta al loro cuore da sempre.

Infine, un sincero ringraziamento a tutti i referees che hanno dedicato tempo a leggere la mia tesi e sono venuti a Milano per discuterne i risultati. Molti di voi lavorano in LHCb, io sono davvero orgogliosa e onorata di farne parte. Durante questi anni ho imparato cosa voglia dire davvero la parola collaborazione e ogni volta che mi fermo a pensarci mi sento sia fortunata sia affascinata. Ognuno fa il suo lavoro, ma allo stesso tempo siamo tutti parte di qualcosa di più grande. In LHCb le differenze non sono causa di divisione, ma una fonte di forza e arricchimento. Lo spirito della collaborazione è ciò che porterò per sempre con me da LHCb.